

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 7.7. 1st Updated SEL Report with Recommendations Public

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1. Summary

The core focus of this Deliverable D7.7 is to continue and update the analysis and assessment of potential and actual societal, ethical and legal challenges related to cybercrime investigation activities presented in Deliverable D7.6. While D7.6 outlined the entire societal, ethical and legal framework for LEAs fighting with cybercrime and already included imminent changes to this framework by new regulatory instruments at international and supranational level, D7.7 updates the analysis and assessment of D7.6 in and to those areas which have evolved further.

The first part of this Deliverable D7.7 comprises chapters 3.–12. which are dedicated to the analysis of the international legal frameworks consisting of the relevant international treaties at global level of the United Nations as well as at regional level of the Council of Europe. Further, the available rules and regulations at supranational level of the European Union are examined in the following ten key areas of interest:

- *Chapter 3* presents the human rights dimension any cybercrime investigation activity has to be aware of and respect with an analysis of the United Nations framework, the Council of Europe framework and the European Union framework.
- *Chapter 4* provides an overview of the relevant legal frameworks for data protection at European level governing cybercrime investigations consisting of the Council of Europe rules and regulations, on the one hand, and the European Union rules and regulations, on the other.
- *Chapter 5* provides an overview of the legal frameworks for victims' rights established in international treaties at global level by the United Nations and at regional level by the Council of Europe as well as by the European Union.
- *Chapter 6* looks at the procedural standards governing online investigations for retrospective and prospective purposes and points out the legal impact of automating large-scale data collection and mining for criminal investigations as well as for purposes of preventing cybercrime.
- *Chapter 7* examines the impact of the likely collection of copyrighted material when operating a crawler and addresses potential violations of license agreements, access restrictions and/or website terms & conditions in the course of collecting data automatically online.
- *Chapter 8* deals with the use of covert tools enabling automated interactive communication with cybercriminals and highlights the international fragmentation of the law regarding (covert) engagement in communication with potential suspects including the use of an agent provocateur.
- *Chapter 9* delves into the areas of how court evidence can be collated and processed through digital forensics and offers a classification of this area of electronic evidence.
- *Chapter 10* demonstrates the legal fragmentation concerning "illegal content" including child pornography, xenophobic material or insults related to cybercriminal content and points out that the criminalisation of illegal content requires a difficult balancing act with right to freedom of expression. In this context, online searches by LEAs concerning

Child Sexual Abuse (CSA) material seem likely to be impacted by the envisioned harmonisation in the proposed Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

- *Chapter 11* first presents an understanding why the United Nations have not yet adopted a specific cybercrime convention and have thereby kept the option for LEAs limited to resorting to the general UN convention on organised crime. Second, the guidance and mechanisms for international cooperation provided in the CoE framework are outlined and, thirdly, the existing as well as the soon-to-be mechanisms for international cooperation within the EU framework are described.
- *Chapter 12* takes a closer look at the regulatory framework for AI proposed by the European Commission in April 2021 and provides a first analysis how this future regulatory framework will apply to innovative tools and systems which could be of avail in the course of cybercrime investigations.

The second part of this Deliverable D7.7 comprises of chapters 13.–15. which outline the ethical and societal framework for the use of automated tools in cybercrime investigations. While chapter 13. identifies the ethical standard relevant for the CYCLOPES project and especially for the network of law enforcement agencies and practitioners to benefit from the innovation watch and research horizon scan, chapter 14. analyses how the seven principles of the soft law “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence” as well as Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence (AP4AI) are to be observed and implemented in the use of artificial intelligence in the law enforcement environment in general and in the course of cybercrime investigations in particular.

2. Introduction

The CYCLOPES project aims to build and maintain an innovation-driven law enforcement network facilitating their combat against cybercrime. It seems an eternal truth that law enforcement has to keep pace with the new methods applied by criminals in order to fulfil their mandate to keep society safe and this truth affects especially cybercrime investigation activities because the learning process about the capabilities of modern technologies and their effects on society at large is constantly evolving. At a global level, society seems well aware of the dangers posed especially by cybercriminal activities not only for targeted groups and individuals, but also for democratic values as the fundamental beliefs our societies are built upon. Therefore, societies have become increasingly anxious to establish sufficient safeguards to maintain their societal, ethical and legal equilibrium. One example for this effort is the recently proposed “Declaration for the Future of the Internet”,¹ in which the European Union and the USA together with 59 international state partners set out their political vision and shared principles of a safe and trusted Internet. The Declaration’s 61 signatories² support a future for the Internet that is open, free, global, interoperable, reliable and secure and affirm their commitment to protecting and respecting individual’s human rights online and across the digital world. The five key principles of this Declaration are:

- “*Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms*” in the online environment for which the signatories include the intention to promote online safety and to combat violence online as well as to reduce illegal and harmful content and activities online while promoting freedom of expression;
- “*A global Internet*” for which the Signatories include the intention to promote cooperation in research and innovation on security threats and responsible state behaviour in cyberspace
- “*Inclusive and Affordable Access to the Internet*”;
- “*Trust in the Digital Ecosystem*” for which the signatories include the intention to work together to combat cybercrime and deter malicious cyber activity, as well as to base government access to personal data according to existing laws and respecting human rights while protecting the individuals’ privacy and their personal data;
- “*Multi-stakeholder Internet Governance*”.

While these guiding principles are not legally binding, they reflect a common understanding and are intended to be used as a reference point for public policy makers.³ Among public policy

¹ „A Declaration for the Future of the Internet“, 28 April 2022, available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/declaration-future-internet>.

² In addition to the European Union and the USA, the „Declaration for the Future of the Internet“ is signed by all 27 EU Member States as well as by: Albania, Andorra, Argentina, Australia, Cabo Verde, Canada, Colombia, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Georgia, Iceland, Israel, Jamaica, Japan, Kenya, Kosovo, Maldives, Marshall Islands, Micronesia, Moldova, Montenegro, New Zealand, Niger, North Macedonia, Peru, Senegal, Serbia, Taiwan, Trinidad and Tobago, the United Kingdom, Ukraine and Uruguay.

³ The reference point is also intended for citizens, businesses, and civil society organisations. According to the EU Commission’s Factsheet of 28 April 2022, „this Declaration goes hand in hand with the Draft EU

makers, the intention to work internationally together to combat cybercrime and deter malicious cyber activity might seem widely spread. However, there is no single authoritative definition of cybercrime.⁴ Rather, the term “cybercrime” is used to describe a wide variety of criminal conduct ranging from traditional computer and network crimes to current Crime-as-a-Service (CaaS) models. The more digitisation affects all parts of society, the more forms of criminality evolve. The methods and tools used by cybercriminals are increasingly adopted in other crime areas and the digital criminal ecosystem continues to evolve pretty much in sync with the development of new technologies. The privacy and convenience offered by communication, distribution and cryptocurrency platforms are beneficial in all society for legal as well as for illegal activities. The wide-scale adoption of encryption technologies creates an increase of online anonymity benefiting lawful users and criminals alike.⁵ The global COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the evolution of cybercrime over the last two years. While the innovative energy to take advantage of new technologies seems endless among cybercriminals, the CaaS model on the dark web ranges from malware over ransomware to corporate network access has created a criminal services ecosystem. As such, the CaaS model has established itself as an equally prominent and cross-cutting feature of cybercriminal activities because the CaaS model not only enables criminals with low technical skills⁶, but also makes the operations of mature and organised cybercrime actors more efficient.⁷

The currently dominant threats in cybercrime include ransomware attacks increasingly taking advantage of widespread teleworking by scanning potential targets’ networks for insecure *remote desktop protocol* (RDP) connections and keeping a keen eye on disclosed virtual private network (VPN) vulnerabilities.⁸ Due to the popularity rise for mobile banking, cybercriminal mobile malware operators have improved their tactics and techniques for stealing credentials so that a number of mobile banking malware families have implemented on-device capabilities to commit fraud by manipulating the banking apps on the user’s device using the Automated Transfer System (ATS) modules powered by the Android Accessibility Service.⁹ Because the pandemic has led to an increase of the reliance on online services, distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks for ransom have re-emerged as dominant cyber

Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles and Europe’s vision for a human centric digital transformation, as reflected in the pioneer Digital Services Act and the Digital Markets Act, as well as in the proposed rules for trustworthy Artificial Intelligence and for a trusted and secure Digital Identity for all Europeans“. The Factsheet is available at:

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/api/files/document/print/en/ip_22_2695/IP_22_2695_EN.pdf.

⁴ Gercke, „Understanding Cybercrime: phenomena, challenges and legal response“, November 2014, p. 12.

⁵ Europol, Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2021, p. 9, available at:

https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/internet_organised_crime_threat_assessment_iocta_2021.pdf.

⁶ For example by making exploit kits and other services available.

⁷ Europol, Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2021, p. 17, available at:

https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/internet_organised_crime_threat_assessment_iocta_2021.pdf.

⁸ Europol, Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2021, p. 21, available at:

https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/internet_organised_crime_threat_assessment_iocta_2021.pdf.

⁹ Europol, Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2021, p. 23, available at:

https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/internet_organised_crime_threat_assessment_iocta_2021.pdf.

threat.¹⁰ The production and distribution of child sexual abuse material (CSAM) have been influenced by the increasing unsupervised presence of children online during the pandemic which in combination with encrypted messaging applications and social media platforms has not only led to a significant increase in online grooming, but also made minors more likely to self-produce and share explicit material for online reputation or monetary gain or due to coercion.¹¹ The pandemic has shifted the focus of online fraud to online shopping and strengthened it as dominant cyber threat: While phishing and social engineering are the main vectors for payment fraud,¹² non-cash payment fraud methods have been on the rise comprising investment fraud as dominant threat but also including business email compromise (BEC) and CEO fraud.¹³ The cyber threats mentioned here merely illustrate the vast variety of cybercrime and serve as a reminder of the constantly evolving cyber threat landscape.

While cybercriminals continue to develop many ways to use the Internet for illicit purposes, their use of the Internet also provides opportunities for gathering intelligence to counter and even prevent acts of cybercrime. Gathering evidence for the prosecution of acts of cybercrime including cyberterrorism could also improve. A significant amount of knowledge about the functioning, activities and sometimes the targets of criminal organisations can be derived from websites, chat rooms and other Internet communications. Further, increased Internet use for criminal purposes provides a corresponding increase in the availability of electronic data which may be compiled and analysed in order to counter cybercrime.

To combat any form of cybercrime, law enforcement officers need therefore to be able to have timely access to data and to conduct lawful undercover work in order to fulfil their mandate of keeping society safe. For this purpose, cybercrime investigators must continuously develop their understanding of the latest threats and trends in cybercrime and are in need of adequate digital tools, solutions and methods to counter them. Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) must keep pace with new technologies, to understand the possibilities they create for criminals and how they can be used as tools for fighting cybercrime.¹⁴

The focus of the CYCLOPES project is to build and maintain an innovation-driven network of LEAs combating cybercrime in an effort to improve their capabilities to counteract the growing pressures of cyber threats. While the ever-increasing digitisation of society requires LEAs to keep pace with new technologies in order to understand the possibilities they create for criminals as well as for law enforcement, any activity in the fight against cybercrime by individual law enforcement officers as well as by LEAs as a whole has to remain within its societal, ethical and legal framework. This comprehensive framework is not automatically in

¹⁰ Europol, Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2021, p. 23, available at: https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/internet_organised_crime_threat_assessment_iocta_2021.pdf.

¹¹ Europol, Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2021, p. 25, available at: https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/internet_organised_crime_threat_assessment_iocta_2021.pdf.

¹² Europol, Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2021, p. 30, available at: https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/internet_organised_crime_threat_assessment_iocta_2021.pdf.

¹³ Europol, Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2021, p. 32, available at: https://www.europol.europa.eu/cms/sites/default/files/documents/internet_organised_crime_threat_assessment_iocta_2021.pdf.

¹⁴ Interpol, „Cyberattacks know no borders and evolve at a rapid pace“, available at: <https://www.interpol.int/Crimes/Cybercrime>.

sync with all technological developments. Rather, the role of law enforcement and its activities within a democratic society requires continuous societal, ethical and legal reflection including the evaluation of proposed solutions and the embedding of accountability mechanisms.

2.1. Overview

The DoA describes Task T7.2 relevant for this Deliverable as follows:

“Task T7.2 - Comprehensive Assessment of Social, Ethical and Legal Issues Related to Cybercrime

The aim of this task is to gather information about a range of possible, and real societal, ethical and legal (SEL) concerns related to cybercrime. Legal regulations, frameworks and recommendations related to SEL will be analysed continually. The starting point will be global and European (EU as well as Council of Europe) standards. The results of the work will feed into the assessment of issues within the discussion with practitioners in WP2. The findings and guidance will also serve as useful input into the innovation watch and research horizon scan. The uptake of tools and methods used to combat cybercrime must align to the legal frameworks, or consequentially, there will be more issues – of a legal nature – for practitioners and the cybercrime departments.”¹⁵

The outcome of Task T7.2 feeds into a report of the assessment which will be updated three times¹⁶ in the course of the CYCLOPES project. The first of these four reports was submitted as Deliverable D7.6 and this Deliverable D7.7 is its first iteration also including practical recommendations.

The key objective of this Deliverable D7.7 is to continue and update the assessment of the societal, ethical and legal (SEL) framework related to cybercrime investigation activities as described in D7.6. Therefore, this Deliverable D7.7 not only outlines the currently existing societal, ethical and legal framework for LEAs fighting with cybercrime, but also reports on imminent changes to this framework by presenting a thorough analysis of the further developments and newly evolved regulatory instruments at international and supranational level most relevant for law enforcement’s fight against cybercrime.

The comprehensive overview of the societal, ethical and legal framework presented in this Deliverable D7.7 provides updated guidance to all partners of the CYCLOPES Consortium as well as to all cybercrime investigators, at the same time. Further and perhaps more importantly, this overall and up-to-date overview helps to prepare the identification of potential gaps and emerging requirements regarding important trainings for cybercrime investigators available within the law enforcement ecosystem the results of which will be presented in Deliverable D7.11.

¹⁵ DoA, Task T7.2, p. 37.

¹⁶ The first updated iteration of Deliverable D7.6 is this Deliverable D7.7 and the two further updated iterations will be D7.8 and D7.9.

2.2. Methodology

The CYCLOPES project aims to coordinate and support the network of law enforcement practitioners fighting against cybercrime. For that purpose, the CYCLOPES Consortium has to ensure that the technological solutions and the priority areas for standardisation suggested in support of LEAs will enjoy not only full legal compliance but will also remain acceptable within the applicable societal and ethical framework.

In this respect, the CYCLOPES project needs to recognise that the chances of ensuring such societal, ethical and legal compliance for solutions and measures suggested and potentially used by LEAs across the entire European Union are limited in areas where there is a high degree of fragmentation in societal, ethical and legal standards. Therefore, the focus of ensuring legal compliance will be related to areas where either the European Union has undertaken approaches to harmonise legislation or countries are – independently from centralised harmonisation initiative – sufficiently aligned anyway because they have separately implemented comparable legislation. In areas with significant fragmentation, ensuring legal compliance will remain the sole responsibility of the LEAs utilizing a suggested solution or measure. The focus of ensuring ethical and societal compliance will be to shed light on the core principles elaborated at rather abstract level for the European Union and interpret their application in the law enforcement ecosystem especially with regard to the fight of cybercrime.

In order to identify the societal, ethical and legal concerns to be included in the assessment provided in this Deliverable D7.2.1, Task T7.2 included a red teaming exercise for the purposes of focus control:

„This task includes a red-teaming action to ensure that the identification of relevant issues for consideration go beyond state of the art, thus providing extra value to the project partners and relevant stakeholders (Europol, CEPOL, ECTEG, etc.).“¹⁷

Red teaming or alternative analysis is a specific method used to review plans, strategies, and hypotheses.¹⁸ Two teams are formed, a Red Team and a Blue Team.¹⁹ The Red Team assumes the role of the attacker, while the Blue Team focuses on defense.²⁰ This method has been successfully employed by the military for decades²¹ and has also been applied in civil

¹⁷ DoA, Task T7.2, p. 37.

¹⁸ See: *Herman/Frost/ Kurz*, Wargaming for Leaders. 2009; *Sabin*, Simulating War, 2012; Fryer-Biggs, Building better cyber red teams, defensenews.com, 14 June 2012; *Lauder*, Red Dawn: The Emergence of a red teaming capability in the Canadian Forces, Canadian Army Journal, Vol. 12.2, 2009; *Longbine*, Red Teaming: Past and Present, 2008; *Wood/Duggan*, Red Teaming of Advanced Information Assurance Concepts, DARPA Information Survivability Conference and Exposition, 2002. DISCEX 00 Proceedings, Vol. 2, S. 112ff.

¹⁹ See *Wood/Duggan*, Red Teaming of Advanced Information Assurance Concepts, DARPA Information Survivability Conference and Exposition, 2002. DISCEX 00 Proceedings, Vol. 2.

²⁰ See *Meija*, Red Team Versus Blue Team – How to run an effective Simulation, CSO 25.03.2008.

²¹ See *Lauder*, Red Dawn: The Emergence of a red teaming capability in the Canadian Forces, Canadian Army Journal, Vol. 12.2, 2009; *Longbine*, Red Teaming: Past and Present, 2008.

activities for a number of years.²² It is explicitly not restricted to the performance of physical attacks. The methodology can also be used to investigate theoretical issues from different angles and with varying emphases – reaching as far as intangible constructs such as a legislative draft.²³

Red teaming can be particularly useful when dealing with cybercrime and developing strategies and measures for maintaining cybersecurity, since the attack situation reflects the real threat scenario. However, strategies are mostly developed from the defense angle. A change or expansion of perspective enables a company's own strategies to be examined more critically. Since red teaming is not limited to a military context, this method can even be utilized in the process of drafting legislation.²⁴ CRI, the task leader for Task T7.2, has successfully utilised this approach in several other EU-funded projects.

The red teaming exercise revealed potential legal conflicts in the context of cybercrime investigations related especially regarding LEA's use of Big Data and automated access to and information exchange regarding databases, the utilisation of artificial intelligence tools as well as online searches by LEAs. As a consequence, these topics were included in the list of legal topics selected for analysis in the **first part** of this Deliverable and the completed list included the following topics encountered in almost every cybercrime investigation:

- Legal framework protecting the fundamental rights of the individual (chapter 3. below),
- Legal framework for data protection regarding the protection of the individual's personal data, on the one hand, and the legal bases available for LEAs for automated screening, on the other (chapter 4. below),
- Legal framework for victim protection (chapter 5. below),
- Legal framework for LEA's performance of online searches not only in targeted investigations and for preventative purposes but also by using search robots (chapter 6. below),
- Legal framework governing potential conflicts with core requirements of copyright and contract law (chapter 7. below),
- Legal framework governing LEA's engagement with persons of interest including legal bases for undercover operations and their automation as well as for operating agent provocateur (chapter 8. below),
- Legal framework governing the collection and preservation of electronic evidence (chapter 9. below),

²² See *Lauder*, Red Dawn: The Emergence of a red teaming capability in the Canadian Forces, Canadian Army Journal, Vol. 12.2, 2009.

²³ See *Gercke*, "Red Teaming" Ansätze zur Effektivierung von Gesetzgebungsprozessen? Die Übertragbarkeit einer klassischen, militärischen Methodik auf Gesetzgebungsprozesse im IT-Bereich, CR 2014, page 344 et seq.

²⁴ See *Gercke*, "Red Teaming" Ansätze zur Effektivierung von Gesetzgebungsprozessen? Die Übertragbarkeit einer klassischen, militärischen Methodik auf Gesetzgebungsprozesse im IT-Bereich, CR 2014, page 344 et seq.

- Legal framework governing handling, monitoring and storage of illegal content (chapter 10. below),
- Legal framework governing cross-border access and transfer of data relevant for cybercrime investigations (chapter 11. below),
- Legal framework governing artificial Intelligence tools (chapter 12. below).

Concerning potential conflicts in cybercrime investigations with the societal and ethical framework for LEAs, the red teaming exercise revealed a focus on the questions of what criteria establish automated tools as trustworthy and what societal perceptions might be at risk of being eroded when LEAs actually use of automated (AI) tools in their fight against cybercrime. Therefore, both topics were included in the list of societal and ethical topics selected for analysis in the **second part** of this Deliverable and the completed list included the following topics relevant for every cybercrime investigation:

- Relevant societal and ethical standard (chapter 13. below),
- Societal and ethical framework for trustworthy artificial intelligence (chapter 14. below),
- Societal and ethical framework LEAs use of automated search tools (chapter 15. below).

2.3. Structure

This Deliverable includes the following chapters:

- *Chapter 1* presents the executive summary of this Deliverable D7.7.
- *Chapter 2* provides an overview and the methodology of the approach to this SEL report as introduction.
- *Chapter 3* presents the human rights dimension any cybercrime investigation activity has to be aware of and respect with an analysis of the United Nations framework, the Council of Europe framework and the European Union framework.
- *Chapter 4* provides an overview of the relevant legal frameworks for data protection at European level governing cybercrime investigations consisting of the Council of Europe rules and regulations, on the one hand, and the European Union rules and regulations, on the other.
- *Chapter 5* provides an overview of the legal frameworks for victims' rights established in international treaties at global level by the United Nations and at regional level by the Council of Europe as well as by the European Union.
- *Chapter 6* looks at the procedural standards governing online investigations for retrospective and prospective purposes and points out the legal impact of automating large-scale data collection and mining for criminal investigations as well as for purposes of preventing cybercrime.

- *Chapter 7* examines the impact of the likely collection of copyrighted material when operating a crawler and addresses potential violations of license agreements, access restrictions and/or website terms & conditions in the course of collecting data automatically online.
- *Chapter 8* deals with the use of covert tools enabling automated interactive communication with cybercriminals and highlights the international fragmentation of the law regarding (covert) engagement in communication with potential suspects including the use of an agent provocateur.
- *Chapter 9* delves into the areas of how court evidence can be collated and processed through digital forensics and offers a classification of this area of electronic evidence.
- *Chapter 10* demonstrates the legal fragmentation concerning “illegal content” including child pornography, xenophobic material or insults related to cybercriminal content and points out that the criminalisation of illegal content requires a difficult balancing act with right to freedom of expression. In this context, online searches by LEAs concerning Child Sexual Abuse (CSA) material seem likely to be impacted by the envisioned harmonisation in the proposed Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.
- *Chapter 11* first presents an understanding why the United Nations have not yet adopted a specific cybercrime convention and have thereby kept the option for LEAs limited to resorting to the general UN convention on organised crime. Second, the guidance and mechanisms for international cooperation provided in the CoE framework are outlined and, thirdly, the existing as well as the soon-to-be mechanisms for international cooperation within the EU framework are described.
- *Chapter 12* takes a closer look at the regulatory framework for AI proposed by the European Commission in April 2021 and provides a first analysis how this future regulatory framework will apply to innovative tools and systems which could be of avail in the course of cybercrime investigations.
- *Chapter 13* identifies the ethical standard relevant for the CYCLOPES project and especially for the network of law enforcement agencies and practitioners to benefit from the innovation watch and research horizon scan.
- *Chapter 14* analyses how the seven principles of the soft law “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence” are to be observed and implemented in the use of artificial intelligence in the law enforcement environment in general and in the course of cybercrime investigations in particular. In this context, the Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence (AP4AI) as ethical and societal framework are dedicated to the law enforcement ecosystem in general and to LEAs’ use of automated tools in cybercrime investigations in particular.

3. Fundamental Rights Regulation

Any form of crime is an act against the human rights of those affected. Nation states have not only the right but also the obligation to do something against crime including cybercrime. To avoid violating human rights of individuals as a nation state, any form of law and its enforcement has to respect human rights in the analogue world as well as in the digital world. As expressly included in the “Declaration for the Future of the Internet” as key principle, nation states have to “protect and respect human rights and fundamental freedoms across the digital ecosystem, while providing access to meaningful remedies for human rights violations and abuses”²⁵.

This political dedication and commitment to the protection of human rights and fundamental principles like the rule of law is at the heart of the mandate for law enforcement in western democratic societies and shapes each and every criminal investigation. In exchange for the constitutional right to use violence for the enforcement of the law, law enforcement in general and all cybercrime investigators in particular have to be aware of the human rights dimension of their activities. Such awareness is all the more necessary because each human right is guaranteed and protected by more than one single legal layer. Three of these layers are outlined in this chapter: the United Nations (UN) framework (section 3.1. below) the Council of Europe (CoE) framework (section 3.2. below) and the European Union (EU) framework (section 3.3. below). In addition to national law, these frameworks govern the legitimate course of action available for LEAs in their fight against cybercrime including the use of tools and digital methods. When retrospectively investigating cybercrimes as well as when proactively preventing, detecting and deterring cybercriminal activity, LEAs must comply with all three of these legal frameworks in order to prevent legal issues for cybercrime investigators and their departments.

3.1. UN Framework

Even though the respect for human rights and the rule of law are an integral part of national states’ fight against cybercrime, there is no international treaty in place at the level of the United Nations specifically addressing combating cybercrime.

The roots of this lack at global level of a legally binding legal instrument dedicated to the fight against cybercrime for all countries to refer to and draw from, seem to emanate from a deadlock concerning the best approach at the United Nations. Up until a future UN convention cybercrime may emerge, the global international legal framework applicable to the fight against cybercrime consists of the United Nations’ more general standards which include treaties, jurisprudence and customary international law.

²⁵ „A Declaration for the Future of the Internet“, 28 April 2022, available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/declaration-future-internet>.

3.1.1. UN Declaration of Human Rights and the Rule of Law

The human rights obligations of the United Nations' Member States are enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR). These obligations to ensure respect for human rights and the rule of law also apply to Member States in their fight against cybercrime. To the extent to which the fight against cybercrime overlaps with the fight against terrorism,²⁶ the international community has manifested this commitment in the United Nations Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy²⁷ which reaffirms the inextricable links between human rights and security, and places respect for the rule of law and human rights at the core of national and international counter-terrorism efforts.²⁸ No less respect for human rights and compliance with other obligations under international law seems appropriate for any other area of the combat against cybercrime, because cyberspace is subject to international law including the rule of law and human rights as unanimously expressed at the UN Security Council's first-ever debate of cyberthreats in Jun 2021.²⁹ To be effective, this needs to include a commitment (as in the United Nations Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy³⁰) to developing national strategies that seek not only to prevent cybercrime and address the conditions conducive to their spread, but also to prosecuting or lawfully extraditing those responsible for such cybercrimes and to giving due attention to the rights of all victims of human rights violations.

Like under the United Nations Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy, effective counter-measures against cybercrime and the protection of human rights are complementary and mutually reinforcing objectives which must be pursued together.

Such counter-measures against cybercrime may have an impact on the enjoyment of a range of human rights, including the right to freedom of expression (Art. 19 UDHR), the right to freedom of association (Art. 20 UDHR), the right to privacy (Art. 12 UDHR) and the right to a fair trial (Art. 10, 11 UDHR).³¹ None of these human rights belongs to the list of non-derogable rights and freedoms under Art. 4(2) ICCPR. Therefore, these human rights may be subject to narrowly construed limitations and derogations.

²⁶ Both, criminals and terrorists are dependent on the same sources for weapons, forged documents, finances and a shared pool of potential recruits, see: Europol, SOCTA 2021, p. 25.

²⁷ United Nations, General Assembly, Resolution 60/288, "The United Nations Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy", A/RES/60/288, adopted on 8 September 2006.

²⁸ United Nations, General Assembly, Resolution 60/288, A/RES/60/288, 8 September 2006, Annex 'Plan of Action', part I. and in particular part IV. referring in No. 1 to Resolution 60/158 by United Nations General Assembly, A/RES/60/158, 16 December 2005.

²⁹ UN Security Council, „Explosive' Growth of Digital Technologies Creating New Potential for Conflict, Disarmament Chief Tells Security Council in First-Ever Debate on Cyberthreats“, press release, SC/14563, 29 June 2021.

³⁰ See part II. of Annex "Plan of action' to United Nations, General Assembly, Resolution 60/288, A/RES/60/288, 8 September 2006.

³¹ United Nations, General Assembly, Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) Resolution 217 A, A/RES/3/217 A, 10 December 1948.

3.1.2. Conditions for Limiting Human Rights

It seems important to highlight that the vast majority of counter-measures against cybercrime are adopted on the basis of ordinary national legislation. In a limited set of exceptional national circumstances, some restrictions on the enjoyment of certain human rights may be permissible.

As provided for by international human rights conventions, Member States may legitimately limit the exercise of certain so-called qualified rights including the right to freedom of expression³², the right to freedom of association and assembly³³, the right to freedom of movement³⁴ and the right to respect for one's private and family life³⁵. In order to fully respect their human rights obligations while imposing such limitations, Member States must demonstrate the *necessity* of a limitation and may only take such measures as are *proportionate* to the pursuance of *legitimate aims* in order to ensure continuous and effective protection of human rights.³⁶ Consequently, in addition to respecting the principles of *equality* and *non-discrimination*, the limitations must be prescribed by law, in pursuance of one or more specific legitimate purposes and proportionate. In no case may the limitations be applied or invoked in a manner that would impair the essence of a human right.³⁷

Taking the right to freedom of expression³⁸ as an example, it is not an absolute right and may be restricted when that freedom is (mis)used to incite discrimination, hostility or violence. Any restriction is subject to satisfaction of strictly construed tests of legality, necessity, proportionality and non-discrimination. However, a key difficulty in cases of incitement to cybercrime is identifying where the line of acceptability lies, because this varies greatly from country to country depending on differing cultural and legal histories. Particularly concerning anti-terrorism measures another key difficulty is that restricting freedom of expression in response to terrorism might facilitate certain terrorist objectives which in particular include the dismantling of human rights protection.³⁹

³² Art. 19 UDHR = Art. 19 ICCPR.

³³ Art. 20 UDHR = Art. 21 and 22 ICCPR.

³⁴ Art. 13 UDHR = Art. 12 ICCPR.

³⁵ Art. 12 UDHR = Art. 17 ICCPR.

³⁶ No. 6 of United Nations, International Covenant of Civil and Political Rights, General Comment No. 31 [80] on "The Nature of the General Legal Obligation Imposed on States Parties to the Covenant" adopted on 29 March 2004.

³⁷ No. 6 of United Nations, International Covenant of Civil and Political Rights, General Comment No. 31 [80] on "The Nature of the General Legal Obligation Imposed on States Parties to the Covenant" adopted on 29 March 2004.

³⁸ Art. 19 UDHR = Art. 19 ICCPR.

³⁹ See „International Mechanisms for Promoting Freedom of Expression“, Joint Declaration by UN Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Opinion and Expression, the OSCE Representative on Freedom of the Media and the OAS Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Expression, 21 December 2005.

3.1.3. Gathering of Potential Evidence by LEAs

Countering cybercrime may involve the surveillance and collection of information relating to suspected individuals. Due regard should be given to protecting persons against arbitrary or unlawful interference with the right to privacy enshrined in Art. 12 UDHR. The right to privacy includes the right to privacy of information about an individual's identity as well as his or her private life.

Domestic laws must be sufficiently detailed regarding, inter alia, the specific circumstances in which such interference may be permitted. Appropriate safeguards must also be in place to prevent abuse of secret surveillance tools. Further, any personal data collected must be adequately protected against unlawful or arbitrary access, disclosure or use.

3.1.4. UN: Due Process Rights

Guaranteeing due process rights is critical for ensuring that counter-measures against cybercrime are effective and respect the rule of law. Human rights protections for anyone charged with cybercriminal offences include the right to be presumed innocent (Art. 11 UDHR), the right to a hearing with due guarantees and within a reasonable time by a competent, independent and impartial tribunal (Art. 10 UDHR) and the right to have a conviction and sentence reviewed by a higher tribunal that meets the same standards.⁴⁰

3.2. CoE Framework

At regional level, the Member States of the Council of Europe base their guarantee of human rights not only on the UDHR, but also on the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms⁴¹ better known as the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR). Because the ECHR was declared considering the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), the ECHR comprises much the same guarantees of fundamental rights and freedoms as the UDHR.

⁴⁰ United Nations, Human Rights, Terrorism and Counter-terrorism, Fact Sheet No. 32, 2008, at part III.F. on p. 38.

⁴¹ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (as amended by Protocols Nos. 11 and 14 and supplemented by Protocols Nos. 1, 4, 6, 7, 12 and 13), 4 December 1950.

3.2.1. Legitimate Restrictions of ECHR Guarantees

Relevant for cybercrime investigations are especially the guarantees of the right to a fair trial⁴² based on the presumption of innocence⁴³, the right to respect of private and family life (privacy)⁴⁴ as well as the freedom of expression⁴⁵ and the freedom of assembly and association⁴⁶. It is crucial to note that the right to private and family life⁴⁷, the freedom of expression⁴⁸ and the freedom of assembly and association⁴⁹ allow for legitimate restrictions in accordance with the law which are “necessary in a democratic society” in the interests of “national security”, “public safety” or “for the prevention of disorder or crime” among other legitimate reasons. According to Article 18 ECHR, such legitimate restrictions may not be applied for any purpose other than those for which they have been prescribed.

To ensure the observance of the protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms, the ECHR established the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) in Articles 19 – 51 ECHR. The judgments of the ECtHR are binding for and enforceable in all Member States according to Article 46 ECHR.

Concerning the automation of online searches in the surface web and in the dark web which enable (cyber)crime investigators to profile suspected individuals in detail, the ECtHR has developed a catalogue of minimum standards for surveillance which are crucial for the evaluation of national surveillance measures.⁵⁰ This catalogue of minimum standards includes:

- the definition of the addressee of a national surveillance measure;
- a list of crimes justifying a national surveillance measure;
- a time limit for the national surveillance measure;
- a procedure for the use of the collected data;
- measures ensuring that the collected data remains undamaged and available for subsequent control and

⁴² Art. 6 ECHR.

⁴³ Art. 6(2) ECHR.

⁴⁴ Art. 8 ECHR.

⁴⁵ Art. 10 ECHR.

⁴⁶ Art. 11 ECHR.

⁴⁷ Art. 8(2) ECHR.

⁴⁸ Art. 10(2) ECHR.

⁴⁹ Art. 11(2) ECHR.

⁵⁰ ECtHR, decision of 4 December 2015 in case of *Zakharov v. Russia*, Application No. 47143/06, at para. 231 and ECtHR, decision of 12 January 2016 in case of *Szabo and Vissy v. Hungary*, Application No. 37138/14, at para. 66.

- provisions for the deletion of the collected data.⁵¹

These minimum standards for surveillance were originally established for surveillance of telephone communications of individuals.⁵² In 2008, the ECtHR transferred these minimum standards to all other surveillance measures on the basis that the potential negative effect on fundamental rights was identical.⁵³ The comparability of the negative effect on fundamental rights and freedoms also affects the type of data which is collected. The ECtHR acknowledged that the collection of content data is as problematic as the collection of traffic data concerning the intensity of encroaching fundamental rights and freedoms. In its more recent case law, the ECtHR specified these minimum standards on several occasions more precisely:

- *Supportive material for measure:* The ECtHR demanded a requirement in national legislation for the authorities to demonstrate the relation between the persons concerned by the surveillance measure and the prevention of any terrorist threat.⁵⁴ There has to be a legal safeguard requiring LEAs to produce supportive materials or, in particular, a sufficient factual basis for the application of secret intelligence gathering measures which then enable the evaluation of necessity of the proposed measure - and this on the basis of an individual suspicion regarding the target person.⁵⁵
- *Effective control:* Based on the rule of law, the ECtHR required that an interference by LEAs with an individual's rights should be subject to an effective control which should normally be assured by the judiciary, at least in the last resort, because judicial control offers the best guarantees of independence, impartiality and a proper procedure.⁵⁶
- *Acute privacy protection:* In a more general way, the ECtHR drew from the technological advances the conclusion that the potential interferences of (mass) electronic surveillance with email, mobile phone and Internet services demanded the ECHR's protection of private life even more acutely.⁵⁷
- *Profiling:* Because these data often compile further information and present LEAs with an opportunity for profiling, The ECtHR emphasized that the possibility for LEAs to acquire a detailed profile of the most intimate aspects of citizens' lives may result in particularly invasive interferences with private life and requires that this threat to privacy

⁵¹ ECtHR, decision of 30 July 1998 in case of *Valenzuela Contreras v. Spain*, Application No. 58/1997/824/1048, at para. 46; ECtHR, decision of 4 December 2015 in case of *Zakharov v. Russia*, Application No. 47143/06, at para. 231 and ECtHR, decision of 12 January 2016 in case of *Szabo and Vissy v. Hungary*, Application No. 37138/14, at para. 66.

⁵² ECtHR, decision of 6 September 1978 in case of *Klass and others v. Germany*, Application No. 5029/71.

⁵³ ECtHR, decision of 1 July 2008 in case of *Liberty and Others v. UK*, Application No. 58243/00, at para. 63.

⁵⁴ ECtHR, decision of 12 January 2016 in case of *Szabo and Vissy v. Hungary*, Application No. 37138/14, at para. 67.

⁵⁵ ECtHR, decision of 12 January 2016 in case of *Szabo and Vissy v. Hungary*, Application No. 37138/14, at para. 71; ECtHR, decision of 4 December 2015 in case of *Zakharov v. Russia*, Application No. 47143/06, at para. 260 .

⁵⁶ ECtHR, decision of 12 January 2016 in case of *Szabo and Vissy v. Hungary*, Application No. 37138/14, at para. 75 and 77.

⁵⁷ ECtHR, decision of 12 January 2016 in case of *Szabo and Vissy v. Hungary*, Application No. 37138/14, at para. 53.

must be subjected to very close scrutiny both on the domestic level and under the ECHR.⁵⁸

- *Prevention of uncontrolled surveillance:* The ECtHR demanded to prevent substituting a terrorist threat for a perceived threat of unfettered executive power intruding into citizens' private spheres by virtue of uncontrolled yet far-reaching surveillance techniques and prerogatives.⁵⁹
- *Strict necessity of secret surveillance:* Given the potential of cutting-edge surveillance technologies to invade citizens' privacy, the ECtHR expounded the requirement "necessary in a democratic society" in this context as requiring "strict necessity" in two aspects:
 - a measure of secret surveillance can be found as being in compliance with the ECHR only if it is strictly necessary, as a general consideration, *for the safeguarding the democratic institutions* and
 - if it is strictly necessary, as a particular consideration, *for the obtaining of vital intelligence* in an individual operation.⁶⁰

The ECtHR established this safeguard to limit a LEA's discretion in interpreting the broad terms of 'persons concerned identified' by following an established practice to verify whether sufficient reasons for intercepting a specific individual's communications exist in each case.⁶¹

3.3. EU Framework

In their fight against cybercrime, Member States of the European Union have to respect human rights and the rule of law not only because of their obligations under the ECHR and the UDHR, but also because of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union⁶² (Charter of Fundamental Rights).

3.3.1. EU Charter of Fundamental Rights

⁵⁸ ECtHR, decision of 12 January 2016 in case of *Szabo and Vissy v. Hungary*, Application No. 37138/14, at para. 70.

⁵⁹ ECtHR, decision of 12 January 2016 in case of *Szabo and Vissy v. Hungary*, Application No. 37138/14, at para. 68.

⁶⁰ ECtHR, decision of 12 January 2016 in case of *Szabo and Vissy v. Hungary*, Application No. 37138/14, at para. 73.

⁶¹ ECtHR, decision of 12 January 2016 in case of *Szabo and Vissy v. Hungary*, Application No. 37138/14, at para. 73 referring to ECtHR, decision of 4 December 2015 in case of *Zakharov v. Russia*, Application No. 47143/06, at para. 249 and 266.

⁶² Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, Official Journal of the European Communities, 2000/C 364/01, 18 December 2000.

The European Union (EU) has established the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000) for the protection of human rights. Concerning the protection of privacy, the Charter of Fundamental Rights comprises not only the right to respect for private and family life⁶³ but also the right to protection of personal data⁶⁴ implying a more coherent approach. The guarantees of the Charter of Fundamental Rights also include the freedom of expression and information⁶⁵, freedom of assembly and of association⁶⁶ as well as the right to a fair trial⁶⁷ and the presumption of innocence⁶⁸.

Article 51 Charter of Fundamental Rights demands the Member States of the EU to respect the rights and to observe the principles laid down in the Charter of Fundamental Rights only when they are implementing Union law. Member States are implementing Union law when national legislation falls within the scope of European Union law which automatically opens the jurisdiction of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) to guide the interpretation of the Charter of Fundamental Rights so that national courts can determine whether a national legislation is compatible with the fundamental rights enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights.⁶⁹

In case of secret cybercrime investigations searching the surface web and the dark web for evidence against potential suspects, the protection of privacy and personal data is crucial for individuals whose activities and connections are examined.

3.3.2. European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade

In January 2022, the European Commission published its proposal for a “European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade” (European Declaration) and this European Declaration was then signed and adopted on 15 December 2022⁷⁰ by the Council, the European Parliament, and the Commission.⁷¹ The European Declaration builds on the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and transposes fundamental rights of individuals into the digital sphere. Even though the proposed European Declaration will not be binding legislation, its vision is intended to have an indirect effect on any future legislation which is likely to incorporate and be aligned with these new principles. The European Declaration defines a set of principles for a human-centred digital transformation and aims to ensure that the values of the Union and the rights and freedoms of individuals as guaranteed by Union law are respected and reinforced both offline and online.

⁶³ Art. 7 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

⁶⁴ Art. 8 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

⁶⁵ Art. 10 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

⁶⁶ Art. 11 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

⁶⁷ Art. 47 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

⁶⁸ Art. 48 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

⁶⁹ CJEU, decision of 26 February 2013 in case *Akerberg Fransson*, C-617/10, at para. 19.

⁷⁰ Council of the EU, „Declaration on digital rights and principles: EU values and citizens at the centre of digital transformation“, Press Release 1113/22, 15 December 2022, available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/12/15/declaration-on-digital-rights-and-principles-eu-values-and-citizens-at-the-centre-of-digital-transformation/pdf>.

⁷¹ European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles for the Digital Decade, 23 January 2023, Official Journal of the EU, C 23, p. 1.

The European Declaration essentially promotes putting humans at the centre of the digital transformation and embracing European values in the digital sphere. In six short chapters, the declaration focuses on:

- (i) the role of human values, such as human rights and democracy, in a digital society;
- (ii) an inclusive and solidarity framework, uniting people and providing fair and equal access for everyone;
- (iii) promoting the users' freedom of choice by preventing discrimination and by making algorithms and AI more transparent and accountable;
- (iv) creating a trustworthy and diverse online space that allows everyone to participate in democratic debate without censorship while stopping the spread of illegal content;
- (v) promoting safe standards that give users power over their data and protect children online; and
- (vi) matching the "Green Deal", and ensuring that digital technology is sustainable and limited in its impact on the environment.

The European Declaration is the first declaration to focus solely on the fundamental rights of individuals in the digital sphere.⁷² Substantively, much of the European Declaration reiterates and adapts the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights to a digital environment. Chapter I. of the proposed European Declaration puts people at the centre of the digital transformation in the EU and includes commitments not only to ensure that the values of the EU and the rights of individuals "*are respected online as well as offline*", but also to "*fostering responsible and diligent action by all digital actors, public and private, for a safe and secure digital environment*".

Although the European Declaration merely declares a political intention with no binding legal effect, it has nevertheless been an important guide in finalising the eEvidence Package⁷³ (section 8.3 below) and continues to guide future EU legislative initiatives including currently pending initiatives like the ePrivacy Regulation⁷⁴. Similarly, legislative initiatives at national level in EU Member States will be affected.

In the context of cybercrime investigations, especially chapters III. and V. of the European Declaration are of interest. Chapter III. addresses the use of algorithms and artificial intelligence and promotes their transparency⁷⁵ as well as the use of "suitable datasets" to prevent discrimination⁷⁶. Furthermore, the European Declaration commits to "*providing for safeguards and taking appropriate action, including by promoting trustworthy standards, to ensure that artificial intelligence and digital systems are, at all times, safe and used in full respect for fundamental rights*".⁷⁷ These commitments currently influence the trilogue negotiations for a future Artificial Intelligence Act (see chapter 12. below).

Chapter V. states that digital technologies, products and services accessible in the EU should be "*safe, secure, and privacy-protective, resulting in a high level of confidentiality, integrity,*

⁷² The three previous EU declarations, which the Declaration of Digital Rights now builds on, are the "Tallinn Declaration on eGovernment" of 6 October 2017 (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/ministerial-declaration-egovernment-tallinn-declaration>), the "Berlin Declaration on Digital Society and Value-based Digital Government" of 8 December 2020 (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/berlin-declaration-digital-society-and-value-based-digital-government>), and the "Lisbon Declaration - Digital Democracy with a Purpose" of (<https://www.lisbondeclaration.eu/>).

⁷³ Section 11.3.2 below.

⁷⁴ Section 4.2.1.1 below.

⁷⁵ Chapter III. lit. a) and b) after No. 9. European Declaration.

⁷⁶ Chapter III. lit. c) after No. 9. European Declaration.

⁷⁷ Chapter III. lit. e) after No. 9. European Declaration.

*availability and authenticity of the information processed*⁷⁸. For this purpose, a commitment is included to protect “*the interests of people, businesses and public institutions against cybersecurity risks and cybercrime*”⁷⁹ as well as to counter and hold accountable “*those that seek to undermine, within the EU, security online and the integrity of the digital environment or that promote violence and hatred through digital means*”⁸⁰. These commitments influence the legislative process for the proposed Draft Regulation Against Online CSA (see chapter 10. below) and also form the backdrop to the legislative process for the Draft Police Cooperation Code (see section 11.3.2 below).

From a legal perspective, it needs to be emphasised that the European Declaration merely declares a political intention and has no binding legal effect, neither between the EU bodies, nor between the Member States. Consequently, this European Declaration will not even confer any direct obligations or claims upon individuals or businesses.

From a societal and ethical perspective, the European Declaration states the “*shared political commitment*” of the three signatories: the EU Commission, European Parliament, and Council.

⁷⁸ Chapter V. No. 16. European Declaration.

⁷⁹ Chapter V. lit b) after No. 16. European Declaration.

⁸⁰ Chapter V. lit c) after No. 16. European Declaration.

4. Data Protection

Cybercriminals continue to develop a variety of ways to use the Internet for illicit purposes. A potentially positive aspect seems to be that their use of the Internet creates opportunities for LEA investigators to gather data as evidence against perpetrators and as intelligence to counter and even prevent cybercrime. A significant amount of knowledge about the functioning, activities and sometimes the targets of (cyber)criminal organisations can be derived from websites, chat rooms and other Internet communications. Further, increased Internet use for cybercriminal purposes provides a corresponding increase in the availability of electronic data which may be compiled and analysed for counter-acting cybercrime. The CYCLOPES project is about improving the capabilities of LEAs to counteract the growing pressures of committed cybercrimes and luring cyber threats. For that purpose, the CYCLOPES Consortium will scan also the market for suitable technological tools enabling LEAs either to retrospectively gather evidence in the course of a cybercrime investigation or to proactively prevent, detect and deter cybercriminal activities.

This chapter provides an overview of the relevant legal framework for data protection at European level relevant in cybercrime investigations. LEA investigations against potential cybercriminals affect the protection of all investigated individuals' personal data. In Europe, there are two separate and overlapping legal regimes governing the protection of personal data emanating from the right to respect for private and family life enshrined in the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), on the one side, and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (Charter of Fundamental Rights), on the other.

In the framework established by the Council of Europe (CoE), the participating states (Parties) base their guarantee of human rights on the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms⁸¹ better known as the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR). Because the ECHR was declared considering the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)⁸², the ECHR comprises much the same guarantees of fundamental rights and freedoms as the UDHR.

In the framework provided by the European Union (EU), the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000) has been established for the protection of human rights. Concerning the protection of privacy, the Charter of Fundamental Rights comprises not only the right to respect for private and family life⁸³ but also the right to protection of personal data⁸⁴ implying a more coherent approach. The guarantees of the Charter of Fundamental Rights

⁸¹ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (as amended by Protocols Nos. 11 and 14 and supplemented by Protocols Nos. 1, 4, 6, 7, 12 and 13), 4 December 1950.

⁸² United Nations, General Assembly, Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) Resolution 217 A, A/RES/3/217 A, 10 December 1948.

⁸³ Art. 7 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

⁸⁴ Art. 8 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

also include the freedom of expression and information⁸⁵, freedom of assembly and of association⁸⁶ as well as the right to a fair trial⁸⁷ and the presumption of innocence⁸⁸.

4.1. CoE Framework

With regard to criminal investigations related to criminal use of the Internet for cybercrime purposes, the Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime contains a set of provisions that reflect widely accepted minimum standards regarding procedural instruments required for online investigations.⁸⁹ The Convention on Cybercrime even addresses issues of high relevance – such as the question whether LEAs are allowed to access information available on servers located in another country. This seems especially relevant for criminal investigations concerning cybercrime and will be analysed in more detail regarding international cooperation (chapter 11. below).

4.1.1. Fundamental Principles

The reference in Art. 15(1) CoE Convention on Cybercrime to the ECHR includes the protection of the right to respect for one’s private and family life as well as one’s home and correspondence enshrined in Art. 8 ECHR which appears most relevant for investigations concerning cybercrime and online terrorist activities. The concepts of “private life” and “correspondence” within the meaning of Art. 8(1) ECHR aim to protect the confidentiality of communications in a wide range of different situations covering mobile telephone communications⁹⁰ as well as other technologies, in particular electronic messages including emails⁹¹ as well as Internet use⁹², and data stored on computer servers⁹³. All forms of interception, monitoring and seizure concerning these communications fall within the scope of Art. 8 ECHR.⁹⁴

⁸⁵ Art. 10 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

⁸⁶ Art. 11 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

⁸⁷ Art. 47 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

⁸⁸ Art. 48 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

⁸⁹ See Articles 15-21 of the Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime.

⁹⁰ ECtHR, decision of 4 December 2015 in case of *Roman Zakharov v. Russia*, Application No. 47143/06, at para. 173; between family members, see ECtHR, decision of 20 January 1992 in case of *Margareta and Roger Andersson v. Sweden*, Application No. 12963/87, at para. 72; or with others, see ECtHR, decision of 15 June 1992 in case of *Lüdi v. Switzerland*, Application No. 12433/86, at para. 38 and 39.

⁹¹ ECtHR, decision of 5 September 2017 in case of *Bărbulescu v. Romania* [GC], Application No. 61496/08, at para. 72; ECtHR, decision of 3 April 2007 in case of *Copland v. the United Kingdom*, Application No. 62617/00, at para. 41.

⁹² ECtHR, decision of 3 April 2007 in case of *Copland v. the United Kingdom*, Application No. 62617/00, at para. 42.

⁹³ ECtHR, decision of 16 October 2007 in case of *Wieser and Bicos Beteiligungen GmbH v. Austria*, Application No. 74336/01, at para 45.

⁹⁴ ECtHR, “Guide on Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights”, 20 August 2020, at para. 487.

To ensure the protection of privacy granted in Art. 8 ECHR, the *European Court of Human Rights* (ECtHR) has developed a body of case law defining more precisely the standards that govern digital investigations. This body of case law seems today one of the most important sources for international standards in respect to investigations related to communication.⁹⁵ The body of case law takes particularly into consideration the *gravity* of interference of the investigation,⁹⁶ the *purpose* of the interference of the investigation,⁹⁷ and the *proportionality* of the interference of the investigation.⁹⁸ The following four fundamental principles can be extracted from the ECtHR's body of case law:

- The need for a *sufficient legal basis* for investigation instruments.⁹⁹
- The requirement that the legal basis must be clear with regard to the *rights of a suspect*.¹⁰⁰
- The *competences of LEAs* need to be foreseeable.¹⁰¹
- The surveillance of communication can only be justified in *context of serious crime*.¹⁰²

In addition to these fundamental principles, Article 15(1) CoE Convention on Cybercrime expressly refers to the *principle of proportionality* which creates for Parties who are not Member States of the Council of Europe an obligation to develop the necessary safeguards.¹⁰³ Surveillance measures regarding communication may only be ordered if there is no prospect of successfully establishing the facts by another method or this would be considerably more difficult.¹⁰⁴

4.1.2. Minimum Standards

⁹⁵ Gercke, "Understanding Cybercrime: phenomena, challenges and legal response", ITU 2012, at 6.5.3, p. 245.

⁹⁶ ECtHR, decision of 12 April 1990 in case of *Kruslin v. France*, Application No. 11801/85, at para. 33.

⁹⁷ ECtHR, decision of 26 April 1985 in case of *Malone v. United Kingdom*, Application No. 8691/79, at para. 67.

⁹⁸ ECtHR, decision of 6 September 1978 in case of *Klass and others v. Germany*, Application No. 5029/71, at para. 42.

⁹⁹ ECtHR, decision of 12 April 1990 in case of *Kruslin v. France*, Application No. 11801/85, at para. 27; ECtHR, decision of 24 April 1990 in case of *Huvig v. France*, Application No. 11105/84, at para. 32.

¹⁰⁰ ECtHR, decision of 4 December 2015 in case of *Roman Zakharov v. Russia*, Application No. 47143/06, at para. 229 et seq.; ECtHR, decision of 27 April 2004 in case of *Doerga v. The Netherlands*, Application No. 50210/99, at para. 50.

¹⁰¹ ECtHR, decision of 15 April 2015 in case of *Dragojević v. Croatia*, Application No. 68955/11, at para. 94; ECtHR, decision of 12 April 1990 in case of *Kruslin v. France*, Application No. 11801/85, at para. 27 and ECtHR, decision of 26 April 1985 in case of *Malone v. United Kingdom*, Application No. 8691/79, at para. 67.

¹⁰² ECtHR, decision of 15 April 2015 in case of *Dragojević v. Croatia*, Application No. 68955/11, at para. 94; ECtHR, decision of 6 September 1978 in case of *Klass and others v. Germany*, Application No. 5029/71, at para. 42.

¹⁰³ Gercke, "Understanding Cybercrime: phenomena, challenges and legal response", ITU 2012, at 6.5.3, p. 245.

¹⁰⁴ ECtHR, decision of 15 April 2015 in case of *Dragojević v. Croatia*, Application No. 68955/11, at para. 94.

Article 15(2) CoE Convention on Cybercrime supplements these five fundamental principles with an explicit reference to some of the most relevant safeguards including independent supervision, grounds justifying an application, and the limitation of the scope and the duration of such power or procedure.¹⁰⁵ One guarantee of an appropriate procedure designed to ensure that surveillance measures regarding communication are not ordered haphazardly, irregularly or without due and proper consideration in criminal investigations is to confine such measures to cases in which there are factual grounds for suspecting a person of planning, committing or having committed certain serious criminal acts.¹⁰⁶ Furthermore and in order to limit the power (and its potential abuse) which might be exercised by national authorities, the ECtHR has developed the following six minimum safeguards that must be set in national law:

- (1) the nature of offences which may give rise to an interception order;
- (2) the definition of the categories of people liable to have their communications intercepted;
- (3) the duration of interception;
- (4) the procedure to be followed for examining, using and storing the data obtained;
- (5) precautions to be taken when communicating the data to other parties and
- (6) circumstances in which recordings may or must be erased or destroyed.¹⁰⁷

All in all, the system of safeguards required by the CoE Convention on Cybercrime combines the ability of LEAs to use the instruments provided in Art. 14 – 21 CoE Convention on Cybercrime in a flexible way with the guarantee of effective safeguards and depends on the implementation of a graded system of safeguards. The decision which safeguard needs to be implemented with regards to which instrument is left to the national legislators of the Parties.¹⁰⁸ The ability to ensure an adequate protection of the rights of a suspected individual within a graded system of safeguards largely depends on how the potential impact of an investigation instrument is balanced with the related safeguards at national level.

4.2. EU Framework

Within the EU, data protection in the police and criminal justice sector is regulated in the context of both national and cross-border processing by police and criminal justice authorities of the Member States and EU actors. The two central instruments for the operation of

¹⁰⁵ This list of most relevant safeguards in Article 15(2) CoE Convention on Cybercrime is not exclusive, see No. 146 of the Explanatory Report to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

¹⁰⁶ ECtHR, decision of 15 April 2015 in case of *Dragojević v. Croatia*, Application No. 68955/11, at para. 94.

¹⁰⁷ ECtHR, decision of 4 December 2015 in case of *Roman Zakharov v. Russia*, Application No. 47143/06, at para. 231.

¹⁰⁸ See No. 147 of the Explanatory Report to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

advanced investigative tools at EU level are Directive (EU) 2016/680¹⁰⁹ which aims to protect personal data collected and processed for criminal justice purposes including prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences, on the one hand, and the Regulation on the European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (Europol Regulation),¹¹⁰ on the other.

4.2.1. Applicability to Criminal Investigations

Art. 51 Charter of Fundamental Rights demands the Member States of the EU to respect the rights and to observe the principles laid down in the Charter of Fundamental Rights only when they are implementing Union law. Member States are implementing Union law when national legislation falls within the scope of European Union law which automatically opens the jurisdiction of the *Court of Justice of the European Union* (CJEU) to guide the interpretation of the Charter of Fundamental Rights so that national courts can determine whether a national legislation is compatible with the fundamental rights enshrined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights.¹¹¹

In case LEAs use advanced investigative tools in criminal investigations including for searching the Internet and the dark web for evidence, the protection of privacy and personal data is crucial for individuals whose activities and connections are examined.

4.2.1.1. Exemptions to GDPR and ePrivacy Directive

Most relevant for the guarantees of the right to respect for private and family life¹¹² and the right to protection of personal data¹¹³ is Art. 2(2)(d) GDPR¹¹⁴ which provides an exemption for LEAs investigating criminal offences from the scope of the GDPR and causes such investigations to fall under Union law.

The ePrivacy Directive ensures the protection of the fundamental right to respect for private and family life, the confidentiality of communications and the protection of personal data in the electronic communications sector. It also guarantees the free movement of electronic

¹⁰⁹ Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA, Official Journal of the EU, L 119/89, 4 May 2016.

¹¹⁰ Regulation (EU) 2016/794 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 May 2016 on the European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (Europol) and replacing and repealing Council Decisions 2009/371/JHA, 2009/934/JHA, 2009/935/JHA, 2009/936/JHA and 2009/968/JHA, OJ 2016 L 135, p. 53.

¹¹¹ CJEU, decision of 26 February 2013 in case *Akerberg Fransson*, C-617/10, at para. 19.

¹¹² Art. 7 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

¹¹³ Art. 8 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

¹¹⁴ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), Official Journal L 119/1, 4 May 2016.

communications data, equipment and services in the Union. It implements in the Union's secondary law the fundamental right to the respect for private life, with regard to communications, as enshrined in Art. 7 Charter of Fundamental Rights. According to its Art. 1(3), the ePrivacy Directive shall not apply in any case to activities concerning (among others) public security and the activities of the State in areas of criminal law. This exemption for LEAs from the scope of the ePrivacy Directive also causes cybercrime investigation activities to fall under the regime provided the Law Enforcement Directive (EU) 2016/680 (section 4.2.3. below).

Because consumers and businesses increasingly rely on internet-based services enabling inter-personal communications such as Voice over IP, text messaging and web-based e-mail services, instead of traditional communications services, the European Commission proposed an ePrivacy Regulation¹¹⁵ at the beginning of 2017. The proposed ePrivacy Regulation also covers machine-to-machine communications when the information can be related to the identifiable end-user receiving the information (e.g. Netflix, IoT devices, etc.)¹¹⁶ and services which are not publicly available, but provide access to a publicly available electronic communications network like the virtual private network (VPN) of a company that gives access to the outside internet.¹¹⁷ However, the proposed ePrivacy Regulation is not envisaged to apply to activities of LEAs “*for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences*” according to Art. 2(2)(d) ePrivacy Regulation. While the European Parliament left this exemption unaltered in its report of October 2017,¹¹⁸ the Council of the EU explicitly added “*including data processing activities*” to this exemption in its mandate for negotiations with the European Parliament adopted in February 2021.¹¹⁹ The legislative process is currently still pending at the trilogue stage and it seems most probably that the exemption for LEAs monitoring online activities in the course of a criminal investigation will remain. Therefore, this exemption of activities of LEAs from the scope of the future ePrivacy Regulation will perpetuate that monitoring of online activities by LEAs falls under the regime provided the Law Enforcement Directive (EU) 2016/680 (section 4.2.3. below).

In this context, it is interesting to note that Over-the-Top (“OTTs”) communications services provided over the public internet and functionally equivalent to more traditional

communication (e.g. WhatsApp) had in general been subject only to the GDPR and were not covered by the Union electronic communications framework including the ePrivacy Directive. This changed in December 2020 when Directive (EU) 2018/1972 establishing the

¹¹⁵ European Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the respect for private life and the protection of personal data in electronic communications and repealing Directive 2002/58/EC (Regulation on Privacy and Electronic Communications), COM(2017) 10 final, 10 January 2017.

¹¹⁶ Recital 12 of the Commission’s Proposal for a ePrivacy Regulation.

¹¹⁷ González/De Hert/Papakonstantinou, „The Proposed ePrivacy Regulation: The Commission’s and the Parliament’s Drafts at a Crossroads?“, Brussels Privacy Hub, Working Paper, Vol. 6, No. 20, March 2020, p. 7.

¹¹⁸ European Parliament, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the respect for private life and the protection of personal data in electronic communications and repealing Directive 2002/58/EC (Regulation on Privacy and Electronic Communications), A8-0324/2017, 20 October 2017.

¹¹⁹ Council of the EU, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the respect for private life and the protection of personal data in electronic communications and repealing Directive 2002/58/EC (Regulation on Privacy and Electronic Communications), 2017/0003(COD), 6087/21, 10 February 2021.

comprehensive European Electronic Communications Code (EECC Directive)¹²⁰ entered into application. While not directly amending the provisions of the ePrivacy Directive, the EECC Directive changed the scope of the ePrivacy Directive's application because it updated key terms previously established by the Framework Directive¹²¹. Consequently, key terms like '*electronic communications network*' and '*electronic communications service*', determining the scope of application of the ePrivacy Directive, are defined in accordance with the definitions of '*interpersonal communication services*' adopted in Art. 2 EECC Directive.¹²² This definition encompasses '*number-independent interpersonal communications services*' (NI-ICS),¹²³ which includes messaging services. As the ePrivacy Directive relies on the definition of *electronic communications services* in the EECC, NI-ICS are subject to the confidentiality rules of the ePrivacy Directive. Therefore, the exemption in Article 1(3) ePrivacy Directive for the activities of the State in areas of criminal law continues to apply and places such activities under the regime provided in the Law Enforcement Directive (EU) 2016/680 (section 4.2.3. below).

In contrast to the GDPR, the ePrivacy Directive does not contain a legal basis for the voluntary processing of content or traffic data for the purpose of detecting child sexual abuse. Therefore, for services falling within the scope of the ePrivacy Directive, a specific derogation to Art. 5(1) and 6(1) ePrivacy Directive was agreed upon by the negotiators from the Council and the European Parliament as temporary measure to allow providers of electronic communications services such as web-based email and messaging services to continue to detect, remove and report child sexual abuse online, also covering anti-grooming, until permanent legislation announced by the European Commission will be in place.¹²⁴ The negotiated Interim Regulation¹²⁵ will apply for three years, or until an earlier date if the permanent legal instrument is adopted by the legislators and repeals these temporary rules before then.

4.2.1.2. Restrictions on Freedoms in the TFEU

The applicability of the Charter of Fundamental Rights also results from the fact that acts of online monitoring may affect the prohibition of restrictions on the freedom to provide services

¹²⁰ Directive (EU) 2018/1972 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 establishing the European Electronic Communications Code, Official Journal of the EU, L 321/36, 17.12.2018 which is applicable since 21 December 2020.

¹²¹ Directive 2002/21/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 7 March 2002 on a common regulatory framework for electronic communications networks and services (Framework Directive), Official Journal of the EU, L 108, 24 April 2002, pp. 33.

¹²² Rojszczak, „OTT regulation framework in the context of CJEU Skype case and European Electronic Communications Code“, Computer Law & Security Review 38 (2020) 105439, p. 11.

¹²³ Art. 2(7) EECC.

¹²⁴ Council of the EU, “Combating child abuse online – informal deal with European Parliament on temporary rules”, 29 April 2021, available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2021/04/29/combating-child-abuse-online-informal-deal-with-european-parliament-on-temporary-rules>.

¹²⁵ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on a temporary derogation from certain provisions of Directive 2002/58/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the use of technologies by number-independent interpersonal communications service providers for the processing of personal and other data for the purpose of combatting child sexual abuse online, COM(2020) 568 final, 10 September 2020.

within the EU in Art. 56 of Treaty of Functioning of the European Union (TFEU).¹²⁶ According to the CJEU, even in a situation where action of a Member States is only partially determined by EU law, the “implementation” requirement of Art. 51(1) Charter of Fundamental Rights is met whenever a national court is called upon to review whether fundamental rights are complied with by a national provision or measure.¹²⁷

4.2.2. Lines of Case Law Synchronising Privacy Protection under EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and ECHR

In the area of privacy and data protection, the CJEU has developed a line of case law which expounds Art. 7 and 8 Charter of Fundamental Rights in combination with Art. 8 ECHR and refers to the established line of case law by the ECtHR on the guarantee of privacy under the ECHR.¹²⁸ In this context, it has to be pointed out that also the ECtHR refers in its more recent case law to the principles developed by the CJEU regarding the interpretation of Art. 7 and 8 Charter of Fundamental Rights.¹²⁹ This kind of cross-referencing to each other’s line of case law appears to be a rather recent phenomenon but allows, nevertheless, to expect a uniform interpretation of the protection of privacy in the future.¹³⁰

Furthermore, the CJEU expressly mentions “minimum safeguards” for individuals against the risk of abuse and unlawful access of data retained by LEAs in their fight against cybercrime and terrorism.¹³¹ With these “minimum safeguards”, the CJEU refers to the line of case law of the ECtHR described at section 4.1.2. above establishing coherent minimum standards for national surveillance measures without formulating its own detailed catalogue of minimum requirements. This reference to the ECtHR’s line of case law leads to the conclusion that the cumulative minimum standards established by the ECtHR are to be applied under the Charter of Fundamental Rights as well. Indeed, the CJEU goes on to examine each of the exact criteria developed by the ECtHR:

- Restrictions of individuals affected by the surveillance measure;¹³²
- Access restrictions to collected data to ensure their availability for serious crimes only;¹³³

¹²⁶ CJEU, decision of 26 February 2013 in case *Akerberg Fransson*, C-617/10, at para. 29.

¹²⁷ CJEU, decision of 26 February 2013 in case *Akerberg Fransson*, C-617/10, at para. 29.

¹²⁸ CJEU, decision of 21 December 2016 in case *Tele2 Sverige AB*, C-203/15 and C-698/15, at paras. 119 and 120; CJEU, decision of 8 April 2014 in case *Digital Rights Ireland*, C-293/12 and C-592/12, at para. 35, 47, 54.

¹²⁹ ECtHR, decision of 12 January 2016 in case of *Szabo and Vissy v. Hungary*, Application No. 37138/14, at para. 68, 70, 73; ECtHR, decision of 4 December 2015 in case of *Zakharov v. Russia*, Application No. 47143/06, at para. 147.

¹³⁰ Boehm/Andrees, CR 2016, pp. 146-154.

¹³¹ CJEU, decision of 8 April 2014 in case *Digital Rights Ireland*, C-293/12 and C-592/12, at para. 54.

¹³² CJEU, decision of 8 April 2014 in case *Digital Rights Ireland*, C-293/12 and C-592/12, at para. 58.

¹³³ CJEU, decision of 8 April 2014 in case *Digital Rights Ireland*, C-293/12 and C-592/12, at para. 60.

- Limitation of data retention period;¹³⁴ and
- Guarantee of data security.¹³⁵

According to the CJEU, the retention of surveillance data requires an explicit reason for the collection of the data¹³⁶ and creates a need for a threat to public security causing the collection of data.¹³⁷

As a result, the protection of the right to respect for private and family life¹³⁸ and of the right to protection of personal data¹³⁹ under the Charter of Fundamental Rights appears currently fully synchronised with the protection of the right to respect for private and family life¹⁴⁰ under the ECHR.

4.2.3. Directive (EU) 2016/680 for Data Protection in the Police and Criminal Justice Sectors

On 5 May 2016, Directive (EU) 2016/680 on the Protection of Natural Persons with regard to the Processing of Personal Data by Competent Authorities for the Purposes of the Prevention, Investigation, Detection or Prosecution of Criminal Offences or the Execution of Criminal Penalties, and on the Free Movement of Such Data¹⁴¹ entered into force and Member States had to transpose it into their national law by 6 May 2018. Directive (EU) 2016/680 is also known as 'Law Enforcement Directive' and applicable to national LEAs in Member States.

Directive (EU) 2016/680 was adopted in order to ensure a high level of data protection while improving cooperation in the fight against cybercrime, terrorism and other serious crime. After the Treaty of Lisbon came into effect, the protection of natural persons in relation to the processing of personal data is expressly recognized as a fundamental right. Article 8(1) Charter of Fundamental Rights and Article 16(1) TFEU provide that everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her. However, Declaration 21, annexed to the final act of the intergovernmental conference which adopted the Treaty of Lisbon, acknowledges that the specific nature of the security field merits special legislative treatment. According to the European institutions' approach, processing in the police and criminal justice context should be differentiated from all other personal data processing. The protection and

¹³⁴ CJEU, decision of 8 April 2014 in case *Digital Rights Ireland*, C-293/12 and C-592/12, at para. 63.

¹³⁵ CJEU, decision of 8 April 2014 in case *Digital Rights Ireland*, C-293/12 and C-592/12, at para. 66.

¹³⁶ CJEU, decision of 8 April 2014 in case *Digital Rights Ireland*, C-293/12 and C-592/12, at para. 58.

¹³⁷ CJEU, decision of 8 April 2014 in case *Digital Rights Ireland*, C-293/12 and C-592/12, at para. 59.

¹³⁸ Art. 7 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

¹³⁹ Art. 8 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

¹⁴⁰ Art. 8 ECHR.

¹⁴¹ Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA, Official Journal of the EU, L 119/89, 4 May 2016.

free movement of data processed by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties has been regulated by a directive, allowing Member States a certain level of flexibility while incorporating it into their respective national laws.

Directive (EU) 2016/680 aims at balancing the data protection objectives with the security policy objectives and, while certainly contributing to the creation of a less fragmented general framework, it does not solve all the shortcomings which had emerged before its adoption. Directive (EU) 2016/680 comprises ten chapters which can be divided into two parts:

The **first part** of Directive (EU) 2016/680 consists of chapters I – V which describe:

- the scope,¹⁴²
- the general principles relating to processing of personal data,¹⁴³
- the rights of the data subject,¹⁴⁴
- the obligations of the controllers and the processors,¹⁴⁵ the technical and organizational measures to ensure security of personal data, which have to be adopted by them,¹⁴⁶ as well as the designation of a data protection officer,¹⁴⁷ and
- the regulation of transfer of personal data to third countries or international organizations.¹⁴⁸

The **second part** of Directive (EU) 2016/680 regulates:

- the independent status,¹⁴⁹ the competence, tasks and powers¹⁵⁰ of the independent supervisory authorities and establishes the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority,
- the cooperation between Member States by mutual assistance,¹⁵¹
- the right to an effective judicial remedy against a controller or processor and the right to compensation for any person who has suffered material or non-material damage as a result of an unlawful processing of personal data.¹⁵²

¹⁴² Art. 1 – 3 Directive (EU) 2016/680, chapter I.

¹⁴³ Art. 4 – 11 Directive (EU) 2016/680, chapter II.

¹⁴⁴ Art. 12 – 18 Directive (EU) 2016/680, chapter III.

¹⁴⁵ Art. 19 – 28 Directive (EU) 2016/680, chapter IV, section 1.

¹⁴⁶ Art. 29 – 31 Directive (EU) 2016/680, chapter IV, section 2.

¹⁴⁷ Art. 32 – 34 Directive (EU) 2016/680, chapter IV, section 3.

¹⁴⁸ Art. 35 – 40 Directive (EU) 2016/680, chapter V.

¹⁴⁹ Art. 41 – 44 Directive (EU) 2016/680, chapter VI, section 1.

¹⁵⁰ Art. 45 – 49 Directive (EU) 2016/680, chapter VI, section 2.

¹⁵¹ Art. 50 – 51 Directive (EU) 2016/680, chapter VII.

¹⁵² Art. 52 – 57 Directive (EU) 2016/680, chapter VIII. The final two of Directive (EU) 2016/680 are about implementing acts, chapter IX, and final provisions, chapter X.

4.2.3.1. Scope

Directive (EU) 2016/680 applies to the processing of personal data by competent authorities “for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties”, Article 2(1) Directive (EU) 2016/680 in connection with Art. 1(1) Directive (EU) 2016/680. The use of advanced investigative tools in criminal investigations falls within the scope of Directive (EU) 2016/680.

- ***Data Processing in the Course of Criminal Investigations***

Directive (EU) 2016/680 protects the personal data of different categories of individuals involved in criminal proceedings, such as witnesses, informants, victims, suspects and accomplices. For this purpose, Art. 6 Directive (EU) 2016/680 requires law enforcement to make a clear distinction between the personal data of these categories. Police and criminal justice authorities are obliged to comply with the Directive’s provisions whenever they process such personal data for law enforcement purposes, within both the personal and the material scope of Directive (EU) 2016/680. However, the use of data for a different purpose is also allowed under certain conditions. The processing of data for a different law enforcement purpose than that for which it was collected is only permitted if this is lawful, necessary and proportionate according to national or EU law.¹⁵³ For other purposes, the rules of the GDPR apply. The logging and documenting of data sharing is one of the competent authorities’ specific duties to assist with the clarification of responsibilities arising from complaints.

It is interesting to note that Recital 49 Directive (EU) 2016/680 seems to suggest that where personal data are processed in the course of “a criminal investigation”, Member States may provide for the exercise of the right to information¹⁵⁴, access¹⁵⁵ and rectification or erasure¹⁵⁶ of personal data to be carried out in accordance with their national law. Read together with Art. 18 as well as Recitals 20 and 107 Directive (EU) 2016/680, this appears to provide an opening for different national laws under the framework of Directive (EU) 2016/680. Because of this ambiguity, the real added value of Directive (EU) 2016/680 depends on its implementation in national law and the willingness of national courts to ensure that Directive (EU) 2016/680 is applied in a uniform manner across the EU.

- ***Data Processing Outside the Scope of Union Law***

Directive (EU) 2016/680 does not regulate the processing of data in the course of an activity which falls outside the scope of Union law, Art. 2(3)(a) Directive (EU) 2016/680. Recital 14 Directive (EU) 2016/680 suggests to interpret Article 2(3)(a) Directive (EU) 2016/680 as

¹⁵³ Art. 4(2) Directive (EU) 2016/680.

¹⁵⁴ Art. 13 Directive (EU) 2016/680.

¹⁵⁵ Art. 14 Directive (EU) 2016/680.

¹⁵⁶ Art. 16 Directive (EU) 2016/680.

relating to activities concerning national security, activities of agencies or units dealing with national security issues and the processing of personal data by the Member States when carrying out activities which fall within the scope of Chapter 2 of Title V of the TEU. As consequence, the wording of Article 2(3) Directive (EU) 2016/680 appears to be in conflict with the inclusion of “safeguarding against and the prevention of threats to public security” in Article 1(1) Directive (EU) 2016/680. The concept of activities concerning national security is not defined in Directive (EU) 2016/680, but seems to include “activities of safeguarding against and prevention of threats to public security”. Until the CJEU will provide guidance on how to resolve this seeming contradiction, the scope of Directive (EU) 2016/680 will depend on the interpretation that national courts will give to the expression “activity which falls outside the scope of Union law” and of the way the Member States decide to implement Directive (EU) 2016/680.

- **Data Processing by EU Institutions, Bodies and Agencies**

Finally, Directive (EU) 2016/680 does not apply to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies, Art. 2(3)(b) Directive (EU) 2016/680. The data processing by the European institutions and bodies is governed by Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement.¹⁵⁷ Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 aims to bring the level of data protection at EU institutions, bodies, offices and agencies in line not only with the GDPR but also with Directive (EU) 2016/680.¹⁵⁸

Europol was established in 1998 and its present legal status as an EU institution is based on the Regulation on the European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (Europol Regulation).¹⁵⁹

- **Harmonisation Level and Comparison with Data Processing Principles in GDPR**

Directive (EU) 2016/680 regulates the processing of personal data by Member States and not only intra-Member States exchanges of data. Nevertheless, Directive (EU) 2016/680 is still far from ensuring maximum harmonisation of data processing in the criminal field. Art. 1(3) Directive (EU) 2016/680 states that Directive (EU) 2016/680 shall not preclude Member States from providing higher safeguards than those established in Directive (EU) 2016/680 for the

¹⁵⁷ European Commission, Regulation (EU) 2018/1725 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and Decision No 1247/2002/EC, 23 October 2018.

¹⁵⁸ Recitals 9 and 10 of the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data by the Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and Decision No 1247/2002/EC, COM(2017) 8 final, 10 January 2017.

¹⁵⁹ Regulation (EU) 2016/794 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 May 2016 on the European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation (Europol) and replacing and repealing Council Decisions 2009/371/JHA, 2009/934/JHA, 2009/935/JHA, 2009/936/JHA and 2009/968/JHA, OJ 2016 L 135, p. 53.

protection of the rights and freedoms of the data subject. As a result, Directive (EU) 2016/680 ensures only a minimum harmonisation.

Several principles relating to processing of personal data are the same as those enshrined in the GDPR. However, because of the peculiarity of the field, while the basic data protection principles are included in its text, some of those set out in the GDPR are not included in Directive (EU) 2016/680. For example:

As far as the *characteristics the data* should have in order to be processed by the competent authorities are concerned, it may be observed that not all the conditions required by the GDPR in order to consider the data processing lawful and fair need to be met under Directive (EU) 2016/680.

The *consent of the data subject* is not a necessary condition for processing personal data by the competent authorities according to Recital 35 Directive (EU) 2016/680 when they order natural persons to comply with requests made in order to perform the tasks of preventing, investigating, detecting or prosecuting criminal offences. Where the data subject is required to comply with a legal obligation, the data subject has no genuine and free choice, so that the reaction of the data subject could not be considered to be a freely given indication of his or her wishes. Whether the correct balance between individual data protection and the interests of the police and criminal justice process is respected depends once again on how Member States have implemented the exemptions contained in Directive (EU) 2016/680.

Directive (EU) 2016/680 also allows Member States to adopt legislative measures restricting the data subject's rights to information¹⁶⁰, access¹⁶¹ and rectification¹⁶² in an attempt to strike a balance between the individual right to data protection and the processing interests and concerns of the police and other LEAs. If exercised to their fullest extent these rights would undermine much of the work done by the police and the competent authorities within the criminal justice system. The level of flexibility accorded to this end depends once more on the breadth of national legislative measures implementing Directive (EU) 2016/680, which can restrict, wholly or partly, the data subject's right in order to assure the due performance of investigations and protect national security, as set out in Art. 15 Directive (EU) 2016/680.

- ***Independent Supervisory Authority***

The final important element of the EU data protection model refers to the establishment of an independent supervisory authority entrusted with the task of monitoring the application of data protection law within the respective Member State. Directive (EU) 2016/680 permits assignment of this role to the authority established for similar purposes under the GDPR. Data Protection Authorities, as independent supervisory authorities, had been introduced by Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC and have become the basic mechanism for enforcement and monitoring of data protection in the EU.

¹⁶⁰ Art. 13(3) Directive (EU) 2016/680.

¹⁶¹ Art. 15(1) Directive (EU) 2016/680.

¹⁶² Art. 16(4) Directive (EU) 2016/680.

The European Data Protection Board has replaced the former Article 29 Working Party and is assigned a central role by the GDPR (especially in the consistency mechanism), but no such role is provided for in Directive (EU) 2016/680. However, in the police and criminal justice context conflicts pertaining to processing of personal data may arise between the Data Protection Authority and the judicial authorities in order to determine whether a Data Protection Authority may monitor processing done by judicial authorities. In order to limit the discretionary power of the Member States, Directive (EU) 2016/680 provides that the processing of data by judicial authorities must not be affected by its provisions when acting within their judicial capacity. In spite of that Art. 1(3) Directive (EU) 2016/680 permits Member States to maintain a higher level of data protection which may ultimately be a cause of problems.

- ***Profiling***

The regulation of profiling in Directive (EU) 2016/680 deserves a separate mention. Profiling is especially problematic in the police and criminal justice context because if profiles are misused they can lead to stressful situations for individuals who could be put under surveillance or arrested on the grounds of automated processing of personal data. The compatibility with the presumption of innocence¹⁶³ may be questioned.

In this context, it is necessary to underline that Directive (EU) 2016/680 provides substantial and procedural safeguards. According to Art. 11(1) Directive (EU) 2016/680, Member States are prohibited from providing for a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces an adverse legal effect concerning the data subject or significantly affects him or her, unless authorised by Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject and which provides appropriate safeguards for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Art. 11(3) Directive (EU) 2016/680 also stresses that profiling resulting in discrimination against natural persons shall be prohibited.

- ***International Data Transfers***

Directive (EU) 2016/680 provides rules for international data transfers in its chapter V.

- ***Data Transfers among Member States***

Where personal data are to be transmitted or made available from another Member State, Art. 35 (1) Directive (EU) 2016/680 requires five enumerated conditions to be met including that the other Member State has to give its prior authorisation to the transfer in accordance with its national law¹⁶⁴. However, according to Art. 35(2) Directive (EU) 2016/680 Member States shall provide for data transfers without prior authorisation by the other Member State to be permitted if, and only if, the data transfer is necessary for the prevention of an immediate and serious

¹⁶³ Art. 48 Charter of Fundamental Rights.

¹⁶⁴ Art. 35(1)(c) Directive (EU) 2016/680.

threat to public security of a Member State or a third country and the prior authorization cannot be obtained in good time. In these scenarios, the second sentence of Art. 35 (2) Directive (EU) 2016/680 requires that the authority which is responsible for giving prior authorization has to be informed without delay.

- **Data Transfers to Third Countries**

With regard to the transfer of personal data to third countries or international organisations, Art. 36(1) Directive (EU) 2016/680 requires that personal data may only be transmitted by a Member State to a third country where the Commission has decided that the recipient ensures an “adequate” level of protection. In June 2021, the Commission adopted its first and so far only¹⁶⁵ ‘adequacy decision’ covering data processing activities for law enforcement purposes under Art. 36 Directive (EU) 2016/680 with the United Kingdom.¹⁶⁶

According to the Commission’s first report on the application and functioning of Directive (EU) 2016/680, global convergence of data protection rules in the area of criminal law enforcement is only now starting to develop (driven, for instance, by multilateral arrangements such as the modernised CoE Convention 108+ or the Second Additional Protocol to the ‘Budapest’ Convention on Cybercrime). In accordance with Recital 68 Directive (EU) 2016/680, the Commission will consider other possible candidates for future adequacy decisions paying close attention to the international commitments of the assessed countries relating to the protection of personal data, including accession to the beforementioned multilateral arrangements or to other law enforcement instruments providing appropriate data protection safeguards.¹⁶⁷

The concept of adequate level of protection has been defined by the CJEU in the cases of *Schrems I*¹⁶⁸ and *Schrems II*¹⁶⁹ as requiring the third country in fact to ensure, by reason of its domestic law or its international commitments, a level of protection of fundamental rights and freedoms that is essentially equivalent to that guaranteed within the EU. The CJEU has also stated that the European Commission’s discretion as to the adequacy of the level of protection ensured by a third Country should be limited, considering, *first*, the important role played by the protection of personal data in the light of the fundamental right to respect for private life and, *secondly*, the large number of persons whose fundamental rights are liable to be infringed

¹⁶⁵ Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and Council of 25 July 2022 on First Report on application and functioning of the Data Protection Law Enforcement Directive (EU) 2016/680 (‘LED’), COM(2022) 364 final, section 3.5.1, p. 26.

¹⁶⁶ Commission, Implementing Decision of 28 June 2021 pursuant to Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the adequate protection of personal data by the United Kingdom, available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/decision_on_the_adequate_protection_of_personal_data_by_the_united_kingdom_law_enforcement_directive_en.pdf.

¹⁶⁷ Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and Council of 25 July 2022 on First Report on application and functioning of the Data Protection Law Enforcement Directive (EU) 2016/680 (‘LED’), COM(2022) 364 final, section 3.5.1, p. 27.

¹⁶⁸ CJEU, decision of 6 October 2015 in case *Schrems*, C-362/14, CRi 2016, p. 25 at para. 73.

¹⁶⁹ CJEU, decision of 16 July 2020 in case *Schrems II*, C-311/18, Cri 2020, p. 109 at para. 105.

where personal data is transferred to a third country without ensuring an adequate level of protection.¹⁷⁰

In that respect it should be underlined that data processing in the police and criminal justice context was up until 2018 a field left outside Union law. Practically all Member States have bilateral agreements with third countries permitting the exchange of personal data for law enforcement related purposes, notwithstanding any “adequacy” finding in respect of the recipients’ data protection safeguards. Therefore, here again Directive (EU) 2016/680 had to maintain a careful balance between, on the one hand, the requirements of police and criminal justice work and existing bilateral agreements and, on the other, the requirement for an increased level of personal data protection.

Directive (EU) 2016/680 appears to do little to affect bilateral agreements which are already in place. As a consequence, Directive (EU) 2016/680 automatically turned all bilateral agreements into definite term ones needing amendment to match its standards. However, if Member States – that are called upon, but not obliged to actively seek to amend bilateral agreements in the foreseeable future¹⁷¹ – have not taken action, the prolonged existence of those bilateral agreements which apply lower standards than Directive (EU) 2016/680 seems to undermine the whole international data transfer edifice.

¹⁷⁰ CJEU, decision of 6 October 2015 in case *Schrems*, C-362/14, CRi 2016, p. 26 at para. 78; CJEU, decision of 8 April 2014 in case *Digital Rights Ireland*, C-293/12 and C-592/12, at para. 47 and 48.

¹⁷¹ See Art. 40 Directive (EU) 2016/680.

5. Victim Protection

Because the evolution of cybercrime has integrated a cyber-component into almost all forms of traditional crime and enables criminals to operate at the speed of the internet and gather more data about their victims in advance,¹⁷² the challenges for law enforcement to protect victims have increased and the COVID-19 pandemic has led to a sudden increase in working from home and remote access to business resources both of which rendered many more individuals and businesses as lucrative targets.¹⁷³

This chapter provides an overview of the legal frameworks established in international treaties at global level by the United Nations (section 5.1. below) and at regional level by the Council of Europe (section 5.2. below) as well as of the legal framework for victims' rights within the European Union (section 5.3. below).

5.1. UN Framework

The provisions of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights¹⁷⁴ and all other international human rights treaties including those of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights¹⁷⁵ apply to any victim of cybercrime or terrorism.¹⁷⁶ Interestingly, it was not until the drafting and near universal ratification of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC)¹⁷⁷ in the late 20th century that the distinct characteristics of childhood have gained international recognition and a child is explicitly recognised as a human rights holder.

5.1.1. Child Protection Rights

At global level, the CRC is the cornerstone of children's rights imposing legally binding obligations on States Parties to respect, protect and fulfil the rights of the child. There are specific protection rights in the CRC which include protection from all forms of child abuse, neglect, exploitation and cruelty before a child falls victim to any of these. While Art. 34 CRC explicitly requires States Parties to protect children from all forms of sexual exploitation and abuse, Art. 19 CRC obligates the States Parties in a much broader sense to prohibit, prevent and respond to all forms of violence, injury or abuse, maltreatment or exploitation of children,

¹⁷² Europol, Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2020, p. 12.

¹⁷³ Europol, Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment (IOCTA) 2021, p. 8.

¹⁷⁴ United Nations, General Assembly, Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), Resolution 217 A, A/RES/3/217 A, 10 December 1948.

¹⁷⁵ United Nations, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, Resolution 2200A (XXI), adopted on 16 December 1966, entered into force on 23 March 1976.

¹⁷⁶ For the most recent report evaluation the progress of the existing United Nations activities regarding victims of terrorism, with a focus on detailed options, including for a voluntarily funded comprehensive programme to support Member States in assisting victims of terrorism through national systems, see: United Nations, "Progress made by the United Nations system in supporting Member States in assisting victims of terrorism", Report to the General Assembly by the Secretary-General, A/74/790, 8 April 2020.

¹⁷⁷ United Nations, Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), Resolution 44/25, adopted on 20 November 1989, entered into force on 2 September 1990; the CRC is the most ratified human rights treaty in the world because all UN Member States (except the USA) have agreed to be bound by the obligation to uphold children's rights in all spheres of life.

including sexual abuse, while in the care of parents or any other legal guardian.¹⁷⁸ For children who have become a victim, the States Parties have to take protective measures including effective procedures for the investigation and treatment of instances of child maltreatment as well as for judicial involvement.¹⁷⁹

5.1.2. Child Victims' Rights

These protective measures require a *child rights approach* furthering the realisation of the rights of all children as set out in the CRC. The States Parties are obligated to develop the capacity of duty bearers to meet their obligations to respect, protect and fulfil rights (Art. 4 CRC) and the capacity of rights holders to claim their rights. This child rights approach has to be guided at all times by the rights to *non-discrimination* (Art. 2 CRC), consideration of the *best interests of the child* (Art. 3(1) CRC), *life, survival and development* (Art. 6 CRC), and *respect for the views of the child* (Art. 12 CRC). Furthermore, children have the right to be directed and guided in the exercise of their rights by caregivers, parents and community members, in line with children's evolving capacities (Art. 5 CRC).¹⁸⁰

The position of a child as victim is explicitly recognised in Art. 39 CRC. This provision requires States Parties to take all appropriate measures to promote physical and psychological recovery and social reintegration of child victims (sentence 1). This recovery and reintegration must take place in an environment which fosters the health, self-respect and dignity of the child (sentence 2). For that reason, Art. 19(2) CRC requires appropriate "investigation" and "treatment" among several other services needed for child victims.

While the investigation of instances of violence requires a child rights-based and child-sensitive approach by qualified professionals,¹⁸¹ the appropriate "treatment" of a child victim must pay heed to: (i) inviting and giving due weight to the child's views; (ii) the safety of the child; (iii) the possible need for her or his immediate safe placement; and (iv) the predictable influences of potential interventions on the child's long-term well-being, health and development. In this respect, a full range of services should be available upon identification of abuse, ranging from medical, mental health, social and legal services and support as well as longer term follow-up services including family group conferencing and other similar practices.¹⁸²

All judicial proceedings involving child victims of violence must not only adhere to the celerity principle while respecting the rule of law, but also treat the child victim in a child-friendly and sensitive manner throughout the justice process, taking into account the child's personal situation, needs, age, gender, disability and level of maturity and fully respecting their physical,

¹⁷⁸ Violence within the meaning of Art. 19(1) CRC includes any form of CSEM as violence through information and communications technologies; see: UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, General comment No. 13 (2011) on the right of the child to freedom from all forms of violence, 18 April 2011, CRC/C/GC/13, at para. 31.

¹⁷⁹ Art. 19(2) CRC.

¹⁸⁰ See the definition of a child rights approach in: UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, General comment No. 13 (2011) on the right of the child to freedom from all forms of violence, 18 April 2011, CRC/C/GC/13, at para. 59.

¹⁸¹ UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, General comment No. 13 (2011) on the right of the child to freedom from all forms of violence, 18 April 2011, CRC/C/GC/13, at para. 51.

¹⁸² UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, General comment No. 13 (2011) on the right of the child to freedom from all forms of violence, 18 April 2011, CRC/C/GC/13, at para. 52.

mental and moral integrity.¹⁸³ The UN Guidelines on Justice in Matters involving Child Victims and Witnesses of Crime provide very detailed guidance on how to implement these aspects in the areas starting with the guiding principles (at III.) over to specifying the impact of: the right to be treated with dignity and compassion (at V.), the right to be protected from discrimination (at VI.), the right to be informed (at VII.), the right to be heard and to express views and concerns (at VIII.), the right to effective assistance (at IX.), the right to privacy (at X.), the right to be protected from hardship during the justice process (at XI.), the right to safety (XII.), as well as the right to reparation (XIII.) and the right to special preventive measures (XIV.).¹⁸⁴

Regarding victims of sexual exploitation, the CRC has been augmented by the Optional Protocol on the sale of children, child prostitution and child pornography.¹⁸⁵ Art. 8(1) of this Optional Protocol obligates States Parties to adopt appropriate measures to protect the rights and interests of child victims at all stages of the criminal justice process. A key guiding principle is enshrined in Art. 3(1) CRC and requires States Parties to ensure that “*the best interests of the child*” are a primary consideration of all state activities (including courts of law and law enforcement activities) in all actions concerning children. The full application of the concept of the *child's best interests* is inherently intertwined with the *child rights approach* engaging all actors to secure the child’s holistic integrity and human dignity.¹⁸⁶ Achieving this requires the cooperation of a broad range of institutions and actors, and the United Nations Model Strategies and Practical Measures on the Elimination of Violence against Children in the Field of Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice identify the “complementary roles of the criminal justice system, child protection agencies, health, education and social service sectors and, in some cases, informal justice systems in creating a protective environment and preventing and responding to incidents of violence against children”.¹⁸⁷

5.2. CoE Framework

In the European regional frame, the Council of Europe (CoE) is an international organisation based on cooperation causing the efficacy of its action to rely on the political will of its States Parties. This means that the efficacy of a convention’s objectives, in principle, depends not only on the ratification of the treaty by the States Parties of the Council of Europe but also on

¹⁸³ UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, General comment No. 13 (2011) on the right of the child to freedom from all forms of violence, 18 April 2011, CRC/C/GC/13, at para. 54(b) and (d); UN Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC), Guidelines on Justice in Matters involving Child Victims and Witnesses of Crime, 22 July 2005, Annex to Resolution 2005/20, especially at 10. – 14.

¹⁸⁴ UN Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC), Guidelines on Justice in Matters involving Child Victims and Witnesses of Crime, Annex to Resolution 2005/20, 22 July 2005. Regarding the interpretation of the right to be informed (at VII.) and the right to be heard (at VIII.) see also: UN Committee on the Rights of the Child (2009), General Comment no. 12 (2009): The right of the child to be heard, CRC/C/GC/12, 1 July 2009, at paras. 62 et seq.

¹⁸⁵ United Nations, Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the sale of children, child prostitution and child pornography, A/RES/54/263, adopted on 16 March 2001, entered into force on 18 January 2002.

¹⁸⁶ UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, General Comment No. 14 (2013) on the right of the child to have his or her best interests taken as a primary consideration (art. 3, para. 1), CRC/C/GC/14, 29 March 2013, at para. 5.

¹⁸⁷ United Nations, 2014, GA Resolution A/RES/69/194, adopted on 18 December 2014, 26 January 2015, Annex at para 23.

the adoption of all national measures necessary to implement the treaty by the relevant States Parties.¹⁸⁸

5.2.1. Convention No. 116 on Compensation of Victims of Violent Crimes

The CoE established the protection of victims' rights with the European Convention on the Compensation of Victims of Violent Crimes adopted on 24 November 1983 (Convention No. 116).¹⁸⁹ Convention No. 116 deals, on the one hand, with victims of intentional crimes who have suffered bodily injury or impairment of health and of dependants of persons who have died as a result of such crimes. On the other hand, Convention N. 116 deals with the need to introduce schemes for compensation for these victims by the state in whose territory the crime was committed,¹⁹⁰ in particular when the offender has not been identified or is without resources.¹⁹¹

According to Art. 3 Convention No. 116, two groups of victims are eligible to compensation: (i) nationals of the States Parties to the Convention and (ii) nationals of all Member States of the Council of Europe who are permanent residents in the state on whose territory the crime was committed. As a result of this approach, three groups of victims are excluded from a possible compensation: (i) the nationals of all Member States of the Council of Europe that are not States Parties to the Convention; (ii) the nationals of all Member States of the Council of Europe that are not permanent residents in the state on whose territory the crime was committed; and (iii) the nationals of third states.

The scope of the victim's compensation shall cover at least loss of earnings, medical and hospitalisation expenses and funeral expenses.¹⁹² However, Convention No. 116 allows States Parties not only to set for any element of compensation, if necessary, an upper limit,¹⁹³ but also to reduce or refuse victim's compensation in four situations: (i) on account of the applicant's financial situation;¹⁹⁴ (ii) on account of the victim's or the applicant's conduct before, during or after the crime;¹⁹⁵ (iii) on account of the victim's involvement in organised crime;¹⁹⁶ or (iv) if awarding compensation would be contrary to a sense of justice or to public policy (*ordre public*).

¹⁸⁸ Fernández de Casadevante Romani in: von Bogdandy/Wolfrum (eds.), Max Planck Yearbook of United Nations Law, Vol. 14, 2010, p. 219 (p. 231).

¹⁸⁹ CoE, Convention on the Compensation of Victims of Violent Crimes, Convention No. 116, adopted on 24 November 1983, entered into force on 1 February 1988.

¹⁹⁰ Art. 3 Convention No. 116.

¹⁹¹ Art. 2 Convention No. 116.

¹⁹² Art. 4 Convention No. 116.

¹⁹³ Art. 5 Convention No. 116.

¹⁹⁴ Art. 7 Convention No. 116.

¹⁹⁵ Art. 8(1) Convention No. 116.

¹⁹⁶ Art. 8(2) Convention No. 116.

5.2.2. Lanzarote Convention

While the CoE Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings (Convention No. 197)¹⁹⁷ already highlights particular needs of child victims in the context of all forms of trafficking in human beings for sexual exploitation,¹⁹⁸ the first instrument to establish the various forms of sexual abuse of children as criminal offences is the CoE Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse (Lanzarote Convention)¹⁹⁹. Art. 31 Lanzarote Convention indicates which general measures of protection States Parties should take to protect the rights and interests of victims, including their special needs as witnesses, at all stages of investigations and criminal proceedings. These measures include (i) informing child victims of their rights and the services at their disposal,²⁰⁰ (ii) enabling child victims to be heard and to supply evidence,²⁰¹ (iii) providing child victims with appropriate support services so that their rights and interests are duly presented and taken into account,²⁰² (iv) protecting their privacy, their identity and their image,²⁰³ (v) providing for their safety from intimidation, retaliation and repeat victimisation,²⁰⁴ (vi) ensuring that contact between child victims and perpetrators within court and LEA premises is avoided.²⁰⁵ In addition, Art. 31 Lanzarote Convention provides that child victims must have access to legal aid.²⁰⁶ At any stage, the information provided must be adapted to child victim's age and maturity and be in a language which the child victim understands.²⁰⁷

The Lanzarote Convention contains also requirements safeguarding interviews of a child victim against delays, child-unfriendly premises or unprofessional interviewers,²⁰⁸ and ensuring that hearings of a child victim in criminal court proceedings can either take place without the presence of the public or victim may be heard in the courtroom without being physically present.²⁰⁹

¹⁹⁷ CoE, Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings, Convention No. 197, adopted on 16 May 2005, entered into force on 1 February 2008.

¹⁹⁸ Convention No. 197 aims to design a comprehensive framework for the protection and assistance of victims, Art. 1(1)(b). For child victims, Convention No. 197 includes particular measures e.g. for their identification, Art. 10(4), for assistance in their physical, psychological and social recovery, Art. 12(1) and (7), and repatriation, Art. 16(7). Further, Convention No. 197 ensures that the child victim is afforded special protection measures taking into account the child's best interests before and during court proceedings, Art. 28 (3) and Art. 30.

¹⁹⁹ CoE, Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse, Convention No. 201, adopted on 25 October 2007, entered in to force on 1 July 2010.

²⁰⁰ Art. 31(1)(a) Lanzarote Convention.

²⁰¹ Art. 31(1)(c) Lanzarote Convention.

²⁰² Art. 31(1)(d) Lanzarote Convention.

²⁰³ Art. 31(1)(e) Lanzarote Convention.

²⁰⁴ Art. 31(1)(f) Lanzarote Convention.

²⁰⁵ Art. 31(1)(g) Lanzarote Convention.

²⁰⁶ Art. 31(3) Lanzarote Convention.

²⁰⁷ Art. 31(6) Lanzarote Convention.

²⁰⁸ Art. 35 Lanzarote Convention.

²⁰⁹ Art. 36(2) Lanzarote Convention.

5.2.3. Guidelines on Child Friendly Justice

As key reference point for how to make a justice system more adaptable to children, the CoE has issued Guidelines on Child-Friendly Justice.²¹⁰ These Guidelines also address the position of child victims, particularly when providing evidence in judicial proceedings, and suggest eleven specific measures in line with the Lanzarote Convention for allowing children to give evidence in the most favourable settings and under the most suitable conditions in the light of their age, maturity and level of understanding.²¹¹ To this end, the Guidelines recommend to involve trained professionals²¹² and encourage audiovisual statements²¹³ as well as the opportunity to give evidence in criminal cases without the presence of the alleged perpetrator.²¹⁴

The child-friendly approach promoted in the Guidelines builds on the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child²¹⁵ and has the *best interests of the child* as guiding thread.²¹⁶ However, the Guidelines are a non-binding instrument even when repeating relevant principles from a binding legal instrument of international law.²¹⁷

5.3. EU Framework

The EU has a solid set of instruments for victim's rights. Complemented by the Compensation Directive and EU rules on European protection orders, the Victims' Rights Directive establishes the right to access information, the right to support and protection, in accordance with victim's individual needs, and a set of procedural rights (section 5.3.1. below). The EU has further adopted instruments that respond to the specific needs of victims of particular crimes like the Anti-Trafficking Directive and the Directive against sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children (section 5.3.2. below). Because this set of instruments has not yet unfolded its full potential, the European Commission has set out a comprehensive strategy for improving the situation of child victims in the EU (section 5.3.3. below).

5.3.1. Victims' Rights Directive

²¹⁰ CoE, Guidelines of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe on child-friendly justice, adopted adopted by the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe on 17 November 2010.

²¹¹ CoE, Guidelines on Child-Friendly Justice, at para. 64 – 74.

²¹² CoE, Guidelines on Child-Friendly Justice, at para. 64.

²¹³ CoE, Guidelines on Child-Friendly Justice, at para. 65.

²¹⁴ CoE, Guidelines on Child-Friendly Justice, at para. 69.

²¹⁵ See section 4.1. above.

²¹⁶ E.g.: This guidance has been implemented in Art. 56(2) of the CoE, Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence, Convention No. 210, adopted on 11 May 2011, entered in to force on 1 August 2014.

²¹⁷ CoE, Guidelines on Child-Friendly Justice, at para. 15. Note for example, how the eleven recommendations in paras. 64. – 74. of the Guidelines mirror the requirements of Art. 31 Lanzarote Convention, as stated in para. 63. of the Guidelines' Explanatory Memorandum.

The Victim's Rights Directive 2012/29/EU²¹⁸ explicitly recognises the position of child victims and introduces minimum standards for their protection. Art. 1(2) Victim's Rights Directive provides that, when the victim is a child, his or her best interests are a primary consideration and must be assessed on an individual basis. In addition, a *child-sensitive approach* must prevail meaning that the child's age, maturity, views, needs and concerns have to be taken into account, when the child victim (and the child's legal representative) is informed of any measures or rights specifically focused on the child.

During criminal proceedings, child victims have the *right to be heard* and Member States must ensure that child victims can also provide evidence while due account is taken of the child victim's age and maturity.²¹⁹ The Member States also have prevent public dissemination of any information leading to the identification of a child victim²²⁰ and are obliged to protect the child victim's privacy, personal integrity and personal data.²²¹ For the purposes of the Victim's Rights Directive, child victims are presumed to have specific protection needs due to their vulnerability to secondary and repeat victimisation, to intimidation and to retaliation.²²² This leads to protective requirements regarding their interview during a criminal investigation²²³ as well as during court proceedings.²²⁴

Especially for child victims in criminal proceedings, Art. 24 Victim's Rights Directive (a) allows for all interviews with the child victim to be audiovisually recorded and used as evidence, (b) requires the appointment of special representatives, and (c) the right to legal representation in the child victim's own name if there is a conflict of interests between the child victim and the holders of parental responsibility. Last but not least, the Victim's Rights Directive contains various provisions for the protection of victims in general, such as the Right to receive information about their case,²²⁵ and the right to access to victim support services.²²⁶

The Victim's Rights Directive is complemented by the Victim's Compensation Directive²²⁷ as well as by the EU rules on European protection orders.²²⁸

²¹⁸ Directive 2012/29/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 establishing minimum standards on the rights, support and protection of victims of crime, and replacing Council Framework Decision 2001/220/JHA (Victim's Rights Directive), 14 November 2012, Official Journal of the EU, L 315, p. 57.

²¹⁹ Art. 10(1) Victim's Rights Directive.

²²⁰ Art. 21(1) Victim's Rights Directive.

²²¹ Art. 21(2) Victim's Rights Directive.

²²² Art. 22(4) Victim's Rights Directive.

²²³ The four requirements set out in Art. 23(2) Victim's Rights Directive not only ensure premises designed for the purpose (a), but also the proper training and the choice of the interviewing professional (b) – (d).

²²⁴ The four requirements set out in Art. 23(3) Victim's Rights Directive aim to avoid (a) visual contact between child victims and offenders, (b) ensure that the child victim may be heard in the courtroom without being physically present, (c) avoid unnecessary questioning concerning the child victim's private life not related to the criminal offence, and (d) the presence of the public during the child victim's hearing.

²²⁵ Art. 6 Victim's Rights Directive.

²²⁶ Art. 8 and 9 Victim's Rights Directive.

²²⁷ Council Directive 2004/80/EC of 29 April 2004 relating to compensation to crime victims, Official Journal of the EU, 6 August 2004, L 261, p. 15.

²²⁸ Directive 2011/99/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on the European protection order and Regulation (EU) No 606/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 June 2013 on mutual recognition of protection measures in civil matters.

5.3.2. Directives on Specific Needs of Child Victims

Before adopting the Victim's Rights Directive, the EU had adopted in 2011 two instruments that respond to the specific needs of child victims of particular crimes: the Anti-Trafficking Directive,²²⁹ and the Directive Against Sexual Abuse and Sexual Exploitation of Children.²³⁰ Both Directives aim to harmonise the preventive criminalisation of their respective crimes and to establish a set of child victim's rights which especially relevant in the context of CSE and CSEM material.

- **Anti-Trafficking Directive**

The Anti-Trafficking Directive 2011/36/EU establishes the rule that a child victim of trafficking in human beings is provided with the assistance, support and protection serving the child's best interests.²³¹ Independently of any criminal investigation or court proceeding, the assistance and support measures have to cater to the individual child victim's physical and psycho-social recovery in the short and long term.²³²

For criminal investigations and proceedings, child victims not only have to be appointed a representative,²³³ but also have undelayed access to free legal counselling and to free legal representation, including for the purpose of claiming compensation,²³⁴ unless they have sufficient financial resources.²³⁵ Member States have to take the necessary measures to ensure that any interview of the child victim in the course of a criminal investigation and proceeding meets the procedural requirements set out in Art. 15(3), (4) and (5) Anti-Trafficking Directive which overlap and partially supplement the procedural requirements established in Art. 23(2) and (3) Victim's Rights Directive.

- **Directive Against Sexual Abuse and Sexual Exploitation of Children**

The main focus of the Directive Against Sexual Abuse and Sexual Exploitation of Children 2011/93/EU is to establish minimum rules concerning the definition of criminal offences and sanctions in the area of sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children, "child pornography" and solicitation of children for sexual purposes. However, Directive 2011/93/EU also introduces provisions to strengthen the protection of the victims thereof:²³⁶

²²⁹ Directive 2011/36/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2011 on preventing and combating trafficking in human beings and protecting its victims, and replacing Council Framework Decision 2002/629/JHA, Official Journal of the EU, 15 April 2011, L 101, p. 1.

²³⁰ Directive 2011/93/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on combating the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child pornography, and replacing Council Framework Decision 2004/68/JHA, Official Journal of the EU, 17 December 2011, L 335, p. 1.

²³¹ Art. 13(1) Anti-Trafficking Directive.

²³² Art. 14(1) Anti-Trafficking Directive.

²³³ Art. 15(1) Anti-Trafficking Directive.

²³⁴ Art. 17 Anti-Trafficking Directive requires Member States to provide (child) victims with access to existing schemes of compensation to victims of violent crimes of intent.

²³⁵ Art. 15(2) Anti-Trafficking Directive.

²³⁶ Art. 1 Directive 2011/93/EU.

While child victims are neither to be prosecuted nor to be imposed penalties for their involvement in criminal activities, which they have been compelled to commit as a direct consequence of being subjected offences concerning their sexual exploitation or “child pornography”,²³⁷ establishes the rule that a child victim of these offences is provided with the assistance, support and protection serving the child’s best interests.²³⁸ This assistance and support has to be provided before, during and for an appropriate period of time after the conclusion of criminal proceedings in order to enable them to exercise the rights.²³⁹

For criminal investigations and proceedings, child victims not only have to be appointed a representative,²⁴⁰ but also have undelayed access to free legal counselling and to free legal representation, including for the purpose of claiming compensation,²⁴¹ unless they have sufficient financial resources.²⁴² Member States have to take the necessary measures to ensure that any interview of the child victim in the course of a criminal investigation and proceeding meets the procedural requirements set out in Art. 20(3), (4) and (5) Directive 2011/93/EU which are identical to the procedural requirements established in Art. 15 Anti-Trafficking Directive. These procedural requirements overlap and partially supplement the procedural requirements established in Art. 23(2) and (3) Victim’s Rights Directive which was adopted a year later.

5.3.3. EU Strategy on Victims’ Rights

In 2020, the Report on the implementation of the Victim’s Rights Directive²⁴³ and the Report on the implementation of the Directive on European protection order²⁴⁴ revealed significant shortcomings in the Member States’ implementation of harmonised victims’ rights. These shortcomings were reminiscent of the previous two Reports on the implementation of the Child Sexual Abuse Directive²⁴⁵ and the Report on the implementation of the Anti-Trafficking

²³⁷ Art. 14 Directive 2011/93/EU referring to Art. 4(2), (3), (5) and (6) regarding sexual exploitation and to Art. 5(6) regarding “child pornography”.

²³⁸ Art. 18(1) Directive 2011/93/EU.

²³⁹ Art. 19(1) Directive 2011/93/EU.

²⁴⁰ Art. 20(1) Directive 2011/93/EU.

²⁴¹ The right to compensation emanates from Framework Decision 2001/220/JHA which establishes a set of victims’ rights in criminal proceedings, see: Recital 32 Directive 2011/93/EU.

²⁴² Art. 20(2) Directive 2011/93/EU.

²⁴³ Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on the implementation of the Victims’ Rights Directive, COM(2020)188 final, 11 May 2020, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2020:188:FIN>.

²⁴⁴ Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on the implementation of Directive 2011/99/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on the European protection order, COM(2020)187final, 11 May 2020, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2020:187:FIN>

²⁴⁵ Two reports: Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council assessing the extent to which the Member States have taken the necessary measures in order to comply with Directive 2011/93/EU of 13 December 2011 on combating the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child pornography, COM/2016/0871 final, 16 December 2016, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52016DC0871>; Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council assessing the implementation of the measures referred to in Article 25 of Directive 2011/93/EU of 13 December 2011 on combating the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child pornography, COM/2016/0872 final, 16 December 2016, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=COM:2016:872:FIN>.

Directive²⁴⁶, both of which had revealed essential shortcomings as well. In the light of all these shortcomings and because the lockdown of society during the COVID-19 pandemic had led to a rise in domestic violence, child sexual abuse and cybercrime, the European Commission issued a first EU Strategy on victims' rights in June 2020 in order to strengthen the framework for support and protection of victims and ensure it is resilient in crisis situations.²⁴⁷

Summarising the bigger picture revealed by the implementation Reports mentioned above, the Commission points out that victims' difficulties in accessing justice are mainly due to lack of information, insufficient support and protection. Victims are often exposed to secondary victimisation during criminal proceedings and when claiming compensation. Those who become victims of crime when travelling abroad find it even more difficult to access justice and compensation. For the most vulnerable victims including child victims it remains particularly challenging to go through criminal proceedings and to deal with the aftermath of crime.²⁴⁸

In order to improve the situation for victims, it is crucial that all Member States fully implement and apply the agreed minimum standards described in this section 4.3. Therefore, the Commission will focus on ensuring the correct implementation of these existing EU rules on victims' rights in practice.²⁴⁹ Based on a two-strand approach, empowering victims of crime and working together for victims' rights, the Commission elaborates five key priorities for the next five years: (i) effective communication with victims and a safe environment for victims to report crime;²⁵⁰ (ii) improving support and protection to the most vulnerable victims;²⁵¹ (iii) facilitating victims' access to compensation;²⁵² (iv) strengthening cooperation and coordination among all relevant actors;²⁵³ and (v) strengthening the international dimension of victims' rights.²⁵⁴

6. Online Searches

²⁴⁶ Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council assessing the extent to which Member States have taken the necessary measures in order to comply with Directive 2011/36/EU on preventing and combating trafficking in human beings and protecting its victims in accordance with Article 23 (1), COM(2016) 722 final, 2 December 2016, available at: https://ec.europa.eu/anti-trafficking/sites/antitrafficking/files/report_on_member_states_compliance_with_directive_2011-36_en.pdf.

²⁴⁷ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, The European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on EU Strategy on victims' rights (2020-2025), COM(2020) 258 final, 24 June 2020, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0258&from=EN>.

²⁴⁸ Commission, Communication on EU Strategy on victims' rights (2020-2025), COM(2020) 258 final, 24 June 2020, p. 2.

²⁴⁹ Commission, Communication on EU Strategy on victims' rights (2020-2025), COM(2020) 258 final, 24 June 2020, p. 3.

²⁵⁰ Commission, Communication on EU Strategy on victims' rights (2020-2025), COM(2020) 258 final, 24 June 2020, p. 4 et seq.

²⁵¹ Commission, Communication on EU Strategy on victims' rights (2020-2025), COM(2020) 258 final, 24 June 2020, p. 8 et seq.

²⁵² Commission, Communication on EU Strategy on victims' rights (2020-2025), COM(2020) 258 final, 24 June 2020, p. 16 et seq.

²⁵³ Commission, Communication on EU Strategy on victims' rights (2020-2025), COM(2020) 258 final, 24 June 2020, p. 19 et seq.

²⁵⁴ Commission, Communication on EU Strategy on victims' rights (2020-2025), COM(2020) 258 final, 24 June 2020, p. 21 et seq.

A central element of cybercrime investigations are searches online. Whether following an initial suspicion or routinely patrolling public online spaces, LEA investigators have to search the surface web and often the dark web as well in order to fulfil law enforcement's mandate to keep society safe.

6.1. Targeted Investigation and Preventive Purposes

At least in civil law countries, LEAs will not be able to investigate crimes without specific laws in place authorising such investigation.²⁵⁵ In order to carry out the investigations, they need to be able to base their investigations on procedural instruments that enable them to take the measures that are necessary to identify an offender and collect the evidence required for the criminal proceedings.²⁵⁶ These measures can be the same ones that are undertaken in other investigations not related to Internet-related content. However, investigating activities of criminals or members of illegal organisations that act online goes along with some unique challenges. As a consequence, investigations may be carried out in a different way compared to traditional investigations.²⁵⁷ If an offender was for example based in one country²⁵⁸, used services that enable anonymous communication and, in addition, published cybercriminal content online by using different public Internet terminals, the identification of the suspect can hardly be based on traditional instruments like search and seizure alone.

With regard to criminal investigations related to cybercriminal use of the Internet the CoE Convention on Cybercrime contains a set of provisions that reflect widely accepted *minimum standards* regarding procedural instruments required for online investigations.²⁵⁹ The CoE Convention on Cybercrime even addresses issues of high relevance – such as the question if LEAs are allowed to access information available on servers located in another country.

While this is very helpful in criminal investigations, it is important to underline that the CYCLOPES project does not solely focus on enhancing the ability of LEAs in retrospectively investigating cybercrime. Rather, the CYCLOPES project focusses equally strong on prevention. As a consequence, the content-based functions of potentially suggested

²⁵⁵ This was also highlighted by the drafters of the Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime, which contains a set of essential investigation instruments. The drafters of the report point out: “Not only must substantive criminal law keep abreast of these new abuses, but so must criminal procedural law and investigative techniques”, see: Explanatory Report to the Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime, No. 132.

²⁵⁶ Regarding user-based approaches in the fight against cybercrime, see: Goerling, The Myth Of User Education, 2006, at www.parasite-economy.com/texts/StefanGorlingVB2006.pdf. See also the comment made by Jean- Pierre Chevenement, French Minister of Interior, at the G8 Conference in Paris in 2000: “More broadly, we have to educate users. They must all understand what they can and can’t do on the Internet and be warned of the potential dangers. As use of the Internet grows, we’ll naturally have to step up our efforts in this respect.”

²⁵⁷ Due to the protocols used in Internet communication and worldwide accessibility, there is very little need for a physical presence at the place where a service is physically offered. Due to this independence of place of action and the crime site, many criminal offences related to the Internet are transnational crimes.

²⁵⁸ The pure fact that the offender is acting from a different country can result in additional challenges for law-enforcement agencies’ investigations even if similar substantive criminal law provisions and procedural law instruments are in place in both countries. In these cases, the investigation nevertheless requires international cooperation between the authorities in both countries, which in general is more time consuming compared to investigations concentrating on a single country.

²⁵⁹ See Articles 15-21 of the Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime.

investigative tools – such as searching, crawling, monitoring as well as gathering, mining and analysing of data – will not be part of a specific investigation but in general independent of investigations in a specific case.

In short: When it comes to suggesting the use of automating investigative tools, it will be important for LEAs to clarify one main question: Is there a provision in national legislation permitting the LEA to carry out automated searches for potential cybercrime content/activities independently of a specific case.

6.2. Use of Search Robots

A review of the legislation in different EU Member States revealed that various investigative instruments exist, that cover the collection of information – a key focus area of currently available search tools. However, it is important to underline that the impact of a single action (carried out manually by an investigator) and an automated mass collection of data could have a significantly different impact.²⁶⁰ Depending on the capacities of a search tool used to collect data from public sources on the surface web and on the dark web, the search tool will not only be able to identify specific content but also even produce profiles of people that published the content.

Automated search tools could increasingly be designed to analyse the collected data in terms of visual, audio and text information using AI technologies to produce structured and validated information about its content. Novel forensic analysis tools could be developed for cybercrime-specific content analysis and classification, content-based geo-localisation and the creation of evidence graphs to connect cases. By applying audio-visual analysis technique capabilities to cybercrime investigations, automated search tools could be able to provide the option to extract, cluster and automatically tag and match shapes and objects from pictures and videos (e.g., buildings or specific objects that facilitate the geolocation of a picture or the identification of a suspect). Further, the automated search tools could also serve to introduce enhanced predictive analytics to LEAs allowing them to determine patterns and predict trends and threats filling the gap between the strategic and operational activities towards identifying suitable tactics and techniques as well as assisting in defining and deriving crime-relevant indicators corresponding to criminal behaviours.

The automation of large-scale data collection and mining for criminal investigations was contested in different Member States. In 2008 the German Constitutional Court for example decided that the automatic collection of registered license plate information on motorways can be permitted but storing such data for longer periods of time can go along with a violation of fundamental rights related to privacy.²⁶¹ Storing the collected data could be a potential main function of an automated search tool.

²⁶⁰ With regard to the impact of mass surveillance see for example: Lyon, Surveillance, power, and everyday life, published in Avgerou/Mansell/Quah/SilverStone, *The Oxford Handbook of Information and Communication Technologies*, 2009; Surveillance and censorship: The impact of technologies on human rights, European Parliament, Directorate-General for External Policies, 2015.

²⁶¹ See: German Constitutional Court, 1 BvR 2075/05. With regard to decisions from different EU member states see: Kindt, *Privacy and Data Protection Issues of Biometric Applications*, 2013, page 927 et seq.

D7.7. First Updated SEL Report with Recommendations

In short: When identifying provisions authorising the use of automated search tools, it is important to not only focus on provisions authorising a single and manual act but the automated collection of data.

7. Conflict with Civil Law Requirements

Contracts and the requirements of copyright and privacy laws in the digital sector are determined by areas of civil law which hold individuals accountable to the terms stated within a copyright agreement or digital contract. Contractual agreements (i.e., contract law) provide a legally binding set of explicit or implicit terms that set out the obligations of each party. The impact of Civil Law on cybercrime investigations is particularly relevant to the usage of tools or acquisition of data, and, in particular where, aspects of investigation utilise an online platform that places certain restrictions on its use through its terms of service. Within Europe, the Rome I Regulation enables Member States to determine which countries laws are applicable in each case.²⁶²

An example of how such contractual obligations may apply and have arisen in relation to cybercrime investigation can be seen through the case where the American Civil Liberties Union (ACLU) identified that the online platform Geofeedia (now Echosec) facilitated the monitoring and tracking of BLM (Black Lives Matter) protestors on social media (mainly Facebook, Twitter and Instagram) by LEAs in the United States.²⁶³ Due to the findings by the ACLU, social media platforms started placing restrictions against LEAs in their terms of service preventing them from using their platforms to perform specific activities where previously they may have had enhanced data access. This places limitations on LEAs' ability to carry out certain investigations online due to much stricter terms of service. In CYCLOPES, LEAs have highlighted, even in the first year of workshops, that open-source intelligence (OSINT) capabilities are required to support them in their everyday investigative roles.

This section will consider the legal implications for cybercrime investigators where they may come into conflict with civil law including both copyright infringements and licencing agreements. The growing need for Artificial Intelligence (AI) solutions, whilst raising ethical concerns in some cases, also often requires large datasets to train and test models. LEAs utilising such technology may come into conflict with copyright, terms of services and licencing restrictions while other technologies such as web crawlers may indiscriminately (although albeit unintentionally) collect copyrighted information.

Civil law requirements therefore may place constraints on how LEAs can utilise such technology, even when this may not be limitation on the general public's use of the same service. Ultimately, despite their status, LEAs cannot take a *carte blanche*²⁶⁴ approach to contract law and should ensure that they respect the requirements provided in contracts. This chapter discusses and demonstrates how such requirements may impact cybercrime investigators and how LEAs may navigate such issues with respect to civil law. In a LEA environment, EU Member State's LEAs must comply with both, the EU legislative environment and comply the national civil code as well as identifying which may take precedence in certain

²⁶² Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations (Rome I)

²⁶³ Leven, S. (2016) ACLU finds social media sites gave data to company tracking black protesters. The Guardian. 11 October 2016. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2016/oct/11/aclu-geofeedia-facebook-twitter-instagram-black-lives-matter>

²⁶⁴ Translates to 'blank document' suggesting a 'free reign' over the law

situations. The EU provides some exceptions for LEAs in copyright law through Article 34 of *Directive 2001/29/EC*²⁶⁵ which is discussed in more detail in the next section.

7.1. Implications for Copyright

Copyright law falls under the banner of Intellectual Property (IP) law and this legislation determines the rights of creators and individuals who create content and the rights of those who wish to access or use content created by others. Such content includes everything from artistic and literary works to software, online content, film and television broadcasts. Therefore, if investigators utilise online content or even adapt existing online tools they should be aware of copyright restrictions.

Historically, copyright laws were designed to protect creative originality of designers, creators, producers etc and have been found to date back to Ancient Greece and Rome where authors would insist upon a '*right of paternity*'²⁶⁶ regarding their work which was a '*droit moral*'²⁶⁷ which is still a legitimate form of legal classification that is referred to within the English Law; Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1988.²⁶⁸ The historical application of copyright highlights the importance of protecting the works and products of creators, and still applies today within the digital context. Due to the more dynamic nature of the digital environment, law that predates this era may require flexibility in interpretation to align with modern-day applications. Copyright law prohibits the reproducing of copyright-protected material, which in most cases is a civil rather than a criminal offence and is not part of EU law but rather the responsibility of the individual Member State's criminal and civil code. While CYCLOPES as a project recommends tools for use by cybercrime investigators, it is the responsibility of the LEA or the investigator themselves to ensure the use of such tools is in compliance with all copyright considering how each tool and/or functionality collates and stores data, however, recommendations would be subjective pertinent to a country's legal requirements.

*Deliverable D3.2*²⁶⁹ has highlighted the suggested techniques including possible technological solutions that are available for end-users based on their requirements for the investigation of cybercrime. In particular, web crawlers have been identified as a useful tool to collect information from the surface, deep and dark web. Web crawlers could be problematic for investigators to maintain compliance with civil law requirements as in general they are not evaluating the potential for copyright infringement for each element of data collected. To function currently, the web crawlers must also store the information collected and therefore, this can exacerbate copyright concerns if this data is stored in the long-term.

In the context of research, the EU's Copyright Directive provides an exemption for scientific research; however, in general this would not be applicable to the operational activities pursued as a result of the recommendations from CYCLOPES. Therefore, the uptake of tools generated

²⁶⁵ European Commission, Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society Article 34

²⁶⁶ See *Little History of Copyright: A Chronology in Relation to Music*, University of Chiester 2001 1

²⁶⁷ Translates to 'Moral Right' in the Context of Copyright Law

²⁶⁸ Copyright, Designs and Patents Act 1998 IV

²⁶⁹ D3.2 *Research Innovation and Market Watch (Draft)*

through the results of research projects (e.g., Horizon 2020) should be evaluated to ensure they do not or have not infringe any copyright laws in the tool development or underpinning data. A further complication may arise if a tool has been developed during research activities (taking advantage of the copyright exemption) and produces good results leading to a desire to implement such tools by LEAs.

Overall, given the jurisdictional factors in play for the application of civil law whereby each Member State holds different national laws referring to copyright, there is no universal EU civil law (just the rules for identifying which Member State law applies in cross-jurisdictional cases). Such differences also mean that there may also be variations in the utilisation of a specific technology and how it can be employed operationally. Full legal compliance should be ensured before any application of a technology that acquires data from external sources.

The *Directive 2001/29/EC* on the “*harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society*”²⁷⁰ allows Member States ‘certain exceptions or limitations such as educational and scientific purposes [...] public security and [...] judicial proceedings’ (Article 3(e)). This acknowledges that the work in public security settings, which includes law enforcement operations, may require certain exceptions to copyright; however, this is dependent on the implementation of Directive 2001/29/EC by the respective Member State. The exception specifically only refers to Article 2 (right to reproduction) and Article 3 (right to communication) and not to Article 4 (right to distribution). Therefore, when recommending tools, CYCLOPES is required to be aware of the possible implications of technology at the feasibility and deployment stages, avoiding any possible legal challenges. Given the differences in implementation at the Member State level, each jurisdiction may need to check the specifics of compliance. Furthermore, definitions of OSINT (open-source intelligence) often mean that data that is subject to copyright would not meet the threshold to be considered ‘open-source’.²⁷¹

7.2. License agreements, access restrictions, and online platform terms and condition

Navigating online spaces means that investigators will likely encounter terms and conditions (or terms of service) and licences (or licencing agreements) either to utilise the platform itself (create an account, for example) or to use downloaded software. When agreeing to use such services, this agreement forms a contract between the service provider and the service user and therefore falls under the definition of contract law. A contract can be defined as

²⁷⁰ European Commission, Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society

²⁷¹ E.g., “*The main qualifiers to open-source information are that it does not require any type of clandestine collection techniques to obtain it and that it must be obtained through means that entirely meet the copyright and commercial requirements of the vendors where applicable.*” Mark M Lowenthal – Former Assistant Director of Central Intelligence for Analysis and Production, US Central Intelligence Agency.
<https://mediasonar.com/2020/04/30/legal-ethical-osint/>

*'a legally binding promise (written or oral) by one party to fulfil an obligation to another party in return for consideration. A basic binding contract must comprise four key elements: offer, acceptance, consideration, and intent to create legal relations.'*²⁷²

To legally enforce a contract, it must be seen as legitimate in the eyes of the Law; regardless of adjudication, a contract must have functioning elements to it showing the willingness to engage in such agreement. How an individual chooses to communicate their acceptance is a subjective matter that has been installed within precedent.

Terms of service are one example of a contract between a user and service provider. For example, when signing up to a site (such as a social media platform) the platform provides a set of conditions the user must agree to when using the site. This includes how the platform uses the data provided and what they can do with such data. In the case of an investigator wish to obtain information from a site, they may have four options (1) utilise a web crawler; (2) use a platform provided API (application programming interface); (3) obtain the data through a third party; or (4) make formal request to the platform to provide the data. Each of these options has different contractual implications for the investigator based on the term of service of the site – in this section we consider only how aspects (1) and (2) apply.

Firstly, a standardised approach to communicating what information can and cannot be scraped is through the *robots.txt* file; different sites allow different levels of access. For example, Twitter states the following is permissible through their Terms of Service (ToS) *"crawling the Services is permissible if done in accordance with the provisions of the robots.txt file, however, scraping the Services without the prior consent of Twitter is expressly prohibited"*. Conversely, if a user embeds a Tweet in their page they give Twitter, a 'non-exclusive, royalty free, non-transferable, non-sublicensable revocable license to access, index, and cache by any means, including web spiders and/or crawlers.'²⁷³ This is an example also of the imbalance of power between service providers and users. Other platforms, such as Facebook, have much stricter ToS. Facebook (now Meta Platforms), state that they forbid 'automated means (without our prior permission) or attempt to access data that you do not have permission to access.'²⁷⁴ Given the repeated desire for cybercrime investigators to use crawling and scraping tools the disparities and limitations on accessing such data should be key consideration.

A further legal complication is highlighted by the outcome of the case of *HiQ Labs, Inc. v. LinkedIn Corp* in the US. The judge found that using a web scraper did not break the U.S Computer Fraud and Abuse Act (CFAA). This case brought by LinkedIn was that its data was being unlawfully obtained by a web crawler via 'unauthorised access' (a crime as constituted by the CFAA). In recent months, this case has reached its final state of opinion, resulting in half a million dollars' being paid in damages. The US Court of Appeal found that HiQ Labs in fact did breach the terms of service of LinkedIn and therefore had also been permanently banned from developing, using, selling, or distributing any software or code for crawling tools for data collection. This has set a precedent that violating terms of services holds a significant

²⁷² Thomas Reuters (n.d) Contract. In Thomas Reuters Practical Law. 2022, Retrieved 26 April 2022

²⁷³ See Twitter, Developer Agreement and Policy' 2020 retrieved from <https://developer.twitter.com/en/developer-terms/agreement-and-policy>

²⁷⁴ Meta Platforms Inc. (2020) Facebook: Terms of Service' 3(2) retrieved from <https://www.facebook.com/terms.php>

financial implication plus an effect on the process of business due to their permanent ban on services. Cybercrime investigators should be aware of the effects of not adhering to appropriate agreements – especially those operating within the field of Law Enforcement. The findings from this case set a strong precedent across the United States; that while developers suggestibly have used web crawlers against a term of service, this opinion in the US courts sets out the repercussions of ignoring these agreements.

In addition, the case of *HiQ Labs, Inc. v. LinkedIn Corp* highlights the complexity of the law surrounding web crawling and scraping; and that it can go beyond the ToS. Within the EU, as the information scraped also concerns personal data, both the GDPR and the Law Enforcement Directive may apply and the investigator may need to demonstrate they have an appropriate lawful basis for obtaining such data – especially if it was in significant quantities. This ultimately requires, that in a European setting, for the interests of LEAs to also consider the protection of personal data, privacy rights and whether they are acting under national law or union law. Nonetheless, the case of *HiQ Labs, Inc. v. LinkedIn Corp* is a landmark case in the United States when referring to publicly accessible data as this case can prevent the creation of ‘information monopolies that would disserve the public interest.’²⁷⁵

Obtaining information either through web crawling, scraping or through an API must be carried out with respect of the ToS of platform. For example, the ToS for developers using any aspect of Meta Platforms (Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram) (i.e., APIs, SDKs, tools, plugins, code, technology, content, and services) has the following restriction under Section 3 – Data Use²⁷⁶

(a) **Prohibited Practices.** *You will not perform, or facilitate or support others in performing, any of the following prohibited practices (collectively, “Prohibited Practices”):*

...

iii. *Processing Platform Data to perform, facilitate, or provide tools for surveillance. Surveillance includes the Processing of Platform Data about people, groups, or events for law enforcement or national security purposes.*

Twitter also makes a similar strong statement in their developer ToS: ²⁷⁷

“In no event shall your use, or knowingly display, distribute, or otherwise make Twitter Content, or information derived from Twitter Content, available to any Government End User whose primary function or mission includes conducting surveillance or gathering intelligence.”

Therefore, any cybercrime investigator accessing online information, even through a third party, from these and other sites with similar policies faces a dilemma of how to effectively navigate compliance with ToS whilst obtaining the intelligence and/or evidence required to effectively carry out their function effectively.

²⁷⁵ *HiQ Labs, Inc. v. LinkedIn Corp.*, 938 F.3d 985

²⁷⁶ Meta Platforms – Platform Terms. https://developers.facebook.com/terms/dfc_platform_terms/#datause

²⁷⁷ Developer Agreement and Policy – Twitter. <https://developer.twitter.com/en/developer-terms/agreement-and-policy>

Contracts in a digital context also utilise and enforce an End User License Agreements (EULA). An EULA has specific requirements that must be adhered too when utilising the referenced tools – this is also applied to the use of software for performing cybercrime investigations. Failing to adhere to terms in the EULA can cause a license agreement to be terminated, for example, removal of the account or the accounts’ privileges to access the data. The EULA may also state the copyright terms in relation to the software; therefore, they are introduced to grant a license to any user who has bought a copy. If it is found that the software is being exploited in a manner that does not comply with the EULA of the software; it can be terminated. Therefore, understanding the ToS/EULA of any software purchased or the rights under any software provided through open-source licences.

Research and educational institutes can supersede some of the requirements if they are authorised by Member State law specifically for research purposes; however, cybercrime investigators and LEAs are required to act accordingly and comply with ToS, EULA and other licencing agreements unless there are exceptions within their national law. Therefore, it is important that any technology or service is fully assessed prior to use and implementation, especially if it could negatively affect further court cases based on the admissibility of the evidence.

8. Legal Bases for Engagement with Persons of Interest

Like in any other traditional crime investigation, cybercrime investigators seek to obtain the necessary information through the overt or covert collection of the evidence. The covert methods traditionally can involve the gathering of intelligence also through undercover infiltration of crimes groups or the use of an ‘agent provocateur’. These approaches are inherent in policing investigative procedures and have been instilled also law enforcement officers from basic training and throughout their policing careers. While specialised cybercrime investigation units are too few and far across the EU Member States to apply these approaches in person for all cybercrime cases, with the emergence of artificial intelligence it seems more than likely that advanced investigative tools can be developed for automated interactive communication with potential persons of interest. Such advanced investigative tools could support effectively investigator’s handling of the prevalence of information and communication technology in cybercrime investigations. This section takes a look at the potential automation of traditional undercover operations and the use of an “agent provocateur” through an advanced investigative tool for automated interactive communication with cybercriminals the development of which could aid LEA’s cybercrime units.

8.1. Undercover Operations and Their Automation

Some functions of Advanced investigative tools could include functions for automated communication in forums where cybercrime or criminal content is posted and discussed. In general, such functions require covert operations because such interaction could fail if the advanced investigative tool used identities that reveal that they are associated to a LEA. An initial end user assessment pointed out a certain need for being able to create social media accounts that cannot be traced back to the acting LEA. Undercover online investigations are not a new technique. They are for example used with regard to Internet sex offenders.²⁷⁸

Closely related to the issue of automated searches independently of a specific case (section 6.1. above) is the question which authority is responsible for using each specific function provided in an advanced investigative tool. In most countries, not all LEAs are automatically mandated to search for cybercrime content online. Some countries strictly separate between preventive police work and investigation of crimes. In addition, some countries have specialised units that are responsible for dealing with cybercrime, organised crime and terrorism.

In short: In view of the territorial fragmentation of criminal law, it can be expected that the application of advanced investigative tools and solutions could be more challenging in some countries than in others. Therefore, it could be important to be able to restrict specific functions of such an investigative tool. Such restrictions could be achieved through a customisation for Member States. Such customisation could also be the solution in countries in which various

²⁷⁸ See for example: Mitchell/Wolak/Finkelhor/Jones, Investigators using the Internet to apprehend sex offenders: findings from the Second National Juvenile Online Victimization Study, Police Practice and Research, 2011; Vendius, Proactive Undercover Policing and Sexual Crimes against Children on the Internet, The European Review of Organized Crime 2 (2), 2015, page 6 et seq.

authorities and split up mandates might require the possibility to restrict specific functions of an investigative tool.

8.2. Agent Provocateur

The use of an “agent provocateur” could be another useful function of advanced investigative tools (such as automated interactive communication in forums where cybercrime content is posted and discussed) which would, in general, require covert operations.

Such interaction could fail if the advanced investigative tool used identities that reveal that they are associated to a LEA. Within the end user assessment, end users pointed out their need for being able to create social media accounts that cannot be traced back to the acting LEA. The undercover use of an “agent provocateur” is an instrument frequently used in investigations related to online child abuse.²⁷⁹ The use in investigations related to terrorism is intensively discussed and various cases are documented.²⁸⁰

In short: Because in some countries the use of advanced investigative tools can be challenging, Therefore, it could be important to be able to restrict specific functions of an considered investigative tool. Such restrictions could be achieved through a customisation.

²⁷⁹ See Martellozzo, Policing online child sexual abuse – the British experience, *European Journal of policing Studies*, 3 (1), 2015, page 32 et seq.

²⁸⁰ See for example: Bjelopera, *The Federal Bureau of Investigation and Terrorism Investigations*, 2013, CRS R 41780.

9. Electronic Evidence & Digital Forensics

Electronic evidence (or e-evidence) is now almost ubiquitous in criminal investigations regardless of whether they have a cybercrime component. That said, cybercrime or digital forensics investigations are likely to have a high proportion of electronic evidence to preserve and consider. This chapter will analyse how e-evidence is collated and processed in cybercrime and digital forensics investigations and the legal implications of such activities. Such processes need to consider the entire lifecycle of the process of collecting any data/evidence that is generated, processed, or transmitted by an electronic device.

E-evidence may be acquired through digital forensics techniques but may also be retrieved through online investigations or through specific platform or service provider requests. E-evidence must be handled appropriately to ensure it is admissible in court. In 2018, the European Commission began the preparations for better regulation of e-evidence with proposals for both a directive²⁸¹ and a regulation on e-evidence in cross-border information sharing settings.²⁸² These preparations have led to the final eEvidence Package which is detailed in section 11.3.2 below.

The concept of e-evidence touches almost all elements of cybercrime and digital forensics investigation from crime scene through to the prosecution of offenders. There are challenges in both the technical implementation and assurance of e-evidence as well as ethical considerations in relation to Fundamental Rights (e.g. Article 8 (Right to Privacy) of the Charter on Fundamental Rights).

The European Union, therefore, has already introduced 'European Production and Preservation Orders' as highlighted within Section 11.3.2 below as a legally binding instruments for court admissible documentation that protects Human Rights. This chapter will highlight requirements and responsibilities for obtaining, processing and preserving e-evidence by LEAs referring to any political, legal, and social factors. This includes Digital Forensics techniques as well as other aspects of cybercrime investigation.

Due to the scale of the recommendations provided by the CYCLOPES project – this chapter will also dissect the possible instances of cross-border communications regarding criminal investigations and the use of e-evidence and digital forensics in combating cybercrime.

9.1 Electronic Evidence

Electronic Evidence is information that has been obtained from digital devices or procured online and meets the threshold for 'evidence' in relation to investigating or prosecuting an offence. Depending on the jurisdiction, several broad categories of evidence are currently admissible in court. In addition to digital evidence, some examples are as follows:

²⁸¹ Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL laying down harmonised rules on the appointment of legal representatives for the purpose of gathering evidence in criminal proceedings (COM/2018/226 final)

²⁸² Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on European Production and Preservation Orders for electronic evidence in criminal matters (COM/2018/225 final)

- Real (Material) Evidence - Producers of physical forensics: Fingerprints, DNA, a knife (in a murder case for example.)
- Demonstrative Evidence – This evidence that expands a testimony by displaying information via images, maps and charts based solely on the information that has been given by the witness in their trial.²⁸³
- Documentary Evidence – This is evidence from a reliable source that contains only documentation that relates to the case and is authentic (not fraudulent). Documentary Evidence for example could be a contract, business records, letters etc.²⁸⁴
- Testimonial Evidence – this is where a witness testifies regarding their evidence of observation on the stand under oath within court.²⁸⁵

Digital or electronic evidence can come from multiple sources which include digital devices (e.g., laptops, desktop and tablets and their associated data storage components); external data storage devices (e.g., memory sticks, SD cards, external drives); cloud storage data; mobile phone data, online service providers data (e.g., social media, messages, photographs, etc.), public camera data, as well as other communications-based data.

A significant proportion of digital data may contain personal identifiable information and therefore this can impact an individual's fundamental rights. Further challenges also arise through its ephemeral nature and its fragility in terms of its propensity for modification²⁸⁶ and deletion.²⁸⁷ This has already been noted as a concern by experts in digital evidence and forensics²⁸⁸ whereby the ability to preserve such evidence is essential for future trials; maintaining the chain of custody is therefore an essential component of any digital tool or technique employed to collect or analyse digital evidence.

One of the main concerns surrounding e-evidence is ensuring its admissibility given a lack of formalised processes that come with new and emerging technologies.²⁸⁹ This key concern was highlighted by the European Law Institute when specifically focusing on the further complications raised by cross-border exchange of e-evidence. This background led to the introduction of a new legislative package within the European Union, proposed by the European Commission, to overcome these concerns and the current legal vacuum (see section 11.3.2. below). While this main concern is further exacerbated by the potential for specific restrictions or requirements placed on LEAs by individual countries. Fortunately, the European Union's draft legislative package for "eEvidence" will provide a significant uplift into

²⁸³ Thomson Reuters 'Demonstrative Evidence' Practical Law Glossary 2022

²⁸⁴ See Documentary Evidence Act 1868 (UK Law)

²⁸⁵ See European Justice 'Taking of Evidence' European Judicial Network available at: https://e-justice.europa.eu/76/EN/taking_of_evidence

²⁸⁶ See Casey, Digital Evidence and Computer Crime, 2004, page 16; Vacca, Computer Forensics, Computer Crime Scene Investigation, 2nd Edition, 2005, page 39.

²⁸⁷ Moore, To View or not to view: Examining the Plain View Doctrine and Digital Evidence, American Journal of Criminal Justice, Vol. 29, No. 1, 2004, page 58

²⁸⁸ Hosmer, Proving the Integrity of Digital Evidence with Time, International Journal of Digital Evidence, 2002, Vol. 1, No. 1, page 1; Insa, Situation Report on the Admissibility of Electronic Evidence in Europe, in: Syllabus to the European Certificate on Cybercrime and E-Evidence, 2008, page 217.

²⁸⁹ See ELI Admissibility of E-Evidence in Criminal Proceedings in the EU, 2022 Page 1, University of Vienna, Draft Legils <https://www.europeanlawinstitute.eu/projects-publications/current-projects/current-projects/admissibility-of-e-evidence/>

the admissibility of evidence in criminal and civil cases across the European Union. The cross-border requirements of evidence into different legal environments concerns the recommendations that can be provided by the CYCLOPES technical partners, therefore, the accessibility to utilise these technologies in their respective jurisdiction must be considered to ensure that is an effective use.

9.2 Digital Forensics

The ability to utilise electronic evidence within a court of law can only be gained through its rightful collection and evaluation.²⁹⁰ In the case of digital forensics, this is a particular concern as investigators can be dealing with potentially volatile storage media that must be handled correctly to maintain the availability and integrity of the data.

Digital forensics has been defined as the art of collecting, processing, preserving, analysing computer-related evidence in support of network vulnerability mitigation and criminal, fraud, counterintelligence or law enforcement investigations.²⁹¹ There is no harmonised law specifically governing digital forensics within the EU, although several international standards exist that support various processes that are required to carry out digital forensics investigations. Specifically, ISO 27037 on Guidelines for identification, collection, acquisition and preservation of digital evidence and the series under ISO 27050 on Electronic discovery are particularly relevant to this area and should ensure a degree of commonality between procedures in different jurisdictions.

As with all investigations, the concepts of *legitimacy, necessity, and proportionality* are essential for ensuring investigations are conducted in an appropriate manner. Such requirements are also core fundamentals of the Directive (EU) 2016/680 the 'Law Enforcement Directive' and therefore apply directly to cybercrime and digital forensics investigations. This is particularly relevant in the digital forensics arena as even personal storage devices can now contain terabytes of data; however, all of such data may not be directly relevant to the investigation in hand and may infringe upon personal data processing or fundamental rights laws.

The Law Enforcement Directive acts as an ombudsman into the ethical practices of LEAs when investigating crimes. Digital forensic methods should be closely regulated and monitored due to the tension in relation to privacy rights given the likelihood of many digital devices containing sensitive personal data.²⁹² Specific regulations on any digital forensics practices are more likely to exist at national level. The first element of the process is ensuring the investigator has the right to access and extract information from the device. For example, in the UK this is achieved through two pieces of legislation: the *Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1984 (PACE)*²⁹³ which gives LEAs the right to gain access to a digital device and the *Data Retention and Investigatory*

²⁹⁰ See Leigland/Krings, A Formalization of Digital Forensics, International Journal of Digital Evidence, 2004, Vol.3, No.2.

²⁹¹ See National Initiative for Cybersecurity Careers and Studies 'Digital Forensics: Workforce Framework for Cybersecurity (NICE Framework) Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency

²⁹² <http://euro.ecom.cmu.edu/program/law/08-732/Evidence/RyanShpantzer.pdf>

²⁹³ Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1984

Powers Act 2014 (IPA) which then gives the rights to access the information in the device.²⁹⁴ Alternatively, in Germany for example it has been highlighted that prosecution of cases via evidence obtained through digital forensics has shown to ‘impact basic rights’ and the constitution of Germany does not provide ‘explicit statutory authorisation.’²⁹⁵

Although there is no harmonised legislation within the EU on digital forensics, the Council of Europe endorses the usage of the guides from the ENFSI (European Network of Forensic Science Institutes) and ENISA (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) around digital forensics. In the context of CYCLOPES, each year one workshop theme will focus particularly on digital forensics. In the first year of the project this was related to mobile devices and wearables whereas in the second year the focus will be on automobile forensics.

There are several challenges that digital forensics investigators face when trying to extract data from digital devices whilst having to ensure the legality and appropriate techniques to apply. For example, one survey noted 17 different issues facing digital forensic investigators.²⁹⁶ Meanwhile other reviews have noted potential legal issues to include everything from the presentation of evidence to the extent to which an investigator should understand the code/tool they are using²⁹⁷ - an issue that is likely to be further exacerbated with the move towards artificial intelligence powered technology.

One of the most common challenges (also echoed in the CYCLOPES WP2 workshops from the first year) is related to encryption and the desire to have access to solutions that can decrypt data obtained from devices. Whilst a technical challenge, this also raises several legal and ethical considerations as well. Several solutions are suggested to navigate the encryption challenge²⁹⁸ including the use of existing legislation to compel the owner to provide the password, the use of specialised techniques to extract or hack the password from volatile memory, or in some cases the use of backdoors to the device. Digital forensic investigators should be aware that some campaigners have challenged the use of approaches that utilised extraction or hacking processes on the basis that it could interfere with evidential integrity.²⁹⁹ Therefore, when selecting software solutions (such as those from Cellebrite, Oxygen Forensics, etc. as well as open-source solutions) the tools or techniques should be well-established and well documented to ensure they are not subject to legal challenge. Similarly, when there have been requests for the implementation of backdoor access to device data (e.g., in the case of the San Bernardino attacks in 2015 where the FBI requested access to a

²⁹⁴ Data Retention and Investigatory Powers Act 2014

²⁹⁵ Freilling, F., Safferling, C (2017) Digital forensics: Not everything that is technically possible is legally permissible. Friedrich-Alexander Universität <https://www.fau.eu/2017/06/07/news/research/digital-forensics-not-everything-that-is-technically-possible-is-legally-permissible/>

²⁹⁶ Liles, S., Rogers, M., & Hoebich, M. (2009). A survey of the legal issues facing digital forensic experts. In IFIP International Conference on Digital Forensics (pp. 267-276). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.

²⁹⁷ Cole, K. A., Gupta, S., Gurugubelli, D., & Rogers, M. K. (2015). A review of recent case law related to digital forensics: the current issues.

²⁹⁸ Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology (2016) POSTnote: Digital forensics and crime. <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/POST-PN-0520/POST-PN-0520.pdf>

²⁹⁹ Open Rights Group (2015) Draft equipment interference code of practice submission. <https://www.openrightsgroup.org/publications/equipment-interference-code-of-practice/>

locked iPhone) this has garnered negative attention from privacy campaigners and in that specific case the device and software manufacturer themselves.³⁰⁰

Another key challenge arising from research in CYCLOPES has been the access to data stored on cloud services. From one direction it is possible for users to remotely change, overwrite or delete the data stored on such services, but it also causes a legislative challenge (one that is also experienced when trying to obtain data from social media companies) that the geographic location of the data is likely not in the same jurisdiction as the investigator and therefore may require the use of a mutual legal assistance treaty (MLAT). Therefore, investigators must be aware of this process and understand how to optimise their requests to obtain data as swiftly as possible. Member State LEAs can rely on Europol's SIRIUS platform for support with access to this information.³⁰¹

Investigators should also be aware of potential adversarial approaches used by criminals to manipulate the appearance of their online information. Such tactics can include changing dates and times of updated files, overwriting files to permanently erase them, using multiple layers of encryption or applying different encryption to different parts of the drive.²⁹⁸ Identifying and addressing such modifications can also potentially cause disruption to the chain of evidence and therefore should be recorded carefully.

³⁰⁰ Electronic Privacy Information Center. Amicus Briefs – Apple v. FBI. <https://epic.org/documents/apple-v-fbi-2/>

³⁰¹ Europol (2022) SIRIUS project. <https://www.europol.europa.eu/operations-services-innovation/sirius-project>

10. Monitoring and Storing of Illegal Content

One component of an advanced investigative tool could be the acquisition of big data.³⁰² Such approach would include the operation of crawlers to be utilized with regard to the surface, deep and dark web as well as P2P networks. One concern when operating such a crawler is that it could collect illegal content. The collection of such material can in certain cases have significant legal consequences. While as a general principle it is safe to say that Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) are authorized to interact with illegal content, this should not be considered a “*carte blanche*” for the operation of crawlers. As an example, a LEA unit investigating tax crimes may not be authorized to store child abuse images that they collected through a crawler.

10.1. Illegal Content and Varying Degrees of Criminalisation

The term “illegal content” is used to describe a wide range of criminalized content including child pornography, xenophobic material or insults related to cybercriminal content.³⁰³ Despite harmonization approaches by the European Commission, value systems and the degree of criminalization differ extensively between countries.³⁰⁴ As an example, the dissemination of xenophobic material may be illegal in many European countries³⁰⁵ but is protected by the principle of freedom of speech³⁰⁶ in others like the United States.³⁰⁷ The use of derogatory

³⁰² See: Work Package 5: Big Data Acquisition and Pre-Processing

³⁰³ For reports on cases involving illegal content, see *Sieber*, Council of Europe Organised Crime Report 2004, page 137 *et seq.*

³⁰⁴ *Gercke*, Understanding Cybercrime, ITU, 2014, page 23.

³⁰⁵ One example of the wide criminalization of illegal content is Sec. 86a German Penal Code. The provision criminalizes the use of symbols of unconstitutional parties: Section 86a: Use of Symbols of Unconstitutional Organizations.

³⁰⁶ Regarding the principle of freedom of speech, see: *Tedford/Herbeck/Haiman*, Freedom of Speech in the United States, 2005; *Barendt*, Freedom of Speech, 2007; *Baker*; Human Liberty and Freedom of Speech; *Emord*, Freedom, Technology and the First Amendment, 1991. Regarding the importance of the principle with regard to electronic surveillance, see: *Woo/So*, The case for Magic Lantern: September 11 Highlights the need for increasing surveillance, Harvard Journal of Law & Technology, Vol. 15, No. 2, 2002, page 530 *et seq.*; *Vhesterman*, Freedom of Speech in Australian Law; A Delicate Plant, 2000; *Volokh*, Freedom of Speech, Religious Harassment Law, and Religious Accommodation Law, Loyola University Chicago Law Journal, Vol. 33, 2001, page 57 *et seq.*; *Cohen*, Freedom of Speech and Press: Exceptions to the First Amendment, CRS Report for Congress 95-815, 2007.

³⁰⁷ Concerns over freedom of expression (e.g. the First Amendment to the United States Constitution) explain why certain acts of racism were not made illegal by the Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime, but their criminalization was included in the First Additional Protocol. See Explanatory Report to the Council of Europe Cybercrime Convention First Additional Protocol, No. 4.

remarks in respect of the Holy Prophet is criminal in several Arabic countries, but not in several European countries.³⁰⁸

10.2. Illegal Content and Freedom of Expression

The criminalization of illegal content is a controversial issue and a difficult balancing act for governments to find the right solution as the criminalization of illegal content should not interfere with the right to freedom of expression as for example defined by principle 1 (b) of the Johannesburg Principles on National Security and Freedom of Expression.³⁰⁹ At the same time, however, principle 1 (c) clarifies that the right to freedom of expression may be subject to restrictions. Despite the possibility to restrict freedom of expression, it is important to underline that based on the above-mentioned concerns, any restriction has to be strictly limited. Such limitations are especially discussed with regard to the criminalization of defamation.³¹⁰ The 2008 Joint Declaration of the UN Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Opinion and Expression and others points out that vague notions such as providing communications and the glorification or promotion of terrorism or extremism should not be criminalized.³¹¹

10.3. Child Sexual Abuse Material / Child Pornography

There is one area of illegal content where the need for a broad criminalization is widely accepted and practiced: Child sexual abuse and exploitation material (CSEM) – in legal documents often referred to as child pornography.³¹² Various international organizations are engaged in the fight against online child pornography³¹³ and have developed legal instruments addressing such content such as: the 1989 United Nations Convention on the Rights of the

³⁰⁸ The 2006 Joint Declaration of the UN Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Opinion and Expression, the OSCE Representative on Freedom of the Media and the OAS Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Expression points out that “in many countries, overbroad rules in this area are abused by the powerful to limit non-traditional, dissenting, critical, or minority voices, or discussion about challenging social issues”. In 2008 the Joint Declaration highlights that international organizations, including the United Nations General Assembly and Human Rights Council, should desist from the further adoption of statements supporting the idea of defamation of religions.

³⁰⁹ 1996 Johannesburg Principles on National Security, Freedom of Expression and Access to Information.

³¹⁰ The 2002 Joint Declaration of the UN Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Opinion and Expression, the OSCE Representative on Freedom of the Media and the OAS Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Expression points out that “defamation is not a justifiable restriction on freedom of expression; all criminal defamation laws should be abolished and replaced, where necessary, with appropriate civil defamation laws”.

³¹¹ International Mechanisms for Promoting Freedom of Expression, Joint Declaration on Defamation of Religions, and Anti-Terrorism and Anti-Extremism Legislation, by the UN Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Opinion and Expression, the OSCE Representative on Freedom of the Media and the OAS Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Expression, and the ACHPR (African Commission on Human and Peoples Rights) Special Rapporteur on Freedom of Expression and Access to Information, 2008.

³¹² ITU Global Cybersecurity Agenda / High-Level Experts Group, Global Strategic Report, 2008, page 34.

³¹³ See, for example, the “G8 Communiqué”, Genoa Summit, 2001.

Child;³¹⁴ the 2011 European Union Directive on combating the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child pornography³¹⁵ and the 2007 Council of Europe Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse.³¹⁶ Provisions criminalizing interaction with child pornography have different aims. The criminalization of the production of child pornography for example seeks to protect children from falling victim to sexual abuse.³¹⁷ But it is important to highlight that most approaches to criminalize child pornography go beyond criminalizing the production or dissemination of such material. The 2011 European Union Directive on combating the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child pornography, that defines the standard for the EU Member States, does not only contain a criminalization of possession but also criminalizes obtaining access by means of information and communication technology, to child pornography.

10.4. UN Framework

The Optional Protocol to the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child³¹⁸ not only addresses the issue of child pornography in general, but explicitly refers to the role of the Internet in distributing such material.³¹⁹ The term “child pornography” is defined as any representation, by whatever means, of a child engaged in real or simulated explicit sexual activities or any representation of the sexual parts of a child for primarily sexual purposes.³²⁰ Article 3 requires the parties to criminalize certain conduct – including acts related to child pornography.

In the context of advanced investigative tools automatically crawling everywhere online to gather potential evidence the following aspects are relevant: Art. 3 of the Optional Protocol requires the Member States to criminalize the possession of child pornography. As a consequence of this international instrument (as well as Council of Europe and European Union instruments), it is likely that the possession of child pornography is criminalized in all countries the Consortium Members operate out of. In addition, it is important for the LEAs as Consortium Member to take note that the Optional Protocol does not include an explicit exemption of criminal liability for LEAs.

10.5. CoE Framework

³¹⁴ United Nations Convention on the Right of the Child, A/RES/44/25, Regarding the importance of cybercrime legislation see: ITU Global Cybersecurity Agenda / High-Level Experts Group, Global Strategic Report, 2008.

³¹⁵ Directive 2011/92/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on combating the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child pornography, and replacing Council Framework Decision 2004/68/JHA

³¹⁶ Council of Europe Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse, CETS No: 201.

³¹⁷ *Levesque*, Sexual Abuse of Children: A Human Rights Perspective, 1999, page 68.

³¹⁸ A/RES/44/25, adopted by the UN General Assembly on 12 December 1989.

³¹⁹ See the preface to the Optional Protocol.

³²⁰ See Art. 2.

The 2001 Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime³²¹ contains a provision addressing child pornography. Art. 9 requires Member States to criminalize a wide range of acts related to child pornography ranging from production to distribution. The Convention on Cybercrime also addresses the issues of possession of child pornography.

In the context of advanced investigative tools automatically crawling everywhere online to gather potential evidence it is important underline that – just like the Optional Protocol to the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child – Art. 9 addresses the criminalization of the possession of child pornography. However, unlike the Optional Protocol the Convention on Cybercrime does not require the criminalization of the possession of child pornography but enables Member States to opt-out. Despite this, it is highly unlikely that Member States, that are bound by the 2011 EU Directive on Child Pornography, have not criminalized the possession of child pornography. In addition, it is worth pointing out that the Convention on Cybercrime does not include an explicit exemption of criminal liability for LEAs.

As part of its approach to improve the protection of minors against sexual exploitation, the Council of Europe in 2007 introduced the Convention on the Protection of Children.³²² One of the essential aims of the Convention on the Protection of Children is the harmonization of criminal law provisions aimed at protecting children from sexual exploitation.³²³ To achieve this aim, the Convention contains an entire set of criminal law provisions. Apart from criminalizing of the sexual abuse of children (Article 18), the Convention also contains provisions addressing child pornography (Article 20) and the solicitation of children for sexual purposes (Article 23).

In the context of advanced investigative tools automatically crawling everywhere online to gather potential evidence it is important to underline that the Convention on the protection of children calls upon Member States to criminalize both the possession of child pornography as well as the act of gaining access to such material. While the Member States can opt out of a criminalization of access to child pornography the criminalization of possession of child pornography is mandatory for Member States that signed the Convention. This is relevant for LEAs operating such crawling functionality as the mere access to child pornography content through a crawler can potentially lead to criminal liability. The Convention does not include an explicit exemption of criminal liability for LEAs.

10.6. EU Framework

³²¹ Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime, ETS 185. See in this regard: CETS 185: Council of Europe Convention on Cybercrime. For more information see: *Sofaer*, Toward an International Convention on Cyber in Seymour/Goodman, *The Transnational Dimension of Cyber Crime and Terror*, page 225.; *Gercke*, *The Slow Awake of a Global Approach Against Cybercrime*, CRi 2006, 140 *et seq.*; *Gercke*, *National, Regional and International Approaches in the Fight Against Cybercrime*, CRi 2008, page 7 *et seq.*; *Gercke*, *10 years Convention on Cybercrime*, Cri 2011, 142 *et seq.*; *Aldesco*, *The Demise of Anonymity: A Constitutional Challenge to the Convention on Cybercrime*, *Entertainment Law Review*, 2002, No. 1; *Broadhurst*, *Development in the global law enforcement of cyber-crime*, in *Policing: An International Journal of Police Strategies and Management*, 29(2), 2006, page 408 *et seq.*; *Adoption of Convention on Cybercrime*, *International Journal of International Law*, Vol. 95, No.4, 2001, page 889 *et seq.*

³²² Council of Europe – Council of Europe Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse (CETS No. 201).

³²³ For more details, see: *Gercke*, *The Development of Cybercrime Law*, *Zeitschrift fuer Urheber- und Medienrecht* 2008, 550ff.

In 2011, the European Union adopted the Directive on combating the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child pornography.³²⁴ The drafters of this Directive pointed out that information technology enables offenders to produce and distribute child pornography more easily³²⁵ and emphasizes the importance of addressing the resulting challenges with specific provisions.

In the context of advanced investigative tools automatically crawling everywhere online to gather potential evidence two aspects are of relevance: Art. 5 (2) and (3) of this EU Directive require Member States to criminalize both obtaining access to child pornography as well as the possession of child pornography. This is relevant for LEAs operating such crawlers as the mere access to child pornography content through a crawler can potentially lead to criminal liability. However, it is worth pointing out that although this EU Directive does not explicitly exclude a criminal liability of LEAs if they access or possess child pornography, its Art. 15 calls for Member States to take measures to enable investigative units to identify victims “by analysing child pornography material”.

In this context, a significant change seems imminent to the legal framework for services falling within the scope of the ePrivacy Directive. Because the ePrivacy Directive does not contain a legal basis for the voluntary processing of content or traffic data for the purpose of detecting child sexual abuse, a specific derogation to Art. 5(1) and 6(1) ePrivacy Directive was introduced by the Regulation (EU) 2021/1232³²⁶ (the Interim Regulation). This derogation enables providers of number-independent interpersonal communications services (NI-ICS) to continue their voluntary practices of detecting, reporting and removing child sexual abuse material online. However, this derogation is temporary and applies only until 3 August 2024.

In addition, the Digital Services Act³²⁷ is an important first step towards digital companies taking greater responsibility for content that appears on their platforms, including content related to children. The DSA extends the temporary derogation to intermediary services³²⁸ and requires the swift removal of illegal online content³²⁹ such as CSAM, illegal hate speech, terrorist

³²⁴ Directive 2011/92/EU of the European Parliament and of The Council of 13 December 2011 on combating the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child pornography, and replacing Council Framework Decision 2004/68/JHA.

³²⁵ See: Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on combating the sexual abuse, sexual exploitation of children and child pornography, repealing Framework Decision 2004/68/JHA, page 2.

³²⁶ Regulation (EU) 2021/1232 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 July 2021 on a temporary derogation from certain provisions of Directive 2002/58/EC as regards the use of technologies by providers of number-independent interpersonal communications services for the processing of personal and other data for the purpose of combating online child sexual abuse, 30 July 2021, Official Journal of the EU, L 274, p. 41.

³²⁷ Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market for Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC (Digital Services Act), 27 October 2022, Official Journal of the EU L 277, p. 1.

³²⁸ Art. 7 DSA. The term „intermediary service“ comprises three different types of services, pursuant to Art. 3(g) DSA: (i) a mere conduit service; (ii) a caching service; and (iii) a hosting service.

³²⁹ Art. 3(h) DSA defines „illegal content“ as „any information that, in itself or in relation to an activity, including the sale of products or the provision of services, is not in compliance with Union law or the law of any Member State which is in compliance with Union law, irrespective of the precise subject matter or nature of that law“.

content and illegal products. A growing number of platforms, including Tiktok and Facebook, are currently training their moderators to detect these types of content.³³⁰

Against this background, the European Commission has proposed to establish a clearing house mechanism for reports on Child Sexual Abuse (CSA) in Europe which involves newly designated national authorities empowered to search and monitor publicly accessible material on hosting services regarding CSA material. This envisioned clearing house mechanism would effectively function as a preliminary filter for CSA reports forwarded to LEAs in Europe and, therefore, would inevitable affect LEAs future use of advanced investigative tools and automated search tools.

The Commission adopted its Proposal for a Regulation laying down rules to prevent and combat child sexual abuse³³¹ (Draft Regulation Against Online CSA) in May 2022. The Draft Regulation Against Online CSA aims to harmonise the rules applicable on the detection, reporting and removal of online CSA as necessary measure to remove existing national barriers to the Digital Single Market and to complement the Digital Services Act.³³² To achieve this objective, the Draft Regulation Against Online CSA introduces targeted and uniform obligations of risk assessment³³³ and mitigation³³⁴ which are complemented where necessary by orders for detection³³⁵, reporting³³⁶ and removal³³⁷ of CSA content. These obligations are applicable to any provider offering hosting or interpersonal communication services on the Digital Single Market regardless of where they have their principal establishment.³³⁸

From a law enforcement perspective, it is most interesting to note that the application and enforcement of these obligations in particular and the Draft Regulation Against Online CSA in general are placed under the responsibility of independent³³⁹ national Coordinating Authorities designated by the Member States for the consistent application, Art. 25(2) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA. For this purpose, the Coordinating Authorities are granted wide ranging

³³⁰ European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS), „Combating child sexual abuse online“, Briefing by Negreiro, PE 738.224, June 2023, p. 3.

³³¹ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council laying down rules to prevent and combat child sexual abuse, COM (2021) 209 final, 2022/0155 (COD), 11 May 2022, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52022PC0209&from=EN>.

³³² Art. 1(3)(b) and Art. 2(a), (g), (r), (t) and (v) as well as Rec. (15), (16), (31), (40) and (42) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA. Commission, Draft Regulation Against Online CSA, COM (2021) 209 final, 11 May 2022, Explanatory Memorandum, p. 2.

³³³ Art. 3 Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³³⁴ Art. 4 Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³³⁵ Art. 7 and 8 Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³³⁶ Art. 5 Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³³⁷ Art. 1(c) and (d) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA alluding to the removal order against an ISP under Art. 14 Draft Regulation Against Online CSA and to the blocking order against an access provider under Art. 16 Draft Regulation Against Online CSA, depending on whether ISPs offer their services in the EU, Re. (32) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³³⁸ Art. 1(2) and Rec. (6) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³³⁹ According to Art. 26(2) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA, the Member States shall ensure that the Coordinating Authorities: (a) are legally and functionally independent from any other public authority; (b) have status to carry out their tasks objectively and impartially; (c) are free from any external influence; (d) neither seek nor take instructions from anyone; and (e) are solely charged with their tasks under the Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

investigatory powers in respect of providers.³⁴⁰ Very relevant in the context of the CYCLOPES project is that the Coordinating Authorities' investigatory powers also include the power to monitor compliance with the Draft Regulation Against Online CSA by conducting searches on publicly accessible material to detect known or new CSA material.³⁴¹ Such searches have to be performed using two types of indicators of online CSA contained in newly created databases, pursuant to Art. 44(1) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA: (a) indicators to detect known CSA material; and (b) indicators to detect unknown CSA material.

In case the search of a Coordinating Authority detects a known or unknown item of CSA material, the Coordinating Authority will notify the provider of the hosting service and request the provider to voluntarily remove or disable access to that item or those items.³⁴² The notified provider then has to report the online CSA immediately³⁴³ to the newly established EU Centre on CSA (EU Centre), a new EU Agency to prevent and combat CSA.³⁴⁴ Having received a CSA report,³⁴⁵ the EU Centre has to assess whether the report is "manifestly unfounded" in order to avoid obvious false positives.³⁴⁶ In case the EU Centre considers a report "not manifestly unfounded", the EU Centre has to forward the report to Europol and to the competent national LEA(s) likely to have jurisdiction to investigate and prosecute the potential CSA of the report.³⁴⁷

This clearing house mechanism would probably shift the focus of online searches performed by LEAs concerning CSA material away from using advanced investigative tools for preventative purposes towards targeted searches retrospectively investigating CSA material. This seems all the more likely because any provider of hosting services or of interpersonal communications services does not have to be notified by a Coordinating Authority for having to report the online CSA to the EU Centre. Rather, these providers have to promptly submit a CSA report to the EU Centre whenever they become aware in any manner of any information indicating potential online CSA on their respective services.³⁴⁸

³⁴⁰ Art. 27(1) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA grants Coordinating Authorities the powers to: (a) require providers to provide information; (b) carry out on-site inspections of any providers' premises for information on suspected infringements; (c) ask any of a provider's staff for explanations about suspected infringements; and (d) assess a provider's compliance with a detection, removal or blocking order.

³⁴¹ Art. 31 Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³⁴² Art. 32 Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³⁴³ Art. 12(1) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³⁴⁴ Art. 40 Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³⁴⁵ Annex III of the Draft Regulation Against Online CSA provides a mandatory template in which the reporting provider has to provide the mandatory information detailed in Art. 13(1) sentence 2 (a)-(k) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³⁴⁶ Art. 43(3)(b) in conjunction with Art. 48(1) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³⁴⁷ Art. 48(3) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

³⁴⁸ Art. 12(1) Draft Regulation Against Online CSA.

11. International Cooperation Against Cybercrime

In order to most effectively contribute their share of law enforcement's mandate to keep society safe, cybercrime investigators need timely access to relevant data. A significant amount of knowledge about the functioning, activities and sometimes the targets of cybercriminal activities can be derived from websites, chat rooms and other Internet communications. Because cybercriminals do not need to be physically present where the cybercrime happens or where the victim is located, cybercrimes typically take full advantage of this freedom to mobility and display an international spread of relevant geolocations. An offender may be based in one country using services for anonymous communication from another country and publish cybercriminal content online in third countries by using different public Internet terminals. Unfortunately, there is neither a comprehensive international legal framework nor a supranational body able to investigate such offences. Rather, international crimes make it necessary for law-enforcement and judicial authorities in all countries involved to cooperate and assist the country that has assumed jurisdiction. Due to differences in national law and limited instruments, international cooperation is considered to be one of the major challenges in the fight against cybercrime.

For cybercrime investigations, the most relevant formal mechanisms supporting international cooperation are mutual legal assistance and extradition. Other mechanisms such as transfer of prisoners, transfer of proceedings in criminal matters, confiscation of criminal proceeds and asset recovery are less important in practice. In addition to the formal mechanisms, there are informal ways of cooperation such as exchange of intelligence among LEAs in different countries. A key demand of cybercrime investigators in international investigations is immediate reaction of their counterparts in the country where the data or the offender is located. Especially in terms of immediacy, traditional instruments of international judicial cooperation in criminal law matters seem rather inadequate to meet the requirements in terms of the speed in online investigations.

This chapter first looks at the UN framework and presents an understanding why the United Nations have not yet adopted a specific cybercrime convention leaving LEAs resort to a general UN convention on organised crime (section 11.1. below). Second, the guidance and mechanisms for international cooperation provided in the CoE framework are outlined (section 11.2. below). Finally, the existing as well as the soon-to-be mechanisms for international cooperation within the EU framework are described (section 11.3. below).

11.1. UN Framework

While cybercriminals take full advantage of the Internet's global availability, the global community has not (yet) found an adequate response to this international dimension within the framework of the United Nations. The question of a global convention to enable much needed international cooperation, including exchanges of information and intelligence for tackling cybercrime emerged at the level of the United Nations well over a decade ago. In 2010, the discussion of this question at the twelfth United Nations Congress of the *Commission on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice* (CCPCJ) revealed lack of sufficient consensus among the

Member States about the most appropriate way forward. There were and up to this day still are two dominant schools of thought opposing each other:

- “Globalisation” of Budapest Convention:
On the one hand, a significant number of Member States advocate for “globalising” the existing Council of Europe (CoE) Convention on Cybercrime (also known as the Budapest Convention), because the CoE Convention on Cybercrime is currently the most comprehensive legal instrument in place at international level with the highest number of State Parties³⁴⁹, and is open for signature to non-members of the Council of Europe. Russia opposed the Budapest Convention because it believed that it would undermine the stately sovereignty of member states through cross-border cybercrime operations.³⁵⁰
- “Original” United Nations Mechanism:
On the other hand, several Member States favour the negotiation of a new mechanism under the auspices of the United Nations. This school of thought points to the difficulty of scaling up to the global level the procedural and cooperation commitments as well as the comparatively high standards contained in the CoE Convention on Cybercrime. In addition, several Member States and groupings, including Russia, the BRICS³⁵¹ and many developing countries, object not only formally to signing a convention without having previously been involved in its drafting, but also on the merits to some provisions relating to cross-border access to data to which they object on procedural and substantive grounds.³⁵²

Against this background, Member States continued to lay the groundwork for international cooperation on cybercrime and the *Commission on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice* (CCPCJ) gradually emerged as the primary platform for cybercrime debates at the United Nations. The CCPCJ established an open-ended international *Expert Group Meeting on Cybercrime*.³⁵³ The expert group’s “Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime” provides an important reference framework for Member States on a number of issues relating to trends, legislation, law enforcement and investigations, electronic evidence and criminal justice,

³⁴⁹ With the latest ratifications of Nigeria (non-member of CoE) in July 2022 and Sweden (member of CoE) in April 2021, the CoE Convention on Cybercrime currently has 68 State Parties plus 2 States who signed but did not ratify, see: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/cets-number/-/abridged-title-known?module=signatures-by-treaty&treatynum=185>.

³⁵⁰ Page, The hypercrisis of Russia’s push for a new global cybercrime treaty, March 2022; available at: <https://www.lowyinstitute.org/the-interpreter/hypocrisy-russia-s-push-new-global-cybercrime-treaty>.

³⁵¹ Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa.

³⁵² Kavanagh, The United Nations, cyberspace and international peace and security: Responding to complexity in the 21st century, UNIDIR, 2017, p, 45, available at: <https://unidir.org/publication/united-nations-cyberspace-and-international-peace-and-security-responding-complexity>; Maurer, „Cyber Norm Emergence at United Nations“, Harvard Kennedy School/Belfer Center for Science and International Affairs, 2011, p. 41, available at: <https://www.un.org/en/ecosoc/cybersecurity/maurer-cyber-norm-dp-2011-11.pdf>.

³⁵³ Kavanagh, The United Nations, cyberspace and international peace and security: Responding to complexity in the 21st century, UNIDIR, 2017, 44–45; UNODC, Global programme on cybercrime, <https://unidir.org/sites/default/files/publication/pdfs//the-united-nations-cyberspace-and-international-peace-and-security-en-691.pdf>.

international cooperation, and the role of the private sector³⁵⁴. This reference framework is complemented by the “*Global Programme on Cybercrime*” established under the auspices of the *United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime* (UNODC) in 2013 to support Member States not only in preventing and combatting cybercrime through “crime prevention and criminal justice technical support”, but also through the development of a growing *Cybercrime Repository* consisting of databases for case law, legislation, best practices and lessons learned from Member States.³⁵⁵

As the UN’s central ‘platform for further discussion on substantive issues concerning cybercrime’³⁵⁶, the last four sessions of the expert group (in 2018³⁵⁷, in 2019³⁵⁸, in 2020³⁵⁹ and in 2021³⁶⁰) served to collect and consolidate ultimately 63 Member State’s recommendations and conclusions on strengthening practical responses to cybercrime in three focus areas: (1) legislation, frameworks and criminalization, (2) law enforcement and investigations, including electronic evidence and criminal justice and (3) international cooperation and prevention.³⁶¹

The core obstacle for the expert group and its stakeholders is and remains, however, that there is no agreement that a United Nations treaty or protocol on cybercrime is necessary.

³⁵⁴ UNODC, *Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime*, draft, February 2013, available at: https://www.unodc.org/documents/organizedcrime/UNODC_CCPCJ_EG.4_2013/CYBERCRIME_STUDY_210_213.pdf. This „Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime“ goes back to this resolution: General Assembly, “Strengthening the United Nations Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice Programme, in Particular its Technical Cooperation Capacity”, UN document A/RES/65/232, 23 March 2011, at no. 4.

³⁵⁵ Information on the Implementation of Crime Commission resolution 22/8, document UNODC/CCPCJ/EG.4/2017/CRP.1, 3 April 2017, p.2 at paras. 7 and 25; available at: https://www.unodc.org/documents/organized-crime/cybercrime/Cybercrime-April-2017/UNODC_CCPCJ_EG_4_2017_CRP_1_E.pdf; see also third session of the „Open-ended intergovernmental expert group to conduct a comprehensive study of the problem of cybercrime“, on 10-13 April 2017, Report and all documentation available at: <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/organized-crime/open-ended-intergovernmental-expert-group-to-conduct-a-comprehensive-study-of-the-problem-of-cybercrime.html>.

³⁵⁶ CCPCJ Resolution 26/4, adopted in May 2017, referenced in UN Doc. E/2018/30-E/CN.15/2018/15, para 6.

³⁵⁷ Fourth session of the „Open-ended intergovernmental expert group to conduct a comprehensive study of the problem of cybercrime“, on 3-5 April 2018, Report and all documentation available at: <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/organized-crime/open-ended-intergovernmental-expert-group-to-conduct-a-comprehensive-study-of-the-problem-of-cybercrime2018.html>.

³⁵⁸ Fifth session of the „Open-ended intergovernmental expert group to conduct a comprehensive study of the problem of cybercrime“, on 27-29 March 2019, Report and all documentation available at: <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/organized-crime/open-ended-intergovernmental-expert-group-to-conduct-a-comprehensive-study-of-the-problem-of-cybercrime2019.html>.

³⁵⁹ „Sixth session of the Open-ended intergovernmental expert group to conduct a comprehensive study of the problem of cybercrime“, on 27-29 July 2020, Report and all documentation available at: <https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/organized-crime/open-ended-intergovernmental-expert-group-to-conduct-a-comprehensive-study-of-the-problem-of-cybercrime2020.html>.

³⁶⁰ „Seventh session of the Open-ended intergovernmental expert group to conduct a comprehensive study of the problem of cybercrime“, on 6-8 April 2021, Report and all documentation available at: https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/organized-crime/open-ended-intergovernmental-expert-group-to-conduct-a-comprehensive-study-of-the-problem-of-cybercrime_2021.html.

³⁶¹ See Annex „Conclusions and recommendations agreed upon by the Expert Group for consideration by the Commission on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice“, of the „Report on the meeting of the Expert Group to Conduct a Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime held in Vienna from 6 to 8 April 2021“, UNODC/CCPCJ/EG.4/2021/2, 19 April 2021, available at: <https://www.unodc.org/documents/organized-crime/cybercrime/Cybercrime-April-2021/Report/V2102595.pdf>.

11.1.1. Drafting a UN Convention on Cooperation in Combating Cybercrime

When the proponents of the school of thought favouring a United Nation's legal instrument suggested the idea of a cybercrime treaty at the Twelfth UN Crime Congress in 2010, the deadlock pointed out in section 11.1. above caused the negotiations to fail over issues of national sovereignty, on the one side, and protection of online rights, on the other³⁶². Russia submitted a Draft UN Convention on Cooperation in Combating Cybercrime³⁶³ in 2017 and led a resolution³⁶⁴ to establish a committee of experts to consider establishing an UN cybercrime treaty.

While the legitimacy of this Russian led UN resolution had raised suspicions,³⁶⁵ the Association for Progressive Communication (APC) had previously argued in an open letter to the UN General Assembly that the Draft UN Convention on Cooperation in Combating Cybercrime proposed by Russia (Russian Draft) undermines the use of the internet to exercise human rights and facilitate social and economic development because: (i) the Russian Draft opens the door to criminalising ordinary online behaviour; (ii) creates a chilling effect; (iii) the Russian Draft lacks sufficient references to balancing the interests of law enforcement and respect for fundamental human rights are absent; and (iv) there is no need for a new international convention on cybercrime especially since a Second Additional Protocol is being developed to the CoE Budapest Convention³⁶⁶ which is the most widely ratified international instrument on cybercrime.³⁶⁷ Further, the establishment of an ad hoc intergovernmental committee of experts to address the issue of cybercrime would exclude key stakeholders, who bring valuable expertise and perspectives both in terms of effectively countering the use of ICTs for criminal purposes and to ensure that such efforts do not undermine the use of ICTs for the enjoyment of human rights and social and economic development.³⁶⁸

Setting the Russian Draft somewhat aside, the General Assembly decided to launch a process towards a new international treaty on cybercrime in December 2019 by establishing an open-ended ad hoc intergovernmental committee of experts (Ad Hoc Committee) to elaborate a

³⁶² „UN rejects Russian cyber-crime treaty”, 21 April 2010, available at: <https://www.itproportal.com/2010/04/21/un-rejects-russian-cyber-crime-treaty/>.

³⁶³ See United Nations, General Assembly, Annex to the letter dated 11 October 2017 from the Permanent Representative of the Russian Federation to the United Nations addressed to the Secretary-General, A/C.3/72/12, 16 October 2017, available at: <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N17/329/59/PDF/N1732959.pdf?OpenElement>.

from the Permanent Representative of the Russian Federation to the United Nations addressed to the Secretary-General

³⁶⁴ United Nations, Resolution 73/187, Countering the use of information and communications technologies for criminal purposes, General Assembly, A/RES/73/187, adopted on 17 December 2018, available at: <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N18/450/53/PDF/N1845053.pdf?OpenElement>.

³⁶⁵ Stolton, “UN backing of controversial cybercrime treaty raises suspicions”, EURACTIV.com, 23 January 2020, available at: <https://www.euractiv.com/section/digital/news/un-backing-of-controversial-cybercrime-treaty-raises-suspicions/>.

³⁶⁶ See section 6.3. of this Deliverable D9.3.

³⁶⁷ APC, “Open letter to UN General Assembly: Proposed international convention on cybercrime poses a threat to human rights online”, 6 November 2019, available at: <https://www.apc.org/en/pubs/open-letter-un-general-assembly-proposed-international-convention-cybercrime-poses-threat-human>.

³⁶⁸ APC, “Open letter to UN General Assembly: Proposed international convention on cybercrime poses a threat to human rights online”, 6 November 2019, available at: <https://www.apc.org/en/pubs/open-letter-un-general-assembly-proposed-international-convention-cybercrime-poses-threat-human>.

“comprehensive international convention on countering the use of information and communications technologies for criminal purposes”.³⁶⁹ The draft of a future UN convention on cybercrime is currently scheduled to be provided to the General Assembly at its 78th session, which will begin in September 2023 and conclude in September 2024.³⁷⁰

The Ad Hoc Committee’s drafting process towards a future UN convention on cybercrime is intended to take into full consideration existing international instruments and efforts at the national, regional and international levels on combating the use of information and communications technologies for criminal purposes and, in particular, “the work and outcomes of the open-ended intergovernmental Expert Group to Conduct a Comprehensive Study on Cybercrime”.³⁷¹ However, it is important to note that the Ad Hoc Committee is a subsidiary body of the General Assembly and as such not only separate, but due to its different mandate also independent from the Expert Group which is a subsidiary body of CCPCJ, even though UNODC (another subsidiary body of CCPCJ) serves as Secretariat for the Ad Hoc Committee.³⁷²

The next step for the Ad Hoc Committee is to convene at least six negotiating sessions of 10 days each, held no less than 11 weeks apart; and held its first negotiation session started on the 28 February 2022 just four days after Russia’s invasion of Ukraine. The sixth session in January 2024 is supposed to finalize the draft that will be concluded in a last session in January 2024.³⁷³

A challenge for all sessions is that all Ad Hoc Committee’s decisions on substantive matters without approval by consensus will be taken by a two-thirds majority of the representatives present and voting.³⁷⁴ Meanwhile, the Ad Hoc Committee has already gone through its 5th session of negotiations in April 2023 and has developed a draft that is not yet fully complete.³⁷⁵ In reviewing the draft, it becomes clear that the UN Convention is modelled on the CoE Convention on cybercrime in broad and central areas.³⁷⁶ For example, the scope and procedural measures in Art. 23 are taken from Article 14 of the CoE Convention. The general principles on international cooperation (Art. 46 ff.) are also based on Art. 23 of the CoE

³⁶⁹ General Assembly, „Countering the use of information and communications technologies for criminal purposes“, Resolution 74.247, A/RES/74/247, adopted on 27 December 2019, p. 3 at para. 2, available at: <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N19/440/28/PDF/N1944028.pdf?OpenElement>.

³⁷⁰ General Assembly, „Countering the use of information and communications technologies for criminal purposes“, Resolution 75.282, A/RES/75/282, adopted on 26 May 2021, p. 2 at para. 4, available at: <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N21/133/51/PDF/N2113351.pdf?OpenElement>.

³⁷¹ General Assembly, Resolution 74.247, A/RES/74/247, adopted on 27 December 2019, p. 3 at para. 2; General Assembly, Resolution 75.282, A/RES/75/282, adopted on 26 May 2021, p. 2 at para. 11.

³⁷² General Assembly, Resolution 75.282, A/RES/75/282, adopted on 26 May 2021, p. 2 at para. 2.

³⁷³ See: documentation of the „First session of the Ad Hoc Committee“, 28 February to 11 March 2022, available at: https://www.unodc.org/unodc/en/cybercrime/ad_hoc_committee/ahc-first-session.html. The documentation also includes a preparatory note containing the views received from Member States on the scope, objectives and structure (elements) of the new convention, see: „“, A/AC.291/4, 17 November 2021, available at: <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/V21/084/20/PDF/V2108420.pdf?OpenElement>.

submitted by Member States on the scope, objectives and structure (elements) of a comprehensive international convention on countering the use of information and communications technologies for criminal purposes“,

³⁷⁴ General Assembly, Resolution 75.282, A/RES/75/282, adopted on 26 May 2021, p. 2 at para. 5.

³⁷⁵ Draft text of the convention:

https://www.unodc.org/documents/Cybercrime/AdHocCommittee/Comments/RF_28_July_2021_-_E.pdf.

³⁷⁶ See: https://www.unodc.org/documents/Cybercrime/AdHocCommittee/6th_Session/general-documents/AHC_6th_session_-_Explanatory_notes_on_DTC.pdf.

Convention on cybercrime and Art. 43 of the Convention against Corruption (UNCAC). Other potentially relevant provisions on the retention of computer data (Art. 25) are borrowed from Art. 16 of the CoE Convention. Art. 11 deals with computer-related forgery and Art. 12 with computer-related theft and fraud, which in turn are modelled on Art. 7 and Art. 8 of the CoE Convention on cybercrime. In addition to the CoE Convention, the UN Convention is also modelled on existing UN conventions such as the Convention against Corruption (UNCAC), the Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC), the Convention on the Rights of the Child, and the CoE Lanzarote Convention. The influence of Russia, which as mentioned above started the ball rolling for a UN convention on cybercrime, seems to have diminished in the course of the negotiations.³⁷⁷ The European Commission, which has so far promoted the CoE Convention as an international standard in fighting cybercrime, has been authorised by Council Decision, with the aim of a consistent European and international legal situation, to participate intensively on behalf of the EU in the negotiations on the UN convention.³⁷⁸ The negotiation directives for the European Commission are listed in a separate Addendum and a special committee has been designated by the Council.³⁷⁹ Probably the inclusion of the EU is the reason why the UN Convention seems to be modelled on the CoE Convention on cybercrime in many areas. In its cooperation, the EU has in mind the protection of personal data and the fundamental right of individuals to respect for their private and family life, their home and their communications.³⁸⁰

Human rights organizations continue to take a critical view of the convention and warn against the criminalization of previously permitted actions on the Internet, state surveillance and the undermining of civil rights.³⁸¹

The further development of the UN Convention of Cybercrime will be closely monitored in the course of the CYCLOPES project and emerging key elements for a future United Nations standard will be analysed and reported about in later iterations of this Deliverable.

11.1.2. UN Convention against Transnational Organised Crime

³⁷⁷ Bannelier, The U.N. Cybercrime Convention Should Not Become a Tool for Political Control or the Watering Down of Human Rights, January 2023.

³⁷⁸ Council Decision (EU) 2022/895 of 24 May 2022 authorising the opening of negotiations on behalf of the European Union for a comprehensive international convention on countering the use of information and communications technologies for criminal purposes, 8 June 2022, Official Journal of the EU L 155, p. 42, available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f701f8d8-e6c5-11ec-a534-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF>; the original recommendation by the Commission of 29 March 2022 for this Council Decision is available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0132>.

³⁷⁹ Art. 2 in conjunction with the Addendum of Council Decision (EU) 2022/895, available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f701f8d8-e6c5-11ec-a534-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF>; Annex to the Recommendation for a Council Decision; available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0132>.

³⁸⁰ Explanatory Memorandum to the Recommendation for a Council Decision; available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52022PC0132>.

³⁸¹ Collings/Rodriguez, Decoding the U.N. Cybercrime Treaty; available: <https://www.eff.org/deeplinks/2023/04/decoding-uncybercrime-treaty>.

The main international instrument for judicial cooperation in criminal matters is the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC).³⁸² This convention contains important instruments for international cooperation, but was not specifically designed to address issues related to cybercrime. Nor does it provide specific provisions dealing with urgent requests to preserve data.

Based on Art. 3(1) UNTOC the Convention is only applicable in cybercrime cases if the offence involves an organised crime group. Art. 2 UNTOC defines an organised crime group as a structured group of three or more people. Despite its relevance for cases involving forms of organised crime, UNTOC may not become applicable in cybercrime investigations because cybercrime groups may not be identified as organised crime group. The Internet enables close cooperation with others and coordination of activities without ever having met face-to-face. This makes it feasible for offenders to work together in fluid ad hoc groups.³⁸³

The procedures for mutual legal assistance are defined in Art. 18 UNTOC which the general principles for international cooperation³⁸⁴ as well as for specific mutual legal assistance requests³⁸⁵. The list is complex and ranges from taking evidence to tracing proceeds of crime. In the context of cybercrime investigations, UNTOC does not contain specific wording for data-related requests, such as requests to intercept communication or preserve data. However, Art. 18(3)(i) UNTOC opens the provision to other requests, so UNTOC can also be used for data-related requests.

Art. 18 (4)-(5) UNTOC deal with intelligence sharing stipulating a form of cooperation which takes place on a voluntary basis, without the need for the request.³⁸⁶ It covers information relating to criminal matters, such as information about potential consumers of child pornography located in another country that has been discovered during an investigation. Especially in complex investigations, where recourse to formal mutual instruments is time-consuming and hence can hinder investigations, LEAs tend to shift to informal means of cooperation. However, information sharing will only be able to work as a substitute if the state receiving the information is able to collect all relevant evidence on its own. In all other cases, formal cooperation is usually required in any event in order to ensure the chain of custody. In the debate on shifting international cooperation from formal requests to spontaneous information sharing, it is necessary to keep in mind that the formal process was developed to protect the integrity of a state as well the rights of the accused. Sharing of information should therefore not circumvent the dogmatic structure of mutual legal assistance.

The procedural aspects of mutual legal assistance are outlined in Art. 18 (6)-(12) UNTOC. In the context of cybercrime investigations, it is important to note that states are enabled to

³⁸² Convention Against Transnational Organized Crime (2000), GA RES/55/25, Entry into Force: 29 September 2003.

³⁸³ Gercke, „Understanding Cybercrime: phenomena, challenges and legal response“, November 2014, p. 281.

³⁸⁴ Art. 18(1) and (2) UNTOC.

³⁸⁵ Art. 18(3) UNTOC.

³⁸⁶ For details about the intention of the drafters, see: Legislative Guides for the Implementation of the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime, 2004, p. 226, available at: www.unodc.org/pdf/crime/legislative_guides/Legislative%20guides_Full%20version.pdf.

decline mutual assistance requests on the grounds of absence of dual criminality³⁸⁷ which can hinder international cooperation based on UNTOC.

The form and content of requests as well as the channels of communication are defined in Art. 18 (13)-(16) UNTOC. With regard to channels of communication, UNTOC follows the idea that requests are transmitted from central authority to central authority³⁸⁸ and emphasises the importance of this procedure to ensure speedy and proper execution of the request. The roles of central authorities may differ, and range from direct involvement in handling and executing requests to forwarding them to the competent authorities. Alternatively, the states have the discretion to require the transmittal through diplomatic channels – a lengthy procedure dramatically slower in transmission and hindering expedited measures such as the preservation of traffic data. While not offering the means of expedited cooperation, UNTOC provides a general procedure for cases of urgency. If states agree, the International Criminal Police Organisation (Interpol) can be used as channel for communication. In order to facilitate identification of the relevant authority in another country, the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crimes (UNODC) maintains an online directory which provides the issuing authority with details of the central authority of the requested state, the channels of communication and other relevant information.³⁸⁹ When submitting the request, it is necessary to meet the formal requirements as defined by paragraphs. Oral requests are only permitted in urgent cases and need to be followed by a written request. UNODC provides a software for drafting such requests with the aim of ensuring that requests are complete (Mutual Legal Assistance Request Writer Tool).³⁹⁰

11.1.3. UN Convention against Corruption (UNCAC)

The UN Convention against Corruption also contains provisions on international cooperation in its Art. 43.³⁹¹ Where appropriate and consistent with their domestic legal system, States Parties shall consider assisting each other in investigations of and proceedings in civil and administrative matters relating to corruption. Apart from the fact that the norm refers exclusively to corruption crimes, it takes into account the specificity of dual criminality of different states. It is necessary that the offense to which the request of a state relates be considered an offense in both countries. The convention does not contain explicit provisions on cybercrime, but it is applicable if cybercrime-related acts fall under the offense of corruption. The crime of corruption must be considered especially in the case of offenses related to the trading of

³⁸⁷ Art. 18(9) UNTOC.

³⁸⁸ For details about the intention of the drafters, see: Legislative Guides for the Implementation of the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime, 2004, p. 225, available at: www.unodc.org/pdf/crime/legislative_guides/Legislative%20guides_Full%20version.pdf.

³⁸⁹ The online directory of Competent National Authorities (CNA Directory) is available on the platform SHERLOC (SHaring Electronic Resources and Law On Crime) at: <https://sherloc.unodc.org/cld/en/st/cna/CNA.html>. Access requires registration and is reserved for competent national authorities. The directory indicates the central authority responsible for receiving the MLA request, languages accepted, channels of communication, contact points, fax and e-mails, specific requests of the receiving states and sometimes even extracts from domestic legislation of that state.

³⁹⁰ The software is available at: <https://www.unodc.org/mla/index.html>.

³⁹¹ See: https://www.unodc.org/documents/brussels/UN_Convention_Against_Corruption.pdf.

cryptocurrency. A request for assistance from the other state is possible in principle on the basis of this convention.

11.2. CoE Framework

In 2001, the Council of Europe (CoE) elaborated the Convention on Cybercrime which is still the only multilateral, legally binding instrument addressing criminal activity conducted via the Internet³⁹². The CoE Convention on Cybercrime seeks to harmonise national laws relating to cybercrime, to improve domestic procedures for detecting, investigating, and prosecuting such crimes and to provide arrangements for fast and reliable international cooperation on these matters. The CoE Convention on Cybercrime establishes a common minimum standard for domestic computer-related offences and provides for the criminalisation of nine such offences³⁹³, including offences relating to unauthorised access to³⁹⁴ and illicit tampering³⁹⁵ with computer systems, programs or data; computer-related forgery³⁹⁶ and fraud³⁹⁷; and attempting, aiding or abetting the commission of such acts³⁹⁸.

The CoE Convention on Cybercrime establishes mechanisms for international cooperation against cybercrime and requires States Parties to establish powers and procedures to obtain electronic evidence (section 11.2.1. below) and to provide each other mutual legal assistance (section 11.2.2. below). The electronic evidence is distinguished into *computer data*, *traffic data* and *subscriber information*. The term “*computer data*” refers to any representation of facts, information or concepts in a form suitable for processing in a computer system,³⁹⁹ whereas “*traffic data*” means any computer data relating to a communication by means of a computer system.⁴⁰⁰ In contrast, the term “*subscriber data*” means any information held by a service provider relating to subscribers of its services other than *traffic or content data*.⁴⁰¹

11.2.1. Gathering Digital Evidence

The procedural powers for gathering digital evidence are enshrined in Articles 14 – 21 CoE Convention on Cybercrime. According to Article 14(2) CoE Convention on Cybercrime, these

³⁹² CoE Convention on Cybercrime, ETS No.185, Budapest, 23 November 2001 (also known as Budapest Convention) which entered into force on 1 July 2004.

³⁹³ See Art. 2 – 10 CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

³⁹⁴ Art. 2 CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

³⁹⁵ Art. 5 CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

³⁹⁶ Art. 7 CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

³⁹⁷ Art. 8 CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

³⁹⁸ Art. 11 CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

³⁹⁹ Art. 1(b) CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴⁰⁰ Art. 1(d) CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴⁰¹ Art. 18(3) CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

procedural powers may be used in specific criminal investigations or proceedings in any type of case.

11.2.1.1. Preservation of Evidence

Art. 16 CoE Convention on Cybercrime requests for LEAs and other competent national authorities the ability to order the expeditious preservation of specified *computer data* including *traffic data*. Such an order according to Art. 16 CoE Convention on Cybercrime obliges the Internet service provider to save the data that were processed by this provider. The provider is not forced to start collecting data it would not normally store⁴⁰² but the data which already exist have to be stored in a way that preserves its current quality and condition.⁴⁰³ The provider is not obliged to transfer the relevant data to the requesting authority. Rather, Art. 16 CoE Convention on Cybercrime authorises LEAs to prevent the deletion of the relevant data.

11.2.1.2. Disclosure of Evidence

The obligation to transfer data is regulated in Art. 17 and 18 CoE Convention on Cybercrime. By separating the obligation to preserve the data from the obligation to disclose the data the CoE Convention on Cybercrime offers the advantage of attaching different conditions to each obligation. Art. 17 CoE Convention on Cybercrime enables LEAs to order the expedited preservation and partial disclosure of *traffic data* which is extremely useful in cases requiring to trace back the route to a suspected individual and the need for immediate access to identify the path through which this communication was transmitted. Based on Art. 18 CoE Convention on Cybercrime, a provider can be obliged to disclose the data which it has preserved. The preservation of the data does not have to be based on a previous preservation order⁴⁰⁴. Rather, Art. 18(a) CoE Convention on Cybercrime provides a general instrument for LEAs which is especially useful in cases not requiring access to hardware.⁴⁰⁵ Article 18(b) CoE Convention on Cybercrime enables LEAs to order the submission of subscriber information which is an extremely useful tool in cases requiring IP-based investigations. If a cybercrime investigator has identified an IP-address, which was used in connection with an offence, then there is a need to identify the person who used this IP-address at the time of the offence. Based on Art. 18(1)(b) CoE Convention on Cybercrime the provider is obliged to submit the subscriber information defined in Art. 18(3) CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

11.2.1.3. Data-Related Search and Seizure

Art. 19 CoE Convention on Cybercrime introduces a data-related search and seizure procedure but does not specify the requirements which have to be met by investigators to carry

⁴⁰² See No. 152 of the Explanatory Report to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴⁰³ See No. 159 of the Explanatory Report to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴⁰⁴ Based on Article 16 CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴⁰⁵ Gercke, “Understanding Cybercrime: phenomena, challenges and legal response”, ITU 2012, at 6.5.3, p. 248.

out such investigations. Art. 19 (1) CoE Convention on Cybercrime aims to establish an instrument that enables the search of computer systems which is as efficient as traditional procedures.⁴⁰⁶ If the investigator of a LEA discovers during such a search that relevant information is stored on another computer system (e.g. cloud computing), Art. 19 (2) CoE Convention on Cybercrime addresses the need to extend the search to that other system. Art. 19 (3) CoE Convention on Cybercrime provides 4 important measures for receiving evidence which is acceptable in court proceedings: (a) an instrument to seizure a computer system, (b) an instrument to copy the data, (c) to maintain the integrity of copied data⁴⁰⁷, and (d) an instrument that allows them to remove the data if it is illegal content or to ensure at least that this illegal content data can no longer be accessed.

Last but not least, Art. 19 (4) CoE Convention on Cybercrime enables the investigator of an LEA to compel a system administrator to assist LEAs because it is necessary for LEAs to identify the exact location of suspicious data. This provision not only obliges the system administrator to provide the necessary information to the investigator, but also relieves the system administrator from contractual obligations or orders by his supervisors.⁴⁰⁸ The scope of the obligation to support the investigator of a LEA extends only as far “as is reasonable”, but the CoE Convention on Cybercrime does not define the term “reasonable”. According to the Explanatory Report “reasonable” may include disclosing a password or other security measure, but does not in general cover such disclosure where this would go along with unreasonable threats to the privacy of other users or data not included in the current search.⁴⁰⁹

11.2.1.4. Traffic Data and Content Data

Under the CoE Convention on Cybercrime, the term “*traffic data*” refers to data generated by computers during the communication process in order to route a communication from its origin to its destination. Therefore, “*traffic data*” includes IP-addresses identifying the partners of an Internet-related communication.⁴¹⁰ Art. 20 CoE Convention on Cybercrime introduces two different ways to collect *traffic data*:

- The *first* way of collecting such *traffic data* is according to Art. 20(1)(a) CoE Convention on Cybercrime to impose an obligation on an Internet service provider to enable LEAs to collect the relevant data directly which generally requires the installation of an interface for LEAs to access the provider’s infrastructure.⁴¹¹
- The *second* way enables LEAs to compel an Internet service provider according to Art. 20(1)(b) CoE Convention on Cybercrime to collect data at their request allowing LEAs to benefit from the technical capacities and the knowledge of the provider.

⁴⁰⁶ This instrument has to be supplemented, see No. 187 of the Explanatory Report to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴⁰⁷ See No. 197 of the Explanatory Report to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴⁰⁸ See No. 201 of the Explanatory Report to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴⁰⁹ See No. 202 of the Explanatory Report to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴¹⁰ See No. 30 of the Explanatory Report to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴¹¹ See No. 220 of the Explanatory Report to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

One of the major difficulties for investigations based on Art. 20 CoE Convention on Cybercrime is the use of means of anonymous communication. Similarly, the use of public internet terminals creates a comparable anonymity for its users, although the Court of Justice of the European Union has introduced a duty to identify users of a public WLAN to avoid liability for copyright and other offences committed using this WLAN.⁴¹²

Art. 21 CoE Convention on Cybercrime provides the possibility for LEAs to record data communications and to analyse the content if the LEAs already know who the communication partners are but have no information about the type of information exchanged. The *content data* affected by this provision includes files downloaded from websites or file-sharing systems, e-mails and chat/VoIP conversations. One of the most important difficulties for investigations based on Article 21 CoE Convention on Cybercrime is the use of encryption technology.⁴¹³

11.2.2. Mutual Legal Assistance Treaty (MLAT)

The CoE Convention on Cybercrime addresses the increasing importance of international cooperation in its Art. 23 to 35. Art. 23 CoE Convention on Cybercrime defines the extent, scope and priority of international cooperation in cybercrime investigations among Parties to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime in three general principles:

- (1) Parties are supposed to provide each other cooperation in international investigations to the widest extent possible.
- (2) The general principles are applicable in any investigation involving the need to collect evidence in electronic form.
- (3) The provisions of the CoE Convention on Cybercrime substitute neither provisions of international agreements pertaining to mutual legal assistance and extradition nor relevant provisions of domestic law pertaining to international cooperation.

The drafters of the CoE Convention on Cybercrime emphasized that mutual legal assistance (MLA) should in general be carried out through the application of relevant treaties and similar arrangements for MLA. As a consequence, the CoE Convention on Cybercrime does not intend to create a separate general regime on MLA.⁴¹⁴

The CoE Convention on Cybercrime requires Parties to adopt a set of procedural powers to secure electronic evidence, such as search and seizure of computer systems⁴¹⁵, production

⁴¹² CJEU, decision of 15 September 2016 in case C-484/14, *Tobias Mc Fadden v. Sony Music Entertainment Germany GmbH*; Bisle/Frommer, CR 2017, pp. 54-63.

⁴¹³ Gercke, “Understanding Cybercrime: phenomena, challenges and legal response”, ITU 2012, at 6.5.3, p. 259.

⁴¹⁴ Gercke, “Understanding Cybercrime: phenomena, challenges and legal response”, ITU 2012, at 6.6.5, p. 274.

⁴¹⁵ Art. 19 CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

orders for data⁴¹⁶, interception of communications⁴¹⁷. These are subject to rule of law safeguards. They apply to electronic evidence in relation to any crime.

In the course of cybercrime investigations, a core difficulty for national LEAs is that electronic evidence needed is increasingly available only in foreign, sometimes unknown, multiple or shifting jurisdictions. MLA arrangements appear not always feasible or too cumbersome to secure volatile electronic evidence, although Art. 25 CoE Convention on Cybercrime highlights the importance of fast communication and Art. 26 CoE Convention on Cybercrime sets out regulations necessary for LEAs to inform foreign LEAs without jeopardising their own investigation. This is hardly surprising because both formal processes were developed to protect the integrity of a Party as a state as well as to safeguard the rights of the accused.⁴¹⁸ Bearing in mind the principle of national sovereignty, the procedural instruments provided by the CoE Convention on Cybercrime can only be used for investigations at the national level. If cybercrime investigators realise that evidence has to be collected outside their national territory, they need to request MLA.

Except for one, all procedural instruments for gather digital evidence established in the Art. 16 – 21 CoE Convention on Cybercrime⁴¹⁹ have a corresponding provision in the Art. 28 – 33 CoE Convention on Cybercrime enabling LEAs to apply the procedural instruments upon request of a LEA in another jurisdiction. Only Art. 18 CoE Convention on Cybercrime on production orders including on subscriber information has no corresponding provision in Chapter III on international co-operation of the CoE Convention on Cybercrime. However, the Cybercrime Convention Committee (T-CY) adopted a Guidance Note on the Production of Subscriber Information (Article 18 CoE Convention on Cybercrime) in 2017.⁴²⁰ This Guidance Note provides criminal justice authorities with the ability to request a service provider offering its service in the territory of a Party to produce subscriber information for example of a webmail or a social media account even if the data or the provider are in another Party's jurisdiction. Consequently, Art. 18 CoE Convention on Cybercrime could serve as the domestic legal basis.

11.2.3. Publicly Available Data and Individual Consent

The CoE Convention on Cybercrime provides in its Art. 32 two scenarios in which a Party may have access to stored *computer data* without the authorisation of another Party:

⁴¹⁶ Art. 16, 17 and 18 CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴¹⁷ Art. 21 CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴¹⁸ Gercke, “Understanding Cybercrime: phenomena, challenges and legal response”, ITU 2012, at 6.6.5, p. 276.

⁴¹⁹ Chapter III. on International co-operation of the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴²⁰ Cybercrime Convention Committee (T-CY), “T-CY Guidance Note #10 on Production Orders for Subscriber Information (Art. 18. Budapest Convention)”, adopted on 1 March 2017, available at: <https://ccdcoe.org/uploads/2018/11/COE-170228-GN10-1.pdf>.

- The first scenario concerns access to publicly available (open source) stored *computer data* regardless of where the data is located geographically⁴²¹. An example of such publicly available data is information made available on websites without access control (such as passwords). If cybercrime investigators were not allowed to access these websites, this could seriously hamper their investigation.
- The second scenario concerns access to data based on the consent of the person in control of this data⁴²². When an investigator has obtained the lawful and voluntary consent of the person who has lawful authority to disclose the data, the investigator may access this data.

Whereas the first scenario appears widely accepted, the second scenario raises serious concerns because it probably contradicts fundamental principles of international law. Based on international law, investigators have to respect national sovereignty during an investigation.⁴²³ Investigators are especially not allowed to carry out investigations in another state without the consent of the competent authorities in that state. The decision whether such permission should be granted is not in the hands of an individual, but of the state authorities because interference with national sovereignty not only affects the rights of the individual, but also state concerns. However, it may be argued that Parties ratifying the CoE Convention on Cybercrime partly waive their protection by the principle of national sovereignty and allow other countries to carry out investigations affecting their territory.⁴²⁴ This argument is supported by the Guidance Note of the Cybercrime Convention Committee on the interpretation of Article 32(b) CoE Convention on Cybercrime which points out that this provision would not cover situations where the data are not stored in another Party or where it is uncertain where the data are located.⁴²⁵

Other concerns regarding the second scenario are that Art. 32(b) CoE Convention on Cybercrime neither defines any procedures for the investigation nor safeguards the suspect's right to privacy, right to protection of his personal data and procedural rights. The wording of this provision seems to suggest that not even limitations of national law are applicable which would apply to identical domestic investigations. However, the Guidance Note of the Cybercrime Convention Committee on the applicable law points out that access to data would not be permitted under Art. 32(b) CoE Convention on Cybercrime if access or disclosure was

⁴²¹ Art. 32(a) CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴²² Art. 32(b) CoE Convention on Cybercrime.

⁴²³ National sovereignty is a fundamental principle in international law, see: Roth, "State Sovereignty, International Legality, and Moral disagreement, 2005, p. 1, available at: <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/view/4246351/state-sovereignty-international-legality-and-moral-disagreement->.

⁴²⁴ Gercke, "Understanding Cybercrime: phenomena, challenges and legal response", ITU 2012, at 6.6.5, pp. 277-278.

⁴²⁵ Cybercrime Convention Committee, T-CY Guidance Note on Transborder Access to Data (Article 32), adopted on 2-3 December 2014, T-CY(2013)29rev, 8 December 2014, p. 22 on the notion of "transborder" and "location".

not permitted domestically.⁴²⁶ Further, it has to be pointed out that LEAs may only seek (!) permission of the person who has the lawful authority to disclose the data. This contrasts starkly with the instrument of a production order according to Art. 18 CoE Convention on Cybercrime. Finally, it has to be pointed out that the standard hypothesis underlying Art. 32(b) CoE Convention on Cybercrime is that the person contacted to provide access to the data is physically located in the territory of the requesting Party leading the Cybercrime Convention Committee to suggest in its Guiding Note that LEAs should take into account that many Parties would object or consider it a criminal offence, if a person who is physically in their territory is directly approached by foreign LEAs seeking his or her cooperation.⁴²⁷

11.2.4. The 24/7 Network of Contacts

To increase the speed of international investigations, the CoE Convention on Cybercrime not only highlights in its Art. 25 the importance of enabling the use of expedited means of communication, but also obliges its Parties in its Art. 35 to designate a contact point for MLA requests which is available without any time limitations. To improve the efficiency of MLA requests, the Parties are obliged to establish these contact points and to ensure that they are able to carry out certain immediate action⁴²⁸ as well as to maintain their service⁴²⁹.

The CoE Convention on Cybercrime does not prescribe which national authority should be responsible for operating the national contact point of the 24/7 network. Nevertheless, the idea of the 24/7 network of contact points provides a useful answer to the challenges of fighting cybercrime associated especially with the speed of data exchange processes. Unfortunately, a study carried out in 2009 on the functioning of 24/7 points of contact in an international network fighting cybercrime⁴³⁰ revealed that the full potential of such a network is not (yet) used because not all Parties of the CoE Convention on Cybercrime had created a functioning contact point and not all contact points were used to their full capacity or known domestically.

11.2.4.1. Second Additional Protocol to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime (on enhanced co-operation and disclosure for electronic evidence)

⁴²⁶ T-CY Guidance Notes, T-CY(2013)29rev, 8 December 2014, p. 22 on the applicable law regarding Transborder Access to data (Article 32).

⁴²⁷ T-CY Guidance Notes, T-CY(2013)29rev, 8 December 2014, p. 23 on the location of the person consenting to provide access or disclose data regarding Transborder Access to data (Article 32).

⁴²⁸ Article 35(1) CoE Convention on Cybercrime mentions as measures (a) technical advice, (b) preservation of data and (c) the collection of evidence, the provision of legal information and locating of suspects.

⁴²⁹ Article 35(2) CoE Convention on Cybercrime requires for such a contact point (a) the capacity to carry out communications on an expedited basis and (b) the ability to co-ordinate with other national authorities on an expedited basis.

⁴³⁰ CoE Economic Crime Division, „The functioning of 24/7 points of contact for cybercrime“, Discussion Paper, 2 April 2009.

With the aim of moving away from data storage location as a decisive factor, the CoE Committee of Ministers adopted a Second Additional Protocol⁴³¹ to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime on 17 November 2021. In the previous negotiations and decisions on the Second Additional Protocol to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime, the EU participated in order to present a unified line on electronic evidence and cross-border access on an internal level before involving third parties in the negotiations.⁴³² The European Union also focused on ensuring that the Additional Protocol complies with European data protection law and that human rights and fundamental freedoms are taken into account.⁴³³ This Second Additional Protocol addresses the challenges to criminal justice in cyberspace and provides a legal basis for more direct and effective cooperation with service providers on electronic evidence, especially for the disclosure of the domain name registration information, subscriber information and traffic data.⁴³⁴ Art. 3 (1) Second Additional Protocol incorporates the definitions provided in the CoE Convention on Cybercrime for “*computer data*”, “*traffic data*” and “*subscriber information*”.

Art. 6 and 7 Second Additional Protocol permit the competent authority of one Party to engage directly with private entities possessing or controlling the sought information and located in the territory of a second Party, whether an MLAT (Mutual Legal Assistance Treaty) between the two interested Parties exists or not. Whereas Art. 6 Second Additional Protocol relates to information “*for identifying or contacting the registrant of a domain name*”, Art. 7 Second Additional Protocol relates to “*subscriber information*”. For LEAs, this will be associated with both: time savings and reduced effort.

Art. 8 Second Additional Protocol provides for Parties to adopt any legislative measure as necessary to issue orders incoming from another Party and addressing OSPs located in its territory for the production of *subscriber information* and *traffic data*. The strict deadlines introduced for the OSP’s response ensure significantly expedited production of the data (20 days for *subscriber information* and 45 days for *traffic data*).

Art. 9 Second Additional Protocol requires that the 24/7 Network of Contacts to be able to transmit and receive requests from a Point of Contact in another Party seeking immediate assistance in obtaining from a service provider in the territory of that Party the expedited disclosure of specified, stored *computer data* in that service provider’s possession or control, and without the need for a request for mutual legal assistance. Another innovation in Art. 9 Second Additional Protocol is data access in an emergency. The emergency is defined in Art. 3 (2) c Second Additional Protocol as a significant risk to the safety and life of a natural person.

⁴³¹ CoE, Second Additional Protocol to the Convention on Cybercrime on enhanced cooperation and disclosure of electronic evidence, Draft Protocol version 2, 12 April 2021.

⁴³² Questions and Answers: Mandate tot he Additional Protocol tot he Budapest Convention; available: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/MEMO_19_865.

⁴³³ Questions and Answers: Mandate tot he Additional Protocol tot he Budapest Convention; available: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/MEMO_19_865.

⁴³⁴ Summary oft he Second Additional Protocol to the Convention on Cybercrime on enhanced cooperation and disclosure of electronic evidence of the CoE; available at: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list?module=treaty-detail&treatynum=224>.

The Second Additional Protocol of the CoE was opened for signature in May 2022. Since then, 37 countries, latest Mauritius, have signed it. Five of these states have also ratified the protocol. For the entry into force it is required that the Second Additional Protocol of the CoE has been ratified by 5 states. The European Parliament decided on January 17, 2023, that member states of the EU may ratify the convention.⁴³⁵

11.2.5. Applicability and Ranking of the Two Conventions on Cybercrime

Which of the two conventions will prevail at the international level is difficult to predict. Of course, with 193 UN member states, the UN Convention on Cybercrime will have a much wider reach than the CoE Convention with 68 signatory countries. At the European level, the CoE Convention will probably be applied with priority. It is expected that the CoE Convention on Cybercrime will also harmonize with other European laws and meet stricter criteria, for example, in the area of protecting the privacy of individuals. On the other hand, most cyberattacks worldwide originate from states that are not members of the CoE and did not sign the CoE Convention on Cybercrime.⁴³⁶ With the entry into force of the UN Convention, it will at least be possible for European LEAs to get operators of service providers or authorities located in other than EU countries and who have not signed the CoE Convention to cooperate.

However, the fact that the signatures and ratifications of the Second Additional Protocol to the CoE Convention on Cybercrime are so restrained can be scored as a sign that the individual states are waiting for the finalized UN Convention on Cooperation in Combating Cybercrime, and then decide to sign one or the other. During the project the developments in this field are observed and reported.

11.3. EU Framework

This section describes first the existing mechanisms for international cooperation under Directive (EU) 2014/41 (section 11.3.1. below) and then the new mechanisms according to the final eEvidence Package (section 11.3.2. below) as well as the proposed Draft Police Cooperation Code (section 11.3.3 below).

11.3.1. Directive (EU) 2014/41

The main legal instrument at disposal of EU MS seeking electronic data of OSPs established in other EU MS within the framework of criminal proceedings is the *European Investigation Order* (EIO) established by Directive (EU) 2014/41.⁴³⁷ The EIO is a judicial decision, issued or validated by a judicial authority of one Member State (the “*issuing Member State*”), to have one or several specific investigative measure(s) carried out in another Member State (the “*executing Member State*”) to obtain evidence. Applicable investigative measures include,

⁴³⁵ See: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2023-0002_EN.html.

⁴³⁶ See: <https://de.statista.com/themen/9207/cyberangriffe-weltweit/#topicOverview>.

⁴³⁷ Directive (EU) 2014/41 is transposed in all EU Member States since 2017.

among others, interception of telecommunications and preservation of (electronic) evidence. The only types of evidence gathering that are excluded from Directive (EU) 2014/41 are the establishment of a Joint Investigation Team, and the collection of evidence within its framework; and cross-border surveillance provided for in the Convention implementing the Schengen agreement.

From a cybercrime investigator's point of view, Directive (EU) 2014/41 not only approximates the handling of international cooperation cases to the handling of domestic cases,⁴³⁸ but also introduced the possibility of cross-border real-time gathering of evidence allowing access to and transfer of both, telecommunications *traffic* and *location data* as well as *content data*. However, Directive (EU) 2014/41 does not contain specific provisions related to accessing electronic data, except for Art. 10(2)(e) Directive (EU) 2014/41, which concerns the identification of a person holding an IP address.

Further, the timeframe of 30 plus 90 days, while representing a step forward compared to previously existing instruments, is still insufficient to properly address the volatile and dynamic field of electronic data, especially since this deadline may be extended in certain cases (e.g. if the execution of the EIO has the potential to prejudice an ongoing criminal investigation or prosecution, or if the objects, documents, or data concerned are already being used in other proceedings)⁴³⁹.

Another limit of Directive (EU) 2014/41 is that Ireland and Denmark are neither bound by it nor subject to its application, based on Articles 1 and 2 of Protocol No 21 and Articles 1 and 2 of Protocol No 22 annexed to the Treaty of the European Union (TEU). Because several OSPs receiving high numbers of requests are based in Ireland (like Airbnb, Apple, Facebook, Google, Microsoft, Twitter, Verizon Media),⁴⁴⁰ the scope of Directive (EU) 2014/41 seems significantly limited.

Against this background, the procedures and timelines provided for in Directive (EU) 2014/41 establishing the EIO or in the Convention on Mutual Assistance in Criminal Matters do not appear to be appropriate for electronic evidence, which is more volatile and could more easily and quickly be deleted. Obtaining electronic evidence using judicial cooperation channels often takes a long time, resulting in situations where subsequent leads might no longer be available.⁴⁴¹

11.3.2. Final eEvidence Package

⁴³⁸ An EIO is to be treated and executed like comparable domestic cases and comes with precise deadlines: 30 days for the decision on the recognition of the order, and 90 days for the execution of the order, Art. 12 (3) and (4) Directive (EU) 2014/41. It should be noted that the existence of a similar offence in the national legislation of the two or more Member States involved (*double criminality*) is not required by Directive (EU) 2014/41 for an EIO, but is an optional ground for refusal of an EIO.

⁴³⁹ Article 15 of Directive 2014/41/EU

⁴⁴⁰ Europol, Eurojust, EJM, 2020.

⁴⁴¹ Rec. (8) eEvidence Regulation.

Because there is no harmonised framework for cooperation with service providers, but a need to provide for specific rules as regards cross-border judicial cooperation for preserving and producing electronic evidence, which address the specific nature of electronic evidence, the European legislator has adopted in June 2023 the final eEvidence Package which includes an obligation on service providers to respond directly to requests stemming from LEAs in another Member State and clarifies the rules applicable to LEAs and judicial authorities as well as to service providers in the field of electronic evidence.⁴⁴²

This section highlights the new requirements and opportunities for investigators emerging from the final 'eEvidence Package' to inform practitioners, from the CYCLOPES project and beyond, on how changes in managing e-evidence may impact their practice and obligations. Raising awareness and exploiting the benefits of the new regulation should accelerate the practices of LEAs and improve their ability to carry out digital forensics and cybercrime investigations that consistently lead to convictions. First, this section will start with an understanding of how the requirement for an E-Evidence Package came to fruition, as cybercrime investigations were at the forefront of instigating the process.

In April 2018, the European Commission had presented a legislative package on electronic evidence consisting of a proposal for a Regulation on European Production and Preservation Orders in criminal matters (Draft eEvidence Regulation)⁴⁴³ and a proposal for a Directive laying down harmonised rules on the appointment of legal representatives for the purpose of gathering evidence in criminal proceedings (Draft eEvidence Directive).⁴⁴⁴ The Draft eEvidence Package entered the trilogue stage of the legislative process in February 2021⁴⁴⁵ and the compromise text for both, the Compromise eEvidence Directive⁴⁴⁶ as well as the Compromise eEvidence Regulation⁴⁴⁷ was agreed upon almost two years later in January 2023.⁴⁴⁸ The final

⁴⁴² Rec. (8) and (9) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁴³ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European Production and Preservation Orders for electronic evidence in criminal matters, COM(2018) 225 final, 17 April 2018.

⁴⁴⁴ Commission, Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on the appointment of legal representatives for the purpose of gathering evidence in criminal proceedings, COM(2018) 226 final, 17 April 2018.

⁴⁴⁵ See Council of the EU, "E-Evidence Package: First Trilogue Meeting", 10 February 2021, available at: <https://www.2021portugal.eu/en/news/e-evidence-package-first-trilogue-meeting/>.

⁴⁴⁶ Council of the EU, Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on the designation of designated establishments and the appointment of legal representatives for the purpose of gathering electronic evidence in criminal proceedings, final compromise text, 5449/23, 20 January 2023, available at: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-5449-2023-INIT/en/pdf>.

⁴⁴⁷ Council of the EU, Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European Production and Preservation Orders for electronic evidence in criminal proceedings and for the execution of custodial sentences following criminal proceedings, final compromise text, 5448/23, 20 January 2023, available at: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-5448-2023-INIT/en/pdf>.

⁴⁴⁸ Council of the EU, „Electronic evidence: Council confirms agreement with the European Parliament on new rules to improve cross-border access to e-evidence“, Press Release 48/23, 25 January 2023, available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2023/01/25/electronic-evidence-council-confirms-agreement-with-the-european-parliament-on-new-rules-to-improve-cross-border-access-to-e-evidence/>.

version of both, the final eEvidence Regulation⁴⁴⁹ and the final eEvidence Directive⁴⁵⁰ were adopted by the European Parliament on 13 June 2023 and by the Council of the EU on 27 June 2023.⁴⁵¹

11.3.2.1. The Final eEvidence Regulation

In investigations that involve digital information, especially that which is stored by external providers on cloud infrastructure or other remote servers, the retention and preservation of that information relies on the service provider to maintain. A request from a bad actor during a criminal investigation could easily wipe or remove such information at the click of a button removing access to potentially evidentially valuable and incriminating information in an instant. While services established under the same country as the jurisdiction of the crime can rely on national law to instruct the service provider to preserve or produce such evidence, the same cannot be applied to investigations that have a cross border component.

The final eEvidence Regulation introduces binding European Production and Preservation Orders which can be issued to seek preservation or production of data that are stored by a *service provider* located in another jurisdiction and that are necessary as evidence in criminal investigations or criminal proceedings.⁴⁵² The intention behind the European Production and Preservation Orders is to enable a competent judicial authority in a Member State to request a service provider offering services in the Union to produce or preserve electronic evidence.

The categories of data that can be obtained with a European Production Order by the competent authorities include “*subscriber data*”, “*data requested for the sole purpose of identifying the user*” and “*traffic data*” (the three categories were jointly also referred to as ‘*non-*

⁴⁴⁹ For the first reading in the European Parliament the provisions of the Compromise eEvidence Regulation have been re-numbered and, to some extent, rephrased. Therefore, the final provisions of the eEvidence Regulation are quoted from the Parliamentary first reading’s version: Council of the EU, Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European Production and Preservation Orders for electronic evidence in criminal matters, 10312/23, Outcome of European Parliaments first reading, 14 June 2023, available at: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-10312-2023-INIT/en/pdf>.

⁴⁵⁰ For the first reading in the European Parliament the provisions of the Compromise eEvidence Directive have been re-numbered and, to some extent, rephrased. Therefore, the final provisions of the eEvidence Directive are quoted from the Parliamentary first reading’s version: Council of the EU, Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on the appointment of legal representatives for the purpose of gathering evidence in criminal proceedings, 10311/23, Outcome of European Parliaments first reading, 14 June 2023, available at: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-10311-2023-INIT/en/pdf>.

⁴⁵¹ Council of the EU, “Council adopts EU laws on better access to electronic evidence”, Press Release 490/23, 27 June 2023, available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2023/06/27/council-adopts-eu-laws-on-better-access-to-electronic-evidence/>.

⁴⁵² Commission, Proposal for a Regulation on European Production and Preservation Orders for electronic evidence in criminal matters, COM(2018) 225 final, 17 April 2018, p. 4.

*content data*⁴⁵³) and stored *content data*. This distinction exists in the legal orders of many Member States and also in non-EU legal frameworks.⁴⁵⁴

According to Art. 3(8) eEvidence Regulation, '**electronic evidence**' means *subscriber data, traffic data or content data* stored by or on behalf of a service provider, in an electronic form, at the time of receipt of a European Production Order Certificate (EPOC) or a European Preservation Order Certificate (EPOC-PR).⁴⁵⁵

The term "**subscriber data**" means any data held by a service provider relating to the subscription to its services, pertaining to (a) the identity of a subscriber and (b) the type of service and its duration.⁴⁵⁶

The term "**traffic data**" refers to data related to the provision of a service offered by a service provider which serve to provide context or additional information about such service and includes metadata.⁴⁵⁷

The term "**content data**" means any data in a digital format such as text, voice, videos, images, and sound.⁴⁵⁸

In addition, the term "**data requested for the sole purpose of identifying the user**" refers IP addresses as well as the relevant source ports and time stamp (date/time), or technical equivalents of these identifiers and related information where requested by LEAs or by judicial authorities for the sole purpose of identifying the user in a specific criminal investigation.⁴⁵⁹

These core terms of the eEvidence Regulation provide a new common terminology for cross-border access to electronic evidence. In the context of the CYCLOPES project, the possibility to preserve and gather data directly from the service provider through judicial enforcement appears beneficial for any cybercrime investigation of LEAs not only concerning the acquisition of relevant investigative data, but also concerning the preservation of relevant evidence while at the same time ensuring that its admissibility is not affected.

⁴⁵³ The definition of „*non-content data*“ in Rec. (20) of the Commission’s Draft eEvidence Regulation has been dropped in Rec. (20) compromise text and Rec. (31) sentence 1 eEvidence Regulation (enumerating solely “*subscriber data, traffic data and content data*” as covered) in order to bring the categorisation of data in line with Directive 2002/58/EC, with the case law of the CJEU and with international law including in particular the Budapest Convention, Rec. (31) sentence 2 eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁵⁴ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation on European Production and Preservation Orders for electronic evidence in criminal matters, COM(2018) 225 final, 17 April 2018, p. 14.

⁴⁵⁵ The original definition of ‘*electronic evidence*’ in Art. 2(6) of the Commission’s Draft e-Evidence Regulation had referred to „evidence stored in electronic form by or on behalf of a service provider at the time of receipt of a Production or Preservation Order certificate, consisting in stored *subscriber data, access data, transactional data and content data*”.

⁴⁵⁶ Art. 3(9) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁵⁷ Art. 3(11) eEvidence Regulation. The Commission had proposed to term this kind of data “*transactional data*”, Art. 2(9) Draft eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁵⁸ Art. 3(12) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁵⁹ Art. 3(10) eEvidence Regulation. The term “*data requested for the sole purpose of identifying the user*” has evolved in the course of the legislative process. The Commission had originally proposed in Art. 2(8) Draft eEvidence Regulation to define a term “*access data*” as referring to data related to the commencement and termination of a user access session to a service.

The eEvidence Regulation introduces two new legal instruments for access to *electronic evidence*:

- The **European Production Order** as a decision which orders the production of *electronic evidence* (= *subscriber data, traffic data or content data*).⁴⁶⁰
- The **European Preservation Order** as a decision which orders the preservation of *electronic evidence* (by freezing a set of data to avoid its loss) for the purposes of a subsequent request for production.⁴⁶¹

Both orders are served by competent authorities of an EU Member State⁴⁶² (depending on the category of data sought, different authorities may have competence⁴⁶³) either to the *designated establishment*⁴⁶⁴ or to the *legal representatives*⁴⁶⁵ designated by the *service provider* concerned.⁴⁶⁶

The conditions for issuing a **European Production Order** are set out in Art. 5 eEvidence Regulation which requires the European Production Order to be '*necessary and proportionate*'⁴⁶⁷ relating to the rights of the individual who has been alleged of a crime in order to reasonably justify the European Production Order. While a European Production Order to obtain **subscriber data** or to obtain **data requested for the sole purpose of identifying the user** may be issued for all criminal offences and for the execution of certain custodial sentences or detention orders,⁴⁶⁸ the threshold and requirements for accessing *traffic data* and *content data* are more stringent, given that such data potentially contain more intrusive data. Therefore, a European Production Order to obtain **traffic data** or **content data** can only be issued for: (a) *criminal offences punishable by a custodial sentence of a maximum of three years*; or (b) for a set of specific offences, namely (i) *fraudulent activities* as per Directive (EU) 2019/713⁴⁶⁹, (ii) *child sexual abuse and exploitation* as per Directive 2011/93/EU⁴⁷⁰, and (iii) *attacks against information systems* as per Directive 2013/40/EU⁴⁷¹; (c) for *terrorist offences, offences related to a terrorist group and offences related to terrorist activities* as per Directive

⁴⁶⁰ Art. 3(1) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁶¹ Art. 3(2) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁶² Art. 4 eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁶³ The issuing authority for a European Production Order to obtain *subscriber data* and *data requested for the sole purpose of identifying the user* is determined in Art. 4(1) eEvidence Regulation and to obtain *traffic data* is determined in Art. 4(2) eEvidence Regulation, while the issuing authority for a European Preservation Order for data of any category is determined in Art. 4(3) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁶⁴ Defined in Art. 3(6) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁶⁵ Defined in Art. 3(7) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁶⁶ Art. 7(1) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁶⁷ Art. 5(2) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁶⁸ Art. 5(3) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁶⁹ Directive (EU) 2019/713 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on combating fraud and counterfeiting of non-cash means of payment and replacing Council Framework Decision 2001/413/JHA

⁴⁷⁰ Directive 2011/93/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on combating the sexual abuse and sexual exploitation of children and child pornography, and replacing Council Framework Decision 2004/68/JHA

⁴⁷¹ Directive 2013/40/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 August 2013 on attacks against information systems and replacing Council Framework Decision 2005/222/JHA

(EU) 2017/541⁴⁷²; or (d) for *the execution of certain custodial sentences or detention orders of at least four months*.⁴⁷³

Looking at the effects of a European Production Order, the addressee⁴⁷⁴ immediately has to preserve the requested data⁴⁷⁵ which are to be transmitted directly to the issuing authority or the LEAs as indicated in the EPOC within 10 days⁴⁷⁶. In cases of emergency, the 10-day period can become 8 hours or 96 hours when mandatory prior notification is required.⁴⁷⁷ However, it appears most important in the context of the CYCLOPES project that the *service provider* is under no obligation to *decrypt* or provide the data in *unencrypted* format, Rec. (20) sentence 3 eEvidence Regulation.⁴⁷⁸ This could place a significant limitation on the usefulness of the data received from a *service provider*, especially given the current increase in end-to-end encryption of communications data.

Finally, to make a request for a European Production Order the form provided in Annex 1 of the eEvidence Regulation must be completed. This requires the request to include specific information such as IP address, email, telephone number, name/username concerning the subject or the request and an indication of the specific data to be produced.⁴⁷⁹

- (a) Concerning *subscriber data* this can include name, date of birth, address, contact information as well as registration, profile and financial information, amongst others; a time range for the data may also be stipulated.
- (b) Concerning data requested for the sole purpose of identifying the user this can include IP connection records such as IP addresses / logs / access numbers together with other technical identifiers, such as source ports and time stamps or equivalent, the user ID and the interface used in the context of the use of the service.
- (c) Concerning *traffic data* this can include call data and cell site information for phone records; routing and volume information for internet services; and logfiles or other for hosting providers.
- (d) Concerning *content data* this can include dumps of a mailbox, files from a storage service, messages, devices, contact lists, and similar. It is also necessary to provide details of the category of offence.

The conditions for issuing a **European Preservation Order** are set out in Art. 6 eEvidence Regulation and mirror the requirements for a European Production Order. In addition, a

⁴⁷² Directive (EU) 2017/541 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2017 on combating terrorism and replacing Council Framework Decision 2002/475/JHA and amending Council Decision 2005/671/JHA

⁴⁷³ Art. 5(4) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁷⁴ Pursuant to Art. 9(1) eEvidence Regulation, the addressee receives a European Production Order (or a European Preservation Order) certified for the accuracy and correctness of its content in the form of a European Production Order Certificate, EPOC (or a European Preservation Order Certificate, EPOC-PR).

⁴⁷⁵ Art. 10(1) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁷⁶ Art. 10(2) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁷⁷ Art. 10(4) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁷⁸ This requirement originated in Rec. (19) sentence 3 of the Commission's Draft eEvidence Regulation ("*Data should be provided regardless of whether it is encrypted or not.*") and changed from Rec. (19a) sentence 3 of the Compromise eEvidence Regulation ("*However, this Regulation should not stipulate any obligation for service providers to decrypt data*") to its final version in Rec. 20 sentence 3 eEvidence Regulation: "*However, this Regulation should not lay down any obligation for service providers to decrypt data.*"

⁴⁷⁹ Section F "Electronic evidence to be produced" of Annex I of the eEvidence Regulation.

European Preservation Order has to be necessary for and proportionate to the purpose of preventing the removal, deletion or alteration of data with a view to issuing a subsequent request for production of those data via mutual legal assistance, a European Investigation Order (EIO) or a European Production Order, taking into account the rights of the suspect or the accused person.⁴⁸⁰

However, the threshold for a European Preservation Order is lower than for a European Production Order. A European Preservation Order may be requested for all criminal offences provided a similar request could have been made for a domestic case or for the execution of certain custodial sentences or detention orders of at least four months.⁴⁸¹

Upon receiving a European Preservation Order, the *service provider* has to preserve for up to 60 days, and, where applicable, a request to preserve the data for a further 30 days may be made.⁴⁸²

11.3.2.2. The final eEvidence Directive

In the context of cybercrime investigations, the final eEvidence Directive applies to decisions and orders for the purpose of gathering electronic evidence not only on the basis of the eEvidence Regulation, but also on the basis of Directive (EU) 2014/41 as well as on the basis of the Convention⁴⁸³ on Mutual Assistance in Criminal Matters between Member States of the Union.⁴⁸⁴ Furthermore, the eEvidence Directive applies to decisions and orders for the purpose of gathering electronic evidence on the basis of national law addressed by a Member State to a *legal representative* or *designated establishment of a service provider*.⁴⁸⁵

At its core, the eEvidence Directive introduces an obligation for *service providers*⁴⁸⁶ which *offer services in the Union*⁴⁸⁷ (meaning in one or more Member States)⁴⁸⁸ either to designate a

⁴⁸⁰ Art. 6(2) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁸¹ Art. 6(3) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁸² Art. 11(1) eEvidence Regulation.

⁴⁸³ Council Act of 29 May 2000 establishing in accordance with Article 34 TEU the Convention on Mutual Assistance in Criminal Matters between the Member States of the EU, 12 July 2000, Official Journal of the EC, 43 C 197, p. 1.

⁴⁸⁴ Art. 1(2) sentence 1 eEvidence Directive.

⁴⁸⁵ Art. 1(2) sentence 2 eEvidence Directive.

⁴⁸⁶ Defined in Art. 2(1) eEvidence Directive as „any natural or legal person that provides one or more of the following categories of services ...: (a) *electronic communications services* as defined in Art. 2 No. 4 Directive (EU) 2018/1972; (b) *internet domain name and IP numbering services*, such as IP address assignment, domain name registry, domain name registrar and domain name-related privacy and proxy services; and (c) *other information society services* as referred to in Art. 1(1)(b) Directive (EU) 2015/1535 that either (i) enable their users to communicate with each other, or (ii) make it possible to store or otherwise process data on behalf of the users to whom the service is provided, provided that the storage of data is a defining component of the service provided to the user“.

⁴⁸⁷ Art. 2(3) eEvidence Directive.

⁴⁸⁸ Art. 1(5) sentence 2 and Rec. (8) eEvidence Directive explicitly excluding the applicability to “*service providers established on the territory of a single Member State that offer services exclusively on the territory of that Member State*”.

*designated establishment*⁴⁸⁹ or to appoint a *legal representative*⁴⁹⁰ as **addressee for the receipt of, compliance with and enforcement of decisions and orders** within the scope of Art. 1(2) eEvidence Directive issued for the purpose of gathering evidence in criminal proceedings.⁴⁹¹

The term “*offering services*” either “*on the territory of a Member State*”⁴⁹² or “*in the Union*”⁴⁹³ means that the *service provider* (a) enables legal or natural persons in a Member State to use its services, and (b) has a *substantial connection* based on specific factual criteria to the Member State. Such a *substantial connection* is deemed to exist when either (i) the *service provider* has an *establishment* in a Member State or (ii) there is a significant number of users in one or more Member States, or (iii) where there is *targeting of activities* towards one or more Member States.⁴⁹⁴ Such *targeting of activities* towards one or more Member States is to be determined on the basis of all relevant circumstances, including factors such as the use of a language or a currency generally used in that Member State, the availability of an app in the national app store or the possibility of ordering goods or services.⁴⁹⁵

While the *service providers* are free to choose in which Member State they designate their *designated establishment* or their *legal representative*,⁴⁹⁶ the addressee of *service providers* established in the Union with legal personality is to be a *designated establishment*,⁴⁹⁷ while other *service providers* are to appoint a *legal representative* in a Member State taking part in the judicial cooperation instruments referred to in Article 1(2) eEvidence Directive.⁴⁹⁸ The reason for requiring the *legal representative* to be appointed in these Member States is that neither Denmark nor Ireland participate in the judicial cooperation instruments adopted under Title V, Chapter 4, of the TFEU. If the choice of the Member State for *legal representative* had been left solely to the other *service providers*, the effectiveness of the eEvidence Directive would have been put at risk. However, while Denmark will neither be bound by nor subject to the application of the eEvidence Regulation,⁴⁹⁹ Ireland has notified its wish to take part in the adoption and application of the eEvidence Regulation.⁵⁰⁰

11.3.2.3. Impact of the eEvidence Package on Future Criminal Investigations

⁴⁸⁹ Defined in Art. 2(5) eEvidence Directive as „*an establishment with legal personality designated in writing by a service provider established in a Member State taking part in a legal instrument referred to in Art. 1(2), for the purposes referred to in Art. 1(1) and Art. 3(1)*“.

⁴⁹⁰ Defined in Art. 2(6) eEvidence Directive as “*a natural or legal person appointed in writing by a service provider not established in a Member State taking part in a legal instrument referred to in Art. 1(2), for the purposes referred to in Art. 1(1) and Art. 3(1)*”.

⁴⁹¹ Art. 1(1) and Art. 3(1) eEvidence Directive.

⁴⁹² Art. 2(2) eEvidence Directive.

⁴⁹³ Art. 2(3) eEvidence Directive.

⁴⁹⁴ Points (a) and (b) in Art. 2(2) and (3) eEvidence Directive.

⁴⁹⁵ Rec. (11) eEvidence Directive.

⁴⁹⁶ Rec. (13) eEvidence Directive.

⁴⁹⁷ Art. 3(1)(a) eEvidence Directive.

⁴⁹⁸ Art. 3(1)(b) and (c) eEvidence Directive.

⁴⁹⁹ Rec. (101) eEvidence Regulation.

⁵⁰⁰ Rec. (100) eEvidence Regulation.

Together, the eEvidence Regulation and the eEvidence Directive (eEvidence Package) offer several improvements for future cybercrime investigations. *First*, by moving away from considering data location as a determining connecting factor in favour of relying on the economic presence of *service providers*, the eEvidence Package has the potential to overcome key challenges currently encountered in establishing jurisdiction, and proves to be fit for modern technologies such as the cloud, which transcend traditional territorial borders. *Second*, the eEvidence Package creates a direct route to the relevant *service provider*, thus avoiding the additional step of traditional MLA procedures where the judicial authority of the foreign country needs to be involved. This potentially shortens the overall timeframe as well as the administrative burden. *Third*, the eEvidence Package creates a mandatory framework introducing short deadlines⁵⁰¹, enforcement mechanisms⁵⁰² and penalties⁵⁰³ for non-compliance. *Finally*, the eEvidence package includes five clear and user-friendly forms in its annexes,⁵⁰⁴ thus standardising the channels for cooperation.

The legislative processes of the eEvidence Regulation as well as of the eEvidence Directive are officially still pending until their final versions will be published in the Official Journal of the EU.⁵⁰⁵ While both, the eEvidence Regulation⁵⁰⁶ and the eEvidence Directive⁵⁰⁷ will enter into force 20 days after publication in the Official Journal of the EU, the eEvidence Regulation will become applicable after 36 months⁵⁰⁸ and the eEvidence Directive requires Member States to bring into force the laws, regulations and administrative provisions necessary to comply with the eEvidence Directive within 30 months⁵⁰⁹, after which *service providers* in that Member State have further 6 months to designate their legal representative or designated establishment.⁵¹⁰ As a consequence, the new legal framework of the final eEvidence Package will be fully operational three years after publication in the Official Journal of the EU.

Up until then, the current EU legal framework consists of Union cooperation instruments in criminal matters, such as the Directive (EU) 2014/41 regarding the European Investigation Order in criminal matters⁵¹¹ and the Convention on Mutual Assistance in Criminal Matters

⁵⁰¹ 10 days, pursuant Art. 10(3) eEvidence Regulation, which become 8 hours in cases of emergency or 96 hours after a mandatory prior notification Art. 10(4) eEvidence Regulation.

⁵⁰² Art 16 eEvidence Regulation. In comparison, the EU-US MLAT will only include enforceable mechanisms when the executive agreement under the Cloud Act is signed. The CoE Convention on Cybercrime will become mandatory only once its Second Additional Protocol is signed by all Parties.

⁵⁰³ Art. 15 eEvidence Regulation.

⁵⁰⁴ The five forms are: the “European Production Order Certificate (EPOC) for the production of electronic evidence” in Annex I; the “European Preservation Order Certificate (EPOC-PR) for the preservation of electronic evidence” in Annex II, the “Information on the impossibility of executing an EPOC / EPOC-PR” in Annex III, the “Categories of offences referred to in Art. 12(1), point (d)” in Annex IV and the “Confirmation of issuance of a request for production following a European Preservation Order” in Annex V of the eEvidence Regulation.

⁵⁰⁵ Note that there are not just numerical, but significant content differences between the compromise texts for the eEvidence Regulation and the eEvidence Directive which were agreed upon in January 2023 and their text versions adopted by the European Parliament in its first reading on 13 June 2023.

⁵⁰⁶ Art. 34(1) eEvidence Regulation.

⁵⁰⁷ Art. 9 eEvidence Directive.

⁵⁰⁸ Art. 34(2) eEvidence Regulation.

⁵⁰⁹ Art. 7(1) eEvidence Directive.

⁵¹⁰ Art. 3(6) eEvidence Directive.

⁵¹¹ Directive 2014/41/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 3 April 2014 regarding the European Investigation Order in criminal matters, 1 May 2014, Official Journal of the EU L 130, p.1.

between the Member States of the European Union.⁵¹² Referring to national Member State law, the Directive (EU) 2014/41 itself neither defines the term *evidence* nor distinguishes different types of data.

11.3.3. Draft Police Cooperation Code

Most relevant for the CYCLOPES project and the international cooperation between LEAs in EU Member States, the European Commission presented a proposal for an EU Police Cooperation Code in December 2021. The EU Police Cooperation Code aims not only to enhance law enforcement cooperation across Member States but also to give EU police officers more modern tools for information exchange. For that purpose, the proposed EU Police Cooperation Code comprises three elements: (i) a Regulation on Automated Data Exchange for Police Cooperation (“Prüm II”)⁵¹³; (ii) a Directive on Information Exchange between MS LEAs⁵¹⁴; and (iii) a Council Recommendation on Operational Police Cooperation⁵¹⁵.

The Draft Prüm II Regulation is *lex specialis* to the Draft Directive on Information Exchange between MS LEAs and aims to facilitate automated data exchange between LEAs in different Member States and with Europol as the EU criminal information hub.⁵¹⁶ By introducing facial images, police records and driving licence data as additional categories data eligible to automated comparison, the Draft Prüm II Regulation proposes the introduction of a new infrastructure for standardised procedures identifying a match of core data.

As technological architecture for such queries, the Draft Prüm II Regulation envisages the creation of two central routers (the Prüm II router⁵¹⁷ for comparisons of biometric data and EPRIS⁵¹⁸ for comparisons of police records), each acting as a connecting infrastructure point between Member States. This hybrid approach between a decentralised and centralised solution avoids any data storage at central level by connecting national databases in each Member State to the central router instead of connecting to one another and establishing each router as message broker forwarding search transactions and replies to national systems, without creating new data processes, enlarging access rights or replacing national

⁵¹² Council Act of 29 May 2000 establishing in accordance with Article 34 TEU the Convention on Mutual Assistance in Criminal Matters between the Member States of the EU, 12 July 2000, Official Journal of the EC, 43 C 197, p. 1.

⁵¹³ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on automated data exchange for police cooperation (“Prüm II”), amending Council Decisions 2008/615/JHA and 2008/616/JHA and Regulations (EU) 2018/1726, 2019/817 and 2019/818 of the European Parliament and of the Council, COM/2021/784 final, 8 December 2021, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2021:784:FIN>.

⁵¹⁴ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on information exchange between law enforcement authorities of Member States, repealing Council Framework Decision 2006/960/JHA, COM/2021/782 final, 8 December 2021, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2021:782:FIN>.

⁵¹⁵ Proposal for a Council Recommendation on operational police cooperation, COM/2021/780 final, 8 December 2021, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2021:780:FIN>.

⁵¹⁶ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on information exchange between law enforcement authorities of Member States, repealing Council Framework Decision 2006/960/JHA, COM/2021/782 final, 8 December 2021, Explanatory Memorandum, p. 2.

⁵¹⁷ Art. 35 Draft Prüm II Regulation.

⁵¹⁸ Art. 42 Draft Prüm II Regulation.

databases.⁵¹⁹ The Router is to be developed and managed by European Union Agency for the Operational Management of Large-Scale Information Systems in the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice (eu-LISA).⁵²⁰

While the Draft Prüm II Regulation has already foreseen to confer implementing powers to the European Commission, in general, regarding the technical arrangements and specifications for automated searching procedures, the standards for data exchange and the data elements to be exchanged,⁵²¹ the General Approach of the Council includes an additional Art. 23a on principles for the exchange of facial images, in particular, introducing a key role of the European Commission in specifying (1) the relevant European or international standards for facial images exchange to be used by Member States and Europol, and (2) a minimum quality standard for the comparison of facial images.⁵²² The EU-Parliament has not yet adopted its position, but the LIBE Committee's Draft Report seems to agree with the need for inserting an additional Art. 23a on principles for the exchange of facial images granting a key role of the Commission as expressed in the Council's General Approach.⁵²³

Under the framework of the Draft Prüm II Regulation, Europol is envisioned not only to make biometric data obtained through third countries available to MS LEAs for automated comparisons, but also to automatically check its third country-sourced data against Member States' national databases.⁵²⁴ Furthermore, simultaneous queries with biometric data will be permitted in national databases of Member States as well as in the Europol database.⁵²⁵

According to Art. 23(1) Draft Prüm II Regulation, a comparison of facial images is initiated by a request for an automated search which includes the facial images to be compared and their national reference number⁵²⁶. The answer to such a request then includes not only the

⁵¹⁹ Art. 37 Draft Prüm II Regulation for the 'Prüm II router' and Art. 44 Draft Prüm II Regulation for EPRIS. See also: Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on information exchange between law enforcement authorities of Member States, repealing Council Framework Decision 2006/960/JHA, COM/2021/782 final, 8 December 2021, Explanatory Memorandum, p. 4.

⁵²⁰ Recital 23 Draft Prüm II Regulation highlighting the necessity, for this purpose to amend Regulation (EU) 2018/1726 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on the European Union Agency for the Operational Management of Large-Scale IT Systems in the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice (eu-LISA), and amending Regulation (EC) No 1987/2006 and Council Decision 2007/533/JHA and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1077/2011 (OJ L 295, 21.11.2018, p. 99).

⁵²¹ Recital 21 Draft Prüm II Regulation.

⁵²² Council of the EU, „Council adopts two general approaches and a recommendation to improve operational police cooperation and information exchange“, Press Release, 10 June 2022, linking to the General Approach of the Council on the Draft Prüm II Regulation, No. 9544/22, 31 May 2022, available at:

<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/06/10/council-adopts-recommendation-two-negotiating-mandates-improve-operational-police-cooperation-information-exchange/>. See also Art. 22(3)

Draft Prüm II Regulation regarding a minimum standard for facial recognition.

⁵²³ EU-Parliament, LIBE Committee, Draft Report on Draft Prüm II Regulation, 2021/0410(COD), 19 September 2022, Amendment 103, p. 53; available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/LIBE-PR-736469_EN.pdf.

⁵²⁴ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on information exchange between law enforcement authorities of Member States, repealing Council Framework Decision 2006/960/JHA, COM/2021/782 final, 8 December 2021, Explanatory Memorandum, p. 4.

⁵²⁵ Art. 37(1) Draft Prüm II Regulation for simultaneous searches in all or selected databases of Member States or Europol regarding facial images and Art. 42(2)(a) Draft Prüm II Regulation regarding police reports.

⁵²⁶ According to Art. 23 Draft Prüm II Regulation, the national „reference number“ is a combination of (a) a reference number allowing Member States, in case of a match, to retrieve further data and other information in their databases for sharing, and (b) a code to indicate the Member State which holds the facial images.

matching facial images,⁵²⁷ but also their national reference number⁵²⁸ and code⁵²⁹ in the requested Member State, Art. 23(2) Draft Prüm II Regulation. While the European Commission’s proposal includes the obligation for Member States to allow national contact points of other Member States and Europol access to the “facial images” stored in their national databases⁵³⁰, the General Approach of the Council suggests to allow such access only to the “facial images reference data” so that an automated search can be conducted solely by “comparing facial images reference data”⁵³¹ and the Parliament’s Draft Report appears to agree with limiting access to only “facial images reference data”⁵³².

This delta in the potential wording for a future Prüm II Regulation mirrors the delta regarding the scope of Member State’s obligation to include facial images in their national databases: While the European Commission’s proposal included the obligation for Member States to ensure the availability of facial images from their national databases established for the prevention, detection and investigation of criminal offences⁵³³ and Parliament’s Draft Report seems to agree with this requirement merely limiting it to facial images of suspects and convicted persons⁵³⁴, the General Approach of the Council suggests to reduce this obligation to ensuring such availability only for the “facial images reference data”⁵³⁵.

Any matches resulting from a query in requested Member States’ databases and Europol data shall be sent back in an automated manner to the router⁵³⁶ which then ranks the replies in accordance with the score of the correspondence between the biometric data used for querying and the biometric data stored in the Member States’ databases and Europol data⁵³⁷. The list of matching facial images and their scores are automatically returned by the router⁵³⁸ and the result of a successful automatic search is to be followed by the exchange of core data within a tight deadline⁵³⁹. Whereas the European Commission’s proposal set a deadline of “within 24 hours”⁵⁴⁰, the General Approach of the Council suggested to extend this deadline to “within 72

⁵²⁷ Art. 24(2)(f) Draft Prüm II Regulation.

⁵²⁸ Art. 24(2)(e) Draft Prüm II Regulation.

⁵²⁹ Art. 24(2)(d) Draft Prüm II Regulation.

⁵³⁰ Art. 22(1) Draft Prüm II Regulation.

⁵³¹ Art. 22(1) in the General Approach of the Council on the Draft Prüm II Regulation, No. 9544/22, 31 May 2022, adopted on 10 June 2022, available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/06/10/council-adopts-recommendation-two-negotiating-mandates-improve-operational-police-cooperation-information-exchange/>

⁵³² EU-Parliament, LIBE Committee, Draft Report on Draft Prüm II Regulation, 2021/0410(COD), 19 September 2022, Amendment 98, p. 51; available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/LIBE-PR-736469_EN.pdf.

⁵³³ Art. 21(1) Draft Prüm II Regulation.

⁵³⁴ EU-Parliament, LIBE Committee, Draft Report on Draft Prüm II Regulation, 2021/0410(COD), 19 September 2022, Amendment 95, p. 49; available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/LIBE-PR-736469_EN.pdf.

⁵³⁵ Art. 21(1) in the General Approach of the Council on the Draft Prüm II Regulation, No. 9544/22, 31 May 2022, adopted on 10 June 2022, available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/06/10/council-adopts-recommendation-two-negotiating-mandates-improve-operational-police-cooperation-information-exchange/>

⁵³⁶ Art. 37(3) Draft Prüm II Regulation. Parliament’s Draft Report suggests to add that requesting Member State shall be notified in an automated manner where there is no match: EU-Parliament, LIBE Committee, Draft Report on Draft Prüm II Regulation, 2021/0410(COD), 19 September 2022, Amendment 131, p. 64; available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/LIBE-PR-736469_EN.pdf.

⁵³⁷ Art. 37(4) Draft Prüm II Regulation.

⁵³⁸ Art. 37(5) Draft Prüm II Regulation.

⁵³⁹ Art. 47 Draft Prüm II Regulation.

⁵⁴⁰ Art. 47(1) Draft Prüm II Regulation.

hours” and to enumerate in detail the conditions and the path (“via the router”) of such exchange of core data⁵⁴¹. In contrast, Parliament’s Draft Report appears to agree with the shorter deadline of 24 hours as default, but suggests to extend this deadline to 72 hours where a judicial authorisation is required under national law.⁵⁴²

It is very interesting to note that Art. 48 Draft Prüm II Regulation establishes the platform Secure Information Exchange Network Application (SIENA)⁵⁴³ as the default system for any exchange between MS LEAs and with Europol outside the scope of the Draft Prüm II Regulation.

⁵⁴¹ Art. 47(1) in the General Approach of the Council on the Draft Prüm II Regulation, No. 9544/22, 31 May 2022, adopted on 10 June 2022, available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2022/06/10/council-adopts-recommendation-two-negotiating-mandates-improve-operational-police-cooperation-information-exchange/>

⁵⁴² EU-Parliament, LIBE Committee, Draft Report on Draft Prüm II Regulation, 2021/0410(COD), 19 September 2022, Amendment 156, p. 73 et seq.; available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/LIBE-PR-736469_EN.pdf.

⁵⁴³ Europol, „Secure Information Exchange Network Application (SIENA)“: <https://www.europol.europa.eu/operations-services-and-innovation/services-support/information-exchange/secure-information-exchange-network-application-siena>.

12. Evolving Regulation on Artificial Intelligence

This chapter takes a closer look at the regulatory framework for artificial intelligence (AI) proposed by the European Commission in April 2021 and provides a first analysis how this future regulatory framework will apply to tools and systems which could be used in the course of cybercrime investigations. In their fight against cybercrime, LEAs have to search and scan the surface web and the dark web for evidence and the sheer amount of data renders the use of aiding tools a necessity. The more advanced an investigative tool is, the more helpful it could become for cybercrime investigators. Investigative tools and systems can be designed to provide technical solutions for LEAs which include the processing of Big Data, machine learning, artificial intelligence as well as predictive and visual analytics. Such technological solutions aim to improve the handling of intelligence and investigation workflows through extensive content acquisition, information extraction and fusion, knowledge management and enrichment.

In view of the double-edged effect such advanced tools and systems bring with them in that the same elements and techniques that power the socio-economic benefits of AI can also bring about new risks or negative consequences for individuals or the society,⁵⁴⁴ the European Commission proposed a legislative package addressing both of these policy dimensions of AI.⁵⁴⁵ In an effort to strengthen AI uptake, investment and innovation across the EU, the European Commission devised a Coordinated Plan on AI.⁵⁴⁶ Addressing the potential risks AI poses to safety and fundamental rights, the European Commission presented the proposal for a Regulation laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Draft AI Act).⁵⁴⁷ As first-ever legal framework on AI, the Artificial Intelligence Act is complemented by a proposal for a Regulation on Machinery Products⁵⁴⁸ adapting safety rules to increase users' trust in the new, versatile generation of products.

This chapter is dedicated to explain the key features of the Draft AI Act and their impact on future cybercrime investigations. For that purpose, the objectives and the risk-based approach of the Draft AI Act (section 12.1. below) are outlined first. Then it is examined how the Draft AI Act classifies and regulates investigative tools (section 12.2. below) which are considered and potentially suggested for use at LEAs in the course of the CYCLOPES project. Lastly, the

⁵⁴⁴ Commission, Communication: Fostering a European approach to artificial intelligence, COM(2021) 205 final, 21 April 2021, p. 1.

⁵⁴⁵ Starting with the launch of the European AI strategy in April 2018, the Commission's two-pronged policy has been to make the EU a world-class hub for AI, while ensuring that AI is human-centric and trustworthy. See Commission, White Paper on Artificial Intelligence - A European approach to excellence and trust, COM(2020) 65 final, 19 February 2020, setting out as vision for AI in Europe: an ecosystem of excellence and an ecosystem of trust for AI.

⁵⁴⁶ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts, COM(2021) 206 final, 21 April 2021.

⁵⁴⁷ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts, COM(2021) 206 final, 21 April 2021.

⁵⁴⁸ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on machinery products, COM(2021) 202 final, 21 April 2021.

current stage of the legislative process for a future Artificial Intelligence Act is pointed out (section 12.3. below).

12.1. Objectives and Approach of Draft AI Act

In general, the proposed regulatory framework for AI strives to achieve *four specific objectives*: (i) ensure that AI systems are safe and respect existing law on fundamental rights and Union values; (ii) ensure legal certainty; (iii) enhance governance and effective enforcement of existing law on fundamental rights and safety; and (iv) facilitate the development of a single market for lawful, safe and trustworthy AI applications.⁵⁴⁹ For this purpose, the Draft AI Act sets harmonised rules for the development, placement and use of AI systems in the EU. The Draft AI Act recognises that AI systems vary by characteristic as well as by risk and includes prohibitions and a conformity assessment system adapted from EU product safety law.

The *risk-based approach* of the Draft AI Act allows to distinguish four different risk categories regarding AI practices:

- *unacceptable risks* (section 12.2.2. below):
Title II of the Draft AI Act *prohibits* certain particularly harmful AI practices and places *specific restrictions and safeguards* on law enforcement's use of remote biometric identification systems.⁵⁵⁰
- *high risks* (section 12.2.3. below):
Title III of the Draft AI Act requires AI practices posing a *high-risk*⁵⁵¹ to the health and safety or fundamental rights of individuals to comply with a set of horizontal mandatory requirements for trustworthy AI⁵⁵² and follow conformity assessment procedures⁵⁵³. Complementing these technological requirements, Title III of the Draft AI Act also sets out obligations on each and every provider and user of a *high-risk AI system* to ensure safety and respect for fundamental rights throughout the entire lifecycle of such an AI system.⁵⁵⁴
- *limited risks* (section 12.2.4. below):
Title IV of the Draft AI Act requires users and providers of AI tools posing a *limited risk* to meet specific transparency obligations.
- *minimal risks*:
Title IX of the Draft AI Act encourages providers of AI tools involving a *minimal risk* to draw up codes of conduct fostering the voluntarily application of the requirements for trustworthy AI.⁵⁵⁵

⁵⁴⁹ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts, COM(2021) 206 final, 21 April 2021, p. 3.

⁵⁵⁰ Art. 5 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁵¹ Art. 6 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁵² Art. 8(1) Draft AI Act demanding compliance with all requirements of Chapter 2 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁵³ Art. 43 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁵⁴ See Artt. 16 – 29 Draft AI Act (Chapter 3).

⁵⁵⁵ Art. 69 Draft AI Act.

The Draft AI Act's risk methodology reveals that the requirements for trustworthy AI set out in its Chapter 2 are a crucial feature for AI systems in the EU. This set of specifically designed requirements echoes the criteria elaborated in the H-LEG's "Ethical Guidelines for Trustworthy AI"⁵⁵⁶ which are examined in detail in chapter 14. below. Chapter 2 of the Draft AI Act requires the operation of a risk management system,⁵⁵⁷ the use of high-quality datasets,⁵⁵⁸ the establishment of appropriate documentation⁵⁵⁹ to enhance traceability,⁵⁶⁰ the sharing of adequate information with the user,⁵⁶¹ the design and implementation of appropriate human oversight measures,⁵⁶² and the achievement of the highest standards in terms of robustness, safety, cybersecurity and accuracy.⁵⁶³

12.2. Application to Tools for Cybercrime Investigations

The applicability of the Draft AI Act to tools and systems considered for use in cybercrime investigations hinges on the question whether such a tool or system constitutes an AI system.

12.2.1. Scope of the AI Act

Art. 3(1) Draft AI Act defines an "AI system" as software that can, for a given set of human-defined objectives, generate outputs such as content, predictions, recommendations or decisions influencing the environments they interact with. Further, the software has to be developed with at least one of the techniques and approaches listed in Annex I which contains (a) machine learning approaches, (b) logic- and knowledge-based approaches, and (c) statistical approaches, Bayesian estimation, search and optimisation methods.

This definition of an AI system is technology-neutral and, according to Art. 4 Draft AI Act, open to be updated by the European Commission in line with (future) market and technological developments on the basis of characteristics that are similar to the techniques and approaches listed in Annex I. This definition is also significantly broader than the definition of AI elaborated by the High-Level Expert Group on AI in 2018,⁵⁶⁴ because the definition suggested in the Draft AI Act appears to lack the element of unpredictability as well as the element of a black box effect. Therefore, this definition of AI appears to comprise not only deterministic software but also traditional expert systems.⁵⁶⁵

⁵⁵⁶ AI H-LEG, "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI", 8 April 2019.

⁵⁵⁷ Art. 9 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁵⁸ Art. 10 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁵⁹ Art. 11 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁶⁰ Art. 12 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁶¹ Art. 13 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁶² Art. 14 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁶³ Art. 15 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁶⁴ High-Level Expert Group on AI, "A Definition of AI: Main Capabilities and Disciplines", 8 April 2019, page 6.

⁵⁶⁵ Spindler, "Der Vorschlag der EU-Kommission für eine Verordnung zur Regulierung von Künstlicher Intelligenz", *Computer und Recht* 2021, page 361.

In the context of cybercrime investigations, advanced Big Data solutions could be available for mining and analysing electronic data gathered from multiple sources on the surface web and the dark web which could either standardise the management of potentially incriminating data or could avoid duplicate processing and enhance collaboration amongst national LEAs within the EU, or even both.

Advanced investigative tools could be able to analyse collected data in terms of visual, audio and text information using AI technologies to produce structured and validated information about its content.

Advanced forensic analysis tools could provide capabilities for cybercrime-specific content analysis and classification, content-based geo-localisation and the creation of evidence graphs to connect cases. By applying audio-visual analysis technique capabilities to cybercrime investigations, advanced investigative tools could provide the option to extract, cluster and automatically tag and match shapes and objects from pictures and videos (e.g., buildings, specific objects that facilitate the geolocation of a picture or the identification of a suspect).

Advanced investigative tools could also serve to introduce enhanced predictive analytics to LEAs allowing them to determine patterns and predict trends and threats filling the gap between the strategic and operational activities towards identifying suitable tactics and techniques as well as assisting in defining and deriving crime-relevant indicators corresponding to criminal behaviours.

As a consequence, any of these advanced investigative tools qualifies as “AI system” within the meaning of the Draft AI Act.

12.2.2. AI Practices with Unacceptable Risks

The Draft AI Act contains four prohibited AI practices. While two AI practices take advantage of unacceptable forms of manipulation (subliminal techniques and exploitation of vulnerabilities) causing physical or psychological harm,⁵⁶⁶ one AI practice relies on unacceptable forms of social scoring for the evaluation of the trustworthiness of individuals which cause detrimental treatment⁵⁶⁷ and all three of these AI practices are prohibited in their entirety.

The fourth prohibited AI practice concerns the use of ‘real-time’ and ‘remote’ biometric identification systems and provides an exception for law enforcement. If accompanied by an independent authorisation regime, LEAs can make use of such biometric identification systems, provided such use is strictly necessary for one of the following objectives:⁵⁶⁸

- (i) the targeted search for specific potential victims of crime, including missing children;

⁵⁶⁶ Art. 5(1)(a) and (b) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁶⁷ Art. 5(1)(c) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁶⁸ Art. 5(1)(d) Draft AI Act.

- (ii) the prevention of a specific, substantial and imminent threat to the life or physical safety of natural persons or of a terrorist attack;
- (iii) the detection, localisation, identification or prosecution of a perpetrator or suspect of a crime with a maximum sentence of at least 3 years that would allow for the issuing of a European Arrest Warrant.

Regarding the use of advanced investigative tools in the course of cybercrime investigations it is important to highlight two aspects: *First*, this strict regime concerns only ‘real-time’ identification tools and systems that capture, compare, and identify ‘instantaneously, near-instantaneously or in any event without a significant delay’⁵⁶⁹. Consequently, tools and systems offering ‘post’ identification by, for example, biometrically analysing footage after an event, or identifying individuals after-the-fact are regulated by the strict regime of Art. 5 Draft AI Act. *Second*, online spaces do not qualify as ‘publicly accessible spaces’ within the meaning of Art. 3(39) Draft AI Act because they are not physical spaces.⁵⁷⁰ Consequently, live biometric identification on e.g. video streams remain unaffected by the strict regime of Art. 5 Draft AI Act and qualify as *high-risk AI system*.⁵⁷¹

12.2.3. AI Practices with High Risks

Title III of the Draft AI Act governs AI systems that pose ‘*high-risk*’ to ‘health, safety and fundamental rights’.⁵⁷² Many advanced investigative tools and systems will fall under the definition of a *high-risk AI system* established in Art. 6(2) Draft AI Act in connection with Annex III No. 1 listing any AI system for remote biometric identification of natural persons⁵⁷³ as well as No. 6 regarding the area of law enforcement listing explicitly AI systems intended to be used by LEAs for:

- the evaluation of the reliability of evidence,⁵⁷⁴
- profiling in the course of an investigation,⁵⁷⁵ and
- Big Data applications⁵⁷⁶.

These *AI systems* intended to be used in the law enforcement context have been classified as *high-risk* because their accuracy, reliability and transparency is particularly important to avoid adverse impacts, retain public trust and ensure accountability and effective redress.⁵⁷⁷

As *high-risk AI system*, an advanced investigative tool or system has to be registered in the EU database for *stand-alone high-risk AI systems* established by Art. 60 Draft AI Act before

⁵⁶⁹ Art. 3(37) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁷⁰ Recital 9 sentence 3 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁷¹ Art. 6(1)

⁵⁷² Recital 43 and Art. 7(2) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁷³ ‘real time’ and ‘post’.

⁵⁷⁴ Annex III No. 6(d) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁷⁵ Annex III No. 6(f) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁷⁶ Annex III No. 6 (g) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁷⁷ Recital 38 sentence 4 Draft AI Act.

the tool or system can be placed on the market or put into service.⁵⁷⁸ For such a registration, a *high-risk AI system* has to comply with the seven mandatory requirements established in Title III. Chapter 2 of the Draft AI Act:

- (1) the operation of a *risk management system*,⁵⁷⁹
- (2) the use of *high-quality datasets*,⁵⁸⁰
- (3) the establishment of *appropriate documentation*,⁵⁸¹
- (4) the inclusion of *logging capabilities* to enhance traceability,⁵⁸²
- (5) the sharing of *adequate information* with the end-user,⁵⁸³
- (6) the design and implementation of *appropriate human oversight measures*,⁵⁸⁴ and
- (7) the achievement of the highest standards in terms of *robustness, safety, cybersecurity and accuracy*.⁵⁸⁵

For such a registration, the *high-risk AI system* has to undergo a mandatory conformity assessment procedure.⁵⁸⁶ Once the conformity assessment has demonstrated the *high-risk AI system's* compliance with the requirements set out in Title III. Chapter 2 Draft AI Act, an *EU declaration of conformity* can be drawn up⁵⁸⁷ and a *CE marking of conformity* can be affixed⁵⁸⁸.

The provider of a *high-risk AI system* has to fulfil all obligations established in Art. 16 Draft AI Act. These obligations serve to ensure the compliance of the *high-risk AI system* with the Draft AI Act throughout its lifecycle. In addition to ensuring that the *high-risk AI system* is compliant with the requirements set out in Title III. Chapter 2 Draft AI Act,⁵⁸⁹ it is also necessary to:

- put in place a *quality management system* in accordance with Art. 17 Draft AI Act,⁵⁹⁰
- provide the *technical documentation* of the *high-risk AI system*,⁵⁹¹ and
- keep the *logs* automatically generated by the *high-risk AI system*.⁵⁹²

According to Art. 29(1) Draft AI Act, the user of a *high-risk AI system* is merely obliged to use such systems in accordance with the instructions of use accompanying the systems. Whether the user organises its own resources and activities for the purpose of implementing the human oversight measures indicated by the provider, is left to the user's discretion.⁵⁹³ Only to the

⁵⁷⁸ Art. 51 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁷⁹ Art. 9 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁸⁰ Art. 10 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁸¹ Art. 11 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁸² Art. 12 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁸³ Art. 13 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁸⁴ Art. 14 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁸⁵ Art. 15 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁸⁶ Art. 19(1) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁸⁷ Art. 48 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁸⁸ Art. 49 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁸⁹ Art. 16(a) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁹⁰ Art. 16(b) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁹¹ Art. 16(c) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁹² Art. 16(d) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁹³ Art. 29(2) Draft AI Act.

extent that the user exercises control over the input data, the user shall ensure that the input data is relevant in view of the intended purpose of the *high-risk AI system*.⁵⁹⁴ However, users have the obligation to monitor the operation of the *high-risk AI system* on the basis of the instructions of use and must suspend the use and notify the provider or distributor in cases of serious incidents or malfunctions and in case a risk at national level is posed.⁵⁹⁵

12.2.4. AI Practices with Limited Risks

Title IV of the Draft AI Act lays out three transparency obligations that apply to all AI systems that meet their criteria.⁵⁹⁶ While two of these transparency obligations address the user of an AI system and the third its providers, all three obligations contain exemption for the AI system's use by law enforcement.

Providers of AI systems intended to interact with natural persons (= 'bot' applications) must design their AI systems so that individuals are informed they are interacting with a bot, unless it would be contextually obvious that individuals are interacting with a bot, or if the bot use is authorised by law "to detect, prevent, investigate and prosecute criminal offences".⁵⁹⁷ In the context of cybercrime investigations, it is important to highlight that this criminal prevention exemption does not apply to systems that help the reporting of crime.

Users of an AI system for emotion recognition or a biometric categorisation must inform exposed individuals of the operation of such AI system, except in the case of biometric categorisation permitted by law to be used for crime prevention.⁵⁹⁸

Users of AI systems that generate or manipulate image, audio or video content that "*appreciably resembles existing persons, objects, places or other entities or events*" and would falsely appear to a person to be "*authentic or truthful ('deep fake')*" are required to disclose the artificial nature of the resulting content. An exemption exists for the use by law enforcement "*to detect, prevent, investigate and prosecute criminal offences*".⁵⁹⁹

12.3. Current Stage of the Legislative Process

The legislative process for a future Artificial Intelligence Act is currently still pending and has reached the stage of trilogue negotiations in June 2023. After the proposal of the Draft AI Act by the European Commission in April 2021 which is referred to in this section as Draft AI Act (COM), the Council of the EU adopted its General Approach⁶⁰⁰ to the future Artificial

⁵⁹⁴ Art. 29(3) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁹⁵ Art. 29(4) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁹⁶ Art. 52 Draft AI Act.

⁵⁹⁷ Art. 52(1) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁹⁸ Art. 52(2) Draft AI Act.

⁵⁹⁹ Art. 52(3) sentence 2 Draft AI Act.

⁶⁰⁰ Council, General Approach AI Act, no. 15698/22 on interinstitutional file 2021/0106(COD), 6 December 2022, available at: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CONSIL:ST_15698_2022_INIT&from=EN.

Intelligence Act on 6 December 2022 which is referred to in this section as Draft AI Act (COUNCIL). The European Parliament adopted its position in the first reading of the Draft AI Act (COM) on 14 June 2023 which is referred to in this section as Draft AI Act (PARL).

In the trilogue stage, representatives of the three main institutions in the Ordinary Legislative Procedure⁶⁰¹ negotiate the three different positions regarding a future Artificial Intelligence Act in order to reach a provisional agreement⁶⁰² on a text acceptable to both, the Council and the Parliament. The current Spanish Presidency of the Council of the EU⁶⁰³ has declared as top priority for its current term to reach a political agreement on the future Artificial Intelligence Act by November 2023.⁶⁰⁴ However, the complexity and multitude of diverging positions between the Commission, the Parliament and the Council appear to render any such agreement unlikely before early 2024. The Draft AI Act (PARL) alone consists in total of 771 amendments to the Draft AI Act (COM)⁶⁰⁵ which had been tabled in the final joint Report⁶⁰⁶ by the IMCO Committee and the LIBE Committee in May 2023.

From a bird's eye perspective, all three positions seem in line to regulate the use of AI systems in the EU based on a risk-based approach distinguishing between four different risk categories regarding AI practices. The key differences already start with the definition of the term "AI system"⁶⁰⁷ and continue with the classification as "high-risk AI system"⁶⁰⁸. In addition, the Council suggests to introduce a specific set of rules concerning "general purpose AI

⁶⁰¹ Art. 294 TFEU requires representatives of the European Commission, the European Parliament and the Council of Ministers.

⁶⁰² European Parliament, "Interinstitutional negotiations for the adoption of EU legislation", available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/olp/en/interinstitutional-negotiations>.

⁶⁰³ Spain has taken over the rotating presidency of the EU Council of Ministers on 1 July 2023.

⁶⁰⁴ Bertuzzi, „AI Act enters final phase of EU legislative process“, Euractiv, 14 June 2023, available at: <https://www.euractiv.com/section/artificial-intelligence/news/ai-act-enters-final-phase-of-eu-legislative-process/>. Bertuzzi, „AI Act: Spanish presidency sets out options on key topics of negotiation“, Euractiv, 3 July 2023, available at: <https://www.euractiv.com/section/artificial-intelligence/news/ai-act-spanish-presidency-sets-out-options-on-key-topics-of-negotiation/>.

⁶⁰⁵ European Parliament, „AI Act: a step closer to the first rules on Artificial Intelligence“, Press Release, Ref.: 20230505IPR84904, 11 May 2023, available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20230505IPR84904/ai-act-a-step-closer-to-the-first-rules-on-artificial-intelligence>. The Draft Compromise Amendments adopted on 16 May 2023 are available at: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/resources/library/media/20230516RES90302/20230516RES90302.pdf>.

⁶⁰⁶ IMCO Committee/LIBE Committee, joint Report on the proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on laying down harmonised rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act), A9-0188/2023, 22 May 2023, available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2023-0188_EN.pdf.

⁶⁰⁷ Whereas the Council suggests in Art. 3(1) Draft AI Act (Council) to narrow the definition of "AI system" by requiring "elements of autonomy" distinguishing it from simpler software systems, The European Parliament suggests in Art. 3(1) Draft AI Act (PARL) to require "varying levels of autonomy" for AI systems which may be used as stand-alone software system, integrated into a physical product (*embedded*), to serve the functionality of a physical product without being integrated therein (*non-embedded*) or as an component of a larger system, Rec. (6) and (6b) Draft AI Act (PARL).

⁶⁰⁸ Both, Council and Parliament suggest to include an additional requirement for classifying an AI system as *high-risk*: According to 6(3) Draft AI Act (Council) AI systems listed in Annex III are not classified as *high-risk* when their output is purely accessory and therefore not likely to lead to "a significant risk to the health, safety or fundamental rights", while pursuant to Art. 6(2) Draft AI Act (PARL) the AI systems listed in Annex III are considered *high-risk* only if they pose "a significant risk of harm to the health, safety, or fundamental rights of natural persons".

systems”.⁶⁰⁹ Furthermore, the Parliament suggests, for example, to introduce not only an “European Artificial Intelligence Office” as new EU body with a multitude of tasks,⁶¹⁰ but also a specific regime for “foundation models”⁶¹¹ and especially a mandatory Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment (FRIA) for *high-risk AI systems*⁶¹² while specifying the transparency obligations concerning *limited risk AI systems*⁶¹³.

Against this background, it is impossible to predict the outcome of the trilogue negotiations for a future Artificial Intelligence Act, at this stage. However, if a future Artificial Intelligence Act is agreed upon, then its impact on cybercrime investigations will be massive. For a start, the future definition of AI systems will determine which advanced investigative tools used in cybercrime investigations will be regulated by the future Artificial Intelligence Act. Depending on the *risk-based approach* of the future Artificial Intelligence Act, the criteria distinguishing the four different risk categories (*prohibited, high-risk, limited risk* and *minimal risk*) regarding AI practices will allocate each advanced investigative tool potentially used in a cybercrime investigation to a specific risk category with its specific requirements not only for its *provider* and *distributor* and *importer*, but also for the LEA as *user*. Only an advanced investigative tool which is in compliance with the requirements of the future Artificial Intelligence Act will be eligible for LEAs to use in general and particularly in cybercrime investigations.

⁶⁰⁹ Defined in Art. 3(1b) Draft AI Act (Council) as *AI systems* which are „intended by the provider to perform generally applicable functions“, and regulated in a newly inserted Title IA. consisting of Artt. 4a, 4b and 4c Draft AI Act (Council).

⁶¹⁰ Established in Art. 56 Draft AI Act (PARL), the AI Office, for example: (1) needs to be consulted by the Commission regarding additions and modifications to and deletions from Annex III, Art. 7(2a) Draft AI Act (PARL); (2) can request the Commission to reassess the risk categorization of Annex III, Art. 7a(2b) Draft AI Act (PARL); (3) receives reasoned notifications concerning certain AI systems which are intended for use in two or more Member States, Art. 6(2a) Draft AI Act (PARL); (4) brings together national and international metrology and benchmarking authorities and provide non-binding guidance to address the technical aspects of measuring the appropriate levels of accuracy and robustness, Art. 15((1a) Draft AI Act (PARL); and (5) needs to be consulted by the Commission when issuing a standardization request, Art. 40((1a) AI Act (PARL).

⁶¹¹ Defined in Art. 3(1c) Draft AI Act (PARL) as „an AI system model that is trained on broad data at scale, is designed for generality of output, and can be adapted to a wide range of distinctive tasks“ and regulated in Art. 28b Draft AI Act (PARL).

⁶¹² Art. 29a Draft AI Act (PARL).

⁶¹³ Art. 52 Draft AI Act (PARL).

13. Ethical Standard

An ethical standard does not refer just to the ethical requirements for LEAs and the methods that they utilise. Ethics is a broad subject that refers to the societal requirements surrounding technologies (such as AI, Web Crawlers etc.) but also the presence of data collation, societal views, the presence of rights (this could even be a visual lack of these factors to the public domain of rights and freedoms) which are instances that could affect the solidification of the implementation of a specific technology or the validity of deploying specific types of technologies into European society. This can be found to exacerbate the opinion on the presence of technology within policing, especially when most online LEA techniques in the cybercrime combat are ‘relatively low-tech.’⁶¹⁴ The societal issues develop as technology advances, such as through methods of Facial Recognition Systems and Advanced Automated Search Tools as these are systems that utilise Artificial Intelligence. The development of such automated systems via AI systems has been suggested to produce a bias or causing groups of individuals to be held in a different categorisation due to the large amount of collated data which can cause a disproportion.⁶¹⁵ These societal and ethical concerns lead to the question whether big-data collation could pose a risk to data-protection, especially in a Law Enforcement setting. The Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA) endorses the implementation of a set of bias reduction techniques that could significantly lower the risk of the possibilities when using big data analytic techniques.⁶¹⁶ These concerns, however, have been recognised by the European Union and therefore new legislative and legal grounding to combat bias and misunderstanding of Artificial Intelligence and other technologies in the digital sector is being produced.

In recent years, the development of ethics and societal standards have been integrated into the cybersecurity industry and investigations of serious crimes and other related incidents in the digital domain – especially concerning Digital Forensics. The ethical standard of the CYCLOPES network refers to Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) and practitioners who are required to act in an ethically and legally compliant manner during investigations to ensure that the combat against cybercrime is successful and effective when operating within a functioning European Society. The requirements of a developing ethical perception of cybercrime investigations have become the forefront of the European goal to protect its citizens via new Artificial Intelligence ethical requirements (*Draft AI Act 2021*). The protection of citizens calls for cybercrime investigations to take place, however, Digital Forensic Investigations must hold respect for the core elements of the functioning European Society and international regimes also. These core elements refer to Fundamental Rights & Human Rights when LEAs undertake cybercrime investigations that could possibly utilise methods that may infringe upon an individual’s rights as detailed previously in Section 9. The CYCLOPES network will provide technological capabilities that are ensured to respect the legislative environment and ethical

⁶¹⁴ See *Williams & Stephens* ‘Analysis of the ‘Open-Source Internet Research Tool’: A Usage Perspective from UK Law Enforcement. In International Symposium on Human Aspects of Information Security and Assurance’ 341-352 2021

⁶¹⁵ See Boyd and Crawford, ‘Critical Questions for Big Data.’ *Information, Communication & Society*. 15(5) 662-679 2012

⁶¹⁶ See Fundamental Rights Agency ‘Possible Way to Avoid Big Data Bias’ 2018
<https://fra.europa.eu/en/news/2018/4-possible-ways-avoid-big-data-bias>

requirements of the International and European Level treaties, regulations, directives, and guidelines.

A significant catalyst in the interest of Ethics in Digital Legal environment (including the setting which would affect LEAs) are the current Trustworthy AI Guidelines released in 2019. The introduction of the Draft Artificial Intelligence Act 2021 (*Proposal 2021/206*) sets a new environment for the toolkit of cybercrime investigation techniques in regard to how we utilise Artificial Intelligence into cybercrime and LEA intervention. The CYCLOPES network will ensure that the ethical practices that are provided improve the current conditions of a cybercrime investigation for LEAs and achieve the goal to bring safer and ethically robust technologies into society. The current Trustworthy AI Guidelines contain requirements for Artificial Intelligence systems that are deployed within the European Union; regardless of their soft law status. Once in force and applicable, the Artificial Intelligence Act will transpose most of the Trustworthy AI Guidelines' requirements into hard law and ensure that developers and users of Artificial Intelligence are bound by law and can be held more easily accountable for any wrongdoings. Factors that relate to societal developments and wants from the citizens when using new systems, especially in the field of Artificial Intelligence are the forefront of what constitutes appropriate practices within cybercrime investigations, plus, respecting the current law of the specific Member State. The digital legal environment is increasing in size and complexity at an exponential rate especially within Europe – which contains a fast growing metropolis of new regulations that are designed to improve the future of business and cybersecurity industries.

President *Ursula Von Der Leyen* set the direction of Europe's digital path, *Von Der Leyen's* European Commission statement referred to the future of the internet which commented on the importance of the internet being a 'safe place and trusted space for everyone, and to ensure that the Internet serves our individual freedom.'⁶¹⁷ This statement highlighted the requirement for digital technologies 'that have the potential to promote connectivity, democracy, peace, the rule of law and sustainable development' which also included the protection of fundamental freedoms and human rights.⁶¹⁸ The ethical standard across Europe is evolving, a new *European Declaration on Digital Rights in the Digital Decade* as discussed in section 3.3.2. above aims to ensure that society's core elements of fundamental rights, human rights and privacy are protected at all costs. This European Declaration intends to provide a catered approach to 'essential concepts, based on common European values, and serving as guidance for a human-centred, secure, inclusive, and open digital environment, where no one is left behind'.⁶¹⁹ The development of ethics in all areas of digital technology in Europe could find that an update to specific Digital Forensics *Codes of Ethics* is required by their Member State or partner of the consortium. The United Kingdom for example has specific '*Codes of Practice and Conduct*' for the '*Digital Forensics Services*.' This crown document

⁶¹⁷ European Commission a communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on Establishing a *European Declaration on Digital rights and principles for the Digital Decade*

⁶¹⁸ European Commission a communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on Establishing a European Declaration on Digital rights and principles for the Digital Decade

⁶¹⁹ European Commission a communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on Establishing a European Declaration on Digital rights and principles for the Digital Decade

provides ethical requirements of how LEAs within the UK should perform a digital investigation into a crime in any phase; ‘identification, capture, preservation, investigation, evaluation, reporting’.⁶²⁰ The limitations provided in these ethics guidelines determining how LEAs can constructively police and investigate crimes that require Digital Forensics in an ethical manner by ensuring that there is a ‘formal risk assessment method’ which requires that steps are taken to mitigate risks to any losses or harms (ethically, legally and physically). Codes of Ethics for Digital Forensics do not pertain exclusively to a European Model, however, there are international examples, such as the: *International Society of Forensic Computer Examiners (ISFCE)*. This international organization provides a certification for Digital Forensics tailored specifically towards Law Enforcement by providing a ‘strong code of ethics and professional responsibility for all certified individuals. The international element of this code of ethics can provide all members from any country ‘*integrity, professionalism, competence, quality and respect*’⁶²¹ can be satisfied for Digital Forensics users in an LEA (policing) or Cybersecurity setting.

The demand for further understanding of how specific areas of ethics have a presence within Digital Forensics (the specific use of technologies) is due to public concern hence the introduction of a plethora of precautionary steps to mitigate the risks of technology infringing upon European Citizen rights. Artificial Intelligence as a tool within Cybercrime Investigations is at the forefront of ethics due to the capabilities of upcoming Artificial Intelligence systems in the hands of Law Enforcement Agencies. The capabilities that are available to society can greatly benefit and protect safety through providing systems that can easily identify any individuals who pose a risk. Unfortunately, tabloid media only exposes the negative side of AI systems through popular culture portraying AI as negative. It has been shown that the media feels web crawlers for example are ‘*aggressive*’ and ‘*antagonising*’ as a form of scraping the Internet.⁶²² however, studies have shown that if data handling rules are followed then the public will accept technologies to protect society and hold confidence in their capabilities to protect their information.⁶²³ This causes lasting effects on what can be implemented without public rejection due to these perceptions, the concept of public uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence is developed in 14.1 which details the repressiveness of the public and how it can be mitigated. The ethical standard of cybercrime research and prevention should understand the societal factors of implementing technologies and the secondary requirement of ensuring public satisfaction of new systems; in any form.

The implications of Artificial Intelligence in an ethical and social perspective when operating within the cybercrime investigation and policing environment holds reference to each of the principles that were introduced and called upon in the Guidelines for Trustworthy AI (published in 2019). Chapter 14 dissects the Trustworthy AI guidelines and builds on the factors that pertain specifically to the Digital Forensic / Cybercrime investigation / Cybersecurity industry. The Europol and CENTRIC focused project “*Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence (AP4AI)*.” Also develops on the 2019 Trustworthy AI guidelines and shows a new perspective on how Artificial Intelligence can be assessed and assured for LEA use in the Internal Security

⁶²⁰ See *Forensic Science Regulator Codes of Practice and Conduct: Digital Forensic Services Vol 2*

⁶²¹ See *International Society of Forensic Computer Examiners*

⁶²² See *Skorup* ‘Cops scan social media to help assess your ‘Threat Rating’ Reuters, 2014

⁶²³ See European Commission ‘A European Strategy for Data’ 2021 <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data>

Domain. The elements of AP4AI can greatly impact the presence of Artificial Intelligence's ability to continue to be present in Digital Forensics and investigations for LEAs plus other technologies within a policing setting. The AP4AI framework could be an influential tool in ensuring that accountability in Artificial Intelligence can finally be defined appropriately (14.7).

The ethical pressures of providing a secure and safe investigation have been increased due to the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in police practice and their investigations, however, as detailed above the issues regarding privacy and data protection hold significant control in the ability to use specific tools and techniques. Privacy and the protection of sensitive information (including storing data) is an area upon which society are cautious regarding these factors. Cybercrime investigations lead to the storing of data which is normally the leading factor into ethical scrutiny as large quantities of stored data can cause public unrest.⁶²⁴ It has been highlighted in some instances that cybersecurity research has led to concerns around what data is relevant and holds 'future-use value.'⁶²⁵ This perspective, however, is changing as the requirement of LEAs operating within the cybersecurity remit is becoming more data protection and fundamental rights sighted to ensure that all individuals involved in the investigation process do not find themselves infringed upon. Information that is collated by LEAs and practitioners should ensure that the data they store should satisfy the necessity of storing and proportionality due to the basic requirements of *Regulation 2016/679*. In the context of data storage, providing limitations to data gives more control over how data controllers are required to interact with the data and the data subjects. In a cybersecurity and cybercrime investigations setting the collated data would be information that requires the ethical protection due to it being information regarding victims, witness and innocent suspects (until proven guilty); details of an incident could be sensitive and therefore require the protection and respect to their wishes regarding their personal information.⁶²⁶

It can be shown that cybercrime investigations through the complexities of Digital Forensics should ensure that practitioners and LEAs are aware that the recommendations for investigations will ensure a *privacy driven network for Law Enforcement Agencies that provides transparency and accountability in a diverse and fair society in all deployable technologies that are designed to protect the rights and freedoms of citizens of Europe during Digital Investigations*. The compliancy with this ethical standard will ensure that there is consistency throughout the deployment of new technologies in all forms. The benefit of creating consistency creates accountability for practitioners and developers as any deviation due to an inaccuracy in an ethical standard could be a legitimate form of defence for the inability to follow the projects ethical requirements, however, if those requirements were consistent, they would be accountable. The ethical standard protects the future of the project and the cybersecurity industry due to compatibility with fundamental rights and freedoms of citizens, therefore, making it paramount.

⁶²⁴ See Radwan 'Big Data Ethics: International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security '80-68 2021 19(1)

⁶²⁵ See Andrejevic and Gates 'Big Data Surveillance: Introduction' *Surveillance and Society* 184 2014 12(2)

⁶²⁶ See Lyle 'Risks Related to Illegal Content in Cybercrime and Cyberterrorism Research' In Akhgar *Combatting Cybercrime and Cyberterrorism: Challenges, Trends and Priorities* 2016 117-131

14. Trustworthy AI Principles

The implementation and integration of Artificial Intelligence into society, and ultimately law enforcement, requires an appropriate set of principles and standards to ensure there is a concision between good Artificial Intelligence system practices and compliance with Fundamental Rights and Human Rights of citizens in their respective jurisdiction. Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence systems should ensure the respect of fundamental rights as required by the European Union. Trustworthy AI has been a core goal of the European High-level Expert Group on AI (AI HLEG) which in 2019 the European Commission published its first report into the ethics of trustworthy AI. Since then, the current instrument for ensuring these factors is the upcoming Artificial Intelligence Regulation that has been produced by the European Union; Proposal 2021/01/06 for a “Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council on Laying down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain union legislative acts”.⁶²⁷ Recent work on the “Accountability Framework for Artificial Intelligence in the Security Domain”⁶²⁸ is also a credible framework to highlight the work of security practitioners in combatting cybercrime.

The principles detailed within this section, however, are shaped by the previously standardised Trustworthy AI Guidelines which take a strong ethical approach over how users of Artificial Intelligence should approach the implementation of artificial intelligence. Due to the sensitivity of information that can be used for training, collected by and output from specific forms of AI, the acknowledgement of oversight and the interactions of humans to ensure that these problems are not exacerbated must be detailed; including the technical robustness of Artificial Intelligence to provide a human and technical safety boundary. These factors are required to protect the fundamental rights of a user, specifically their data. In some circles, Artificial Intelligence already has a stigma of failing to provide the necessary protections of the rights of citizens; therefore, the Trustworthy AI Principles also function based on providing diversity, non-discrimination and fairness – this is to provide a neutral technology that does not produce an ethical or minority bias when in operation. Artificial Intelligence can be harnessed to improve society and protect citizens; however, Artificial Intelligence must be utilised in the sense that society is protected and minimise and mitigate against potential negative threats.

The guidelines for trustworthy AI were created for uniformity in the development and operation of Artificial Intelligence across all sectors which then ultimately provides a framework for accountability which can be developed from to find who can be held accountable when an incident occurs that effects one of these trustworthy principles. Accountability has become the forefront of discussion at the release of a new Artificial Intelligence proposal, therefore, the definition of how we see accountability in AI is developing into a more robust and transparent framework that contains a citizens-based approach⁶²⁹ into the development of Artificial

⁶²⁷ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonized rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union legislative acts, COM(2021) 206 final, 21 April 2021

⁶²⁸ Akgbar and others, Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence in the Internal Security Domain (February 2022)

⁶²⁹ Akgbar and others, Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence in the Internal Security Domain (February 2022)

Intelligence to ensure that there is a foundation of understanding for society to avoid any misconceptions of how Artificial Intelligence functions.

14.1. Human Agency & Oversight

Human Agency is the interaction between the user and the Artificial Intelligence, it has been detailed that some technologies could ‘harness shape and influence human behaviour.’⁶³⁰ Artificial Intelligence is an area of technology that contains a plethora of concerns for a lack of human control over specific technologies, this is due to the capabilities of Artificial Intelligence and its independent capabilities. It has been highlighted that due to the concerns of a lack of an input in automated decision making by humans there are now legal requirements of developers that have been enshrined via Directives and precedent in Case Law. Article 11(1) of *Directive 2016/680* finds that there is a binding requirement that:

*‘Member States shall provide for a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces an adverse legal effect concerning the data subject or significantly affects him or her, to be prohibited unless authorised by Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject and which provides appropriate safeguards for the rights and freedoms of the data subject, at least the right to obtain human intervention on the part of the controller.’*⁶³¹

The protection of a data subject’s rights is enshrined within law and are protected under GDPR. The United Kingdom ruled in the *English*⁶³² case of *R (Bridges) v Chief Constable of South Wales Police & Information Commissioner*⁶³³ that an automated facial recognition system that has been on trial within the UK known as “AFR Locate” demonstrated and implemented in South Wales was found to intervene against the Article 8 rights of the appellant. The United Kingdom implemented a mirror law of GDPR post Brexit (Data Protection Act 2018) which therefore highlighted that Section 64 (the mirror of Article 22) was infringed upon due to the South Wales Police failing to provide the appropriate data protection and equality impact assessments (both SWP assessments detailed that s64 of DPA was infringed upon and s.149(1) of the Equality Act did not demonstrate compliancy). S149(1) of the Equality Act refers to public authority in acts of discrimination, harassment, and victimisation which was found that this form of artificial intelligence was not permitted to be used. This created a precedent regarding Human Agency and the requirements of the Police when utilising Artificial Intelligence within the security domain. Exemptions, however, do apply while protecting society under Articles 11, 25 and 29 of Directive 2016/680, however, this is an EU Directive which does not fully hold its remit over countries that are not within the European Union. These exemptions give the ability for LEAs to be able to investigate, prevent or prosecute under

⁶³⁰ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019.

⁶³¹ See Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA

⁶³² *English* is to refer to the courts of England and Wales due to the jurisdiction of courts in the United Kingdom which separate the courts of Scotland and the Courts of Northern Ireland. The are exemptions in this matter, however, are limited to the cases that can be heard in the respective court.

⁶³³ [2020] EWCA Civ 1058

criminal offences, the *Bridges*' case highlighted the social and ethical resistances to automated systems that have not been appropriately integrated or elements that contain infringements upon an individual's Human Rights. The issues that were detailed within this case have added to the call for a re-assessment of how Artificial Intelligence is implemented, therefore, the calling of the Draft Artificial Intelligence Act 2021 (which does not have a remit within the UK) but will have a substantial effect on how AI is integrated regarding the Human Agency and Oversight characteristics.

Artificial Intelligence, especially with its use in law enforcement, can have a negative perception within public discourse; therefore, the implementation of such technologies should ensure they complement and empower human cognitive ability rather than replacing them.⁶³⁴ Providing this, Artificial Intelligence will coincide with the societal and ethical requirements called for within the Draft Artificial Intelligence Act when regarding the impact of such a system with a natural person.⁶³⁵ A Human Centric approach of producing Artificial Intelligence protects the requirements of Human agency as it prioritises the Human input in the development and dissemination of Artificial Intelligence into any country; with respect to specific country legal requirements. The approach to Human Centric AI was a European Union objective when implementing the Trustworthy AI Principles in 2019, a communication paper titled '*Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence*'⁶³⁶ aimed to distinguish the European perspective on Artificial Intelligence and its functionalities regarding Human Agency and the related principles detailed below found that Human Agency can be complied through a 'human-in-the-loop, human-on-the-loop, human-in-command-approach.'⁶³⁷ These techniques are known as 'oversight' and the less oversight the more testing and governance is required⁶³⁸ within Artificial Intelligence systems to ensure that compatibility of 'fundamental rights'⁶³⁹ and the 'wellbeing of the user.'⁶⁴⁰

The human input in any form regarding Artificial Intelligence is paramount to ensuring compliancy with fundamental rights and protecting the users that are exposed to artificial intelligence. LEAs have unique exemptions in the regard to using Artificial Intelligence, however, cannot extend to the point of breaching human rights as found in *Bridges*. The regular question if the specific technology that has been deployed is plausible should be a primary

⁶³⁴ Daugherty and Wilson. "Human + Machine: Reimagining Work in the Age of AI". Harvard Business Review Press, 2018

⁶³⁵ Article 52(1) Draft AI Act

⁶³⁶ European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on '*Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence*' 1

⁶³⁷ European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on '*Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence*' 4

⁶³⁸ European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on '*Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence*'

⁶³⁹ European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on '*Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence*'

⁶⁴⁰ European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on '*Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence*'

element into the assessments that are taken place. The ability to ensure compliancy can improve the understanding of public knowledge regarding Artificial intelligence and avoid any legal challenges.

14.2. Technical Robustness & Safety

The principle of technical robustness and safety turns to ensure that developers who have created a *reliable*⁶⁴¹, *resilient*, *accurate*, *reproduceable* and *verifiably safe* artificial intelligence system with an appropriate *fall-back plan*.⁶⁴² The plans that are introduced to mitigate any losses in the system should be designed to protect the rights and data of individuals by providing a security basis where penetration into the core code of the Intelligence system cannot be manipulated and utilised for misuse. The penalties referring to data leaks and access to information that could be found in storage could lead to actions by the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) or the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) if a member of the United Kingdom for example. This can result in weighted fines that can harm the political stature of a company plus the financial repercussions of failing to follow appropriate GDPR / Data Protection laws.

14.3. Privacy & Data Governance

As stated previously the concern for the protecting of data is paramount in the development, implementation, and deployment of Artificial Intelligence. The functionalities of Data Protection within the respective Member State (under LEA control) should be followed with all appropriate assessments being undertaken. The assessments regarding privacy and data refer to the Data Protection Impact Assessments which hold vital information regarding the plausibility of data protection within an Artificial Intelligence system. The European Union have found that they require the protection of data to be 'guaranteed at all stages'⁶⁴³ *Privacy by design* is a concept that can protect data within the set of Artificial Intelligence systems; this ensures privacy and provides an accountability framework as well.⁶⁴⁴ As stated previously the protection of Data in any form comes through the principles that are found within *Regulation 2016/679* or the "*General Data Protection Regulation*" which controls the uniform protection of personal data across the European Union's Member States. Artificial Intelligence developers should recognise their position as a controller for how information should be integrated throughout a system. This is to ensure the protection of Fundamental Rights but also to provide security to the AI systems presence within society; untrustworthy AI which threatens AI has been seen to

⁶⁴¹ European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on 'Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence'

⁶⁴² European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on 'Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence' 5

⁶⁴³ European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on 'Building Trust in Human-Centric Artificial Intelligence' 8th April 2019

⁶⁴⁴ Akgbar and others, *Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence in the Internal Security Domain* (February 2022)

be rejected by society. An example of possibly harmful and rejected Artificial Intelligence systems was highlighted in the *Bridges*' case regarding South Wales Police's AFR system.⁶⁴⁵

Privacy and the control of data are paramount in the access of Artificial Intelligence systems to the public. These factors have significant input on their presence within the functioning of society due to the sensitivity of Privacy and the requirements of developers and LEAs when installing systems. A damaging implementation of AI can have a lasting effect on society for all reproductions of such a system; this is done to protect privacy (especially in ARF) Artificial Intelligence systems, such as Facial Recognition systems in a publicly accessible space are in the process of a ban within Germany.⁶⁴⁶ After a challenge to Automatic Facial Recognition systems which were operated within Berlin Train Station.⁶⁴⁷ These challenges stemmed through the public pressure from the perspective of tablet newspapers across the European Union; particularly the moderate left-wing online tablet "*Politico*" who detailed LEA usage of ARF in Berlin Train Station as 'big brother'⁶⁴⁸ referring to the concept of dystopian totalitarianism in George Orwell's famous literature *1984*⁶⁴⁹. This details the importance of providing a secure system that protects Privacy and does not overstep what is accepted in society – but solely regarding the protection of privacy is paramount to gaining public trust, this discussion ascertaining to public trust and environmental concerns regarding the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in society continues in section 14.6 below.

Privacy restrictions in specific Member States create damaging possibilities when assessing the capabilities of Artificial Intelligence and how in some areas, fail to coincide with the requirements of a country's privacy regulations. The European Union is heavily controlled regarding the policies that are provided through the new Draft AI Act plus GDPR, however, countries can develop on these laws to protect Privacy further. GDPR, however, is a catalyst in the world of data protection – it has been argued that GDPR is the 'toughest privacy and security law in the world.'⁶⁵⁰ Alternatively a lot of areas of the world follow a similar or identical version of GDPR due the prestigiousness of the regulation. The control of data and privacy is at the forefront of Artificial Intelligence systems and requires LEAs to be fully aware of the possibilities of unwanted legal and public attention if issues were to emanate.

14.4. Transparency

The Trustworthy AI Guidelines define transparency as the ability to improve 'traceability, explainability and communication.'⁶⁵¹ This process is done with the intention of improving the

⁶⁴⁵ R (Bridges) v Chief Constable of South Wales Police & Information Commissioner [2020] EWCA Civ 1058

⁶⁴⁶ *Sozialdemokratischen Partei Deutschlands*, Mehr Fortschritt Wagen: Bündnis für Freiheit, Gerechtigkeit und Nachhaltigkeit 2021-2025

⁶⁴⁷ See *Chee* 'EU Privacy watchdogs call for Ban on Facial Recognition in Public Spaces' *Reuters* 21st Jun. 2021 < <https://www.reuters.com/technology/eu-privacy-watchdogs-call-ban-facial-recognition-public-spaces-2021-06-21/>>

⁶⁴⁸ See Delcker 'Big Brother in Berlin' *Politico* 13th Sep. 2018 < <https://www.politico.eu/article/berlin-big-brother-state-surveillance-facial-recognition-technology/>>

⁶⁴⁹ *Orwell* 'Nineteen Eighty-Four' London: Secker & Warburg, 1949

⁶⁵⁰ See *Woldford* 'What is GDPR, the EU's new Data Protection Law?' H2020 GDPR.eu <https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr>

⁶⁵¹ AI H-LEG, "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI", 8 April 2019.

ability to show the decisions in Artificial Intelligence systems and provide a stronger detailed analysis to any exposures; privacy violations, bias, discrimination, or data leaks. The AI Guidelines state that transparency should relate to the data that Artificial Intelligence collates, the system and any business model upon which it is integrated into. In regards for CYCLOPES, however, LEAs will be required to ensure that upon request that they can openly detail the reasoning for the collation for information, how the process is occurring and why any results are reached. This should refer to the system of AI itself, the core functions behind such a system, and the data that is being used in the AI for training, testing and operation.

Transparency benefits Artificial Intelligence as it provides users with knowledge regarding how they are interacting with an AI system.⁶⁵² Transparency is the act of providing insight and information regarding the system, this is a common issue which creates confusion and uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence within the public. Creating more of an open aspect of communication (which protects the presence of AI in the field) also adds to the public understanding and mitigates possible areas of scrutiny. The draft AI Act has a strong focus on Transparency while the AP4AI framework detailed Transparency as a catalyst for ‘promoting public trust and confidence by enabling those directly and indirectly affected, as well as the wider public, to make informed judgments and accurate risk assessments.’⁶⁵³

Transparency in Artificial Intelligence is a key element for LEAs in the implementation and usage of the recommendations provided by the CYCLOPES project; it is a core aim to protect all assets, stakeholders and data subjects in Artificial Intelligence systems. Nonetheless, it is also prudent to be aware that transparency of how a process works can unwittingly allow those wishing to exploit AI for criminal gain or disrupt law enforcement have a better understanding of how to do so. Therefore, the mechanism for transparency and the extent to which any information is made public is also of paramount importance.

14.5. Diversity, Non-Discrimination & Fairness

Providing a Diverse and Inclusive Artificial Intelligence System provides some mitigation against potential bias or discrimination which ultimately provides a strong foundation when functioning within society by providing societal fairness. The European Union see these characteristics of an AI system as paramount to ensure that systems coincide within the area of operation, especially when in the use for an LEA.

Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness are broad categories that are detailed by the European Commission as requirements to ensure that any ‘historic bias, incompleteness and bad governance’⁶⁵⁴ are mitigated to ensure that the exacerbation of prejudice and marginalisation of specific minorities is not fuelled.⁶⁵⁵ The Fundamental Rights Agency has highlighted that due to the complexity of algorithms the ability to remove complete bias is

⁶⁵² AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, 18

⁶⁵³ Akgbar and others, Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence in the Internal Security Domain (February 2022)

⁶⁵⁴ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, 18

⁶⁵⁵ AI H-LEG, “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019, 18

inherently difficult challenge, however, choosing the appropriate method in developing Artificial Intelligence can significantly improve upon the possibilities of bias.⁶⁵⁶ The ability to include accurate data with diverse and self-reflecting factors can significantly improve upon the alleged bias in Artificial Intelligence systems; this is due to a risk-mitigating framework. It has been argued that data can be easy to manipulate and produce a bias, therefore, by mitigating these factors it can be shown to provide a strengthened technology that respects data subjects.⁶⁵⁷ The ability to ensure that bias is mitigated, and the appropriate non-discriminatory data sets are implemented will ensure that unwanted controversy, crisis and challenges to these factors do not arise which are common in an LEA setting.⁶⁵⁸

Issues arising from fairness have also been argued to extend into false positives and negatives when utilising specific forms of Artificial Intelligence. The possibilities of bias in data sets that produce these instances of falsifying an individual. This creates an anomaly which can be detailed as an unfair decision within the AI system. These failures can also jeopardise the functionalities of the Artificial Intelligence if they are not appropriately identifying a data subject for example. This could have catastrophic results in a LEA setting regarding the functions of purpose of an AI. Alternatively, Ganor found that Algorithms can be carefully examined to reduce false positives and negatives.⁶⁵⁹ Ganor theorised the concept of an extreme incident occurring which could be due to the failings in positive or negative identifications of online content not appropriately identifying a terrorist to LEAs, which could have catastrophic repercussions.⁶⁶⁰

14.6. Societal & Environmental Well-Being

It is a requirement of Artificial Intelligence to be able to coincide with the 'environment and other sentient beings' as they hold ecological responsibility to protect the environment around them. Society should not be hindered by the presence of AI it should be uplifted and supported the presence of Humans that are integrated within its core functionalities. This also refers to the environment and sustainable – Artificial Intelligence should be prepared for the future and attempt to ensure that a carbon neutral or focused on providing a resource that does not exhaust the environment. In the LEA setting fortunately, these requirements would be hard to breach as the Artificial Intelligence used within an LEA setting would have a very limited impact upon the environment.

⁶⁵⁶ See *Fundamental Rights Agency* 'Getting the Future Right: Artificial Intelligence and Rights' European Union Agency, 2020.

⁶⁵⁷ See *Muller* Opinion on the 'European Union Economic and Social Committee on Artificial intelligence — The consequences of artificial intelligence on the (digital) single market, production, consumption, employment, and society' *Official Journal of the European Union* (2017)

⁶⁵⁸ See *Sampson and others*, *The Legal Challenges of Big Data Application in Law Enforcement Big Data for National Security* (2015) London: Elsevier

⁶⁵⁹ See *Ganor* *Artificial or Human: A New Era of Counter-Terrorism Intelligence?* *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 2019, 1-20

⁶⁶⁰ See *Ganor* *Artificial or Human: A New Era of Counter-Terrorism Intelligence?* *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 2019, 1-20

14.7. Accountability

Accountability in functions of AI is a mechanism to ensuring that the appropriate requirements above have been met and if not, who can be held responsible for developing Artificial Intelligence that does not equate to the appropriate ethical requirements. Accountability in Artificial Intelligence is a significant vacuum in the individual who should be held accountable from a legal perspective.

Accountability can be defined as the acknowledgement and assumption of responsibility for actions decisions and their consequences.⁶⁶¹ To provide the access to finding the responsible parties for negligence within a poorly designed AI system is found through breaking down the core requirements of Accountability. The Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence (AP4AI) found that there were 12 core functioning requirements that provide accountable artificial intelligence for LEAs in the EU Internal Security Domain –they extend and develop the understanding of accountability especially within the internal security domain. The twelve core principles identified to provide a primary source of legitimate accountability in artificial intelligence systems can be found as the following.⁶⁶²

- Legality,
- Universality,
- Pluralism,
- Transparency,
- Independence,
- Robust Evidence,
- Enforcability (including Redress),
- Compellability,
- Explainability,
- Constructivness,
- Conduct
- Learning Organisation

There is a concordance between AP4AI and the AI Guidelines regarding the principles, however, AP4AI develops upon the basic guideline requirements to ensure a full accountability framework. Accountability is a core element to providing a secure and functioning AI system which has an appropriate ability to interact in the appropriate legal environment of a Member State. An Artificial Intelligence system should be able to determine who is the accountable factor within their system upon improper implementation up to act of negligence, the developer, or the integrator of such a technology can easily be identified by following the core principles. Different factors in different scenarios can create multiple legal arguments for who has responsibility when things go wrong; however, the aim of the accountability principle and AP4AI is not to apportion blame or assign responsibility after an incident but to ensure that all

⁶⁶¹ See Thomas Reuters ‘Accountability Principles’ 2021 Practical Law
<<https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/w-014-8164>>

⁶⁶² Akgbar and others, *Accountability Principles for Artificial Intelligence in the Internal Security Domain* (February 2022)

appropriate safeguards have been put in place prior to implementation or procurement and that these oversight measures remain in place as long as the system is in operation.

The methodology presented within AP4AI provides a new understanding of accountability in the context of LEAs deployment of AI systems across the European internal security domain. In the past year, AP4AI has accelerated from the previously outlined cycles and has entered the phase of deploying an actionable software tool designed to incorporate the principles created by the AP4AI project. The principles are then incorporated into AI Accountability Agreements (AAA) which are designed to provide an assessment to AI. As it currently stands, AP4AI is at the forefront of improving compliance with upcoming regulation across Europe including the Integration of the new European standard for artificial intelligence (chapter 12. above). AP4AI is a useful tool in cybercrime investigations; especially for those deploying AI systems as determined by the future Artificial Intelligence Act. AI systems deployed within the area of combatting cybercrime will fall into the suggested ‘high-risk’ category as it will involve Law Enforcement (section 12.2.3 above). The usage of AP4AI can ensure that LEAs protect their interests and those of others.

The AP4AI principles as stated previously are designed to provide a greater understanding to the function of accountability in AI. The deployment of this software tool across the European Union will ensure that the pursuit of negating negligence and poorly designed AI systems would be enhanced through the implementation of such a tool. To do this, AP4AI employs the usage of an AI Accountability Agreement (AAA) which compiles all 12 principles into an operational

Figure 1 - AP4AI AI Accountability Agreement (AAA) process

setting. To employ such a method the AI Accountability Agreement will contain four baselines: *context*, *scope*, *methodology* and *accountability governance*. *Figure 1* highlights the phases of the AI Accountability Agreement process of which at each phase the 12 Principles of AP4AI must adopt and utilise them as a milestone to progress to the next stage.

The functionality of these AI Accountability Agreements can be a powerful tool across cybercrime investigation tools. LEAs can use this methodology through the usage of a software tool designed to embed an AAA into their practice. The LEA can then update their AI processes and procedures to ensure that they deploy an accountable AI system within the policing and security field.

15. Use of Automated Search Tools

Automated Search Tools are commonly used by LEAs to equate information that relates to criminal activities online. Automated Search Tools have been under the headlights of the law in recent years due to their possibility to infringe upon the rights of platform owners (Facebook, Twitter, Reddit etc.) to questions in data protection. This section will highlight the claims of using Automated Search Tools and how techniques are being implemented to mitigate any loss when referring to these tools commonly utilised in Europe.

Automated Search Tools are used in a Law Enforcement setting to collate information from web and social media sites which then can be utilised to combat cybercrime and terrorism related crimes. The capabilities of these tools can include collecting information from the surface web, deep web and the Dark Web with the ability to produce a profile of published content relating to a specific individual who could be partaking in illicit crime. The automated mass collation of data, however, can lead to issues referring to the protection of data as there could be significantly different impacts in mass collection compared to the collection of data by a singular LEA in a targeted investigation.⁶⁶³ This is due to factors of Human Agency and Oversight and the ability of this principle to mitigate any possibilities of data losses or infringements of data. As stated previously, however, LEAs do have exemptions as stated in section 14.1 above but those do not give the right to LEAs to be ‘above the law’ as stated in the first principle of the *Magna Carta*.⁶⁶⁴ A secondary issue when utilising Automated Search Tools can also be the conflict of Civil Law requirements (chapter 7. above). These tools have the capabilities to be present on specific social media or information retrieval websites that do not allow crawlers to be present which automatically search for information, however, as detailed in chapter 7. above, specific Terms of Service do not authorise the utilisation of these tools due to the concerns of data protection and rights to privacy.

Automated Search Tools can be seen as controversial but are an asset to the protection of fundamental freedoms and the protection of society. The CYCLOPES network is aware of the societal cost of poor implementation of such a tool if it was found to be infringing upon privacy, therefore, all recommendations of technologies including Automated Search Tools respect the requirements of Fundamental Rights and Data Protection.

⁶⁶³ With regard to the impact of mass surveillance see for example: Lyon, Surveillance, power, and everyday life, published in Avgerou/Mansell/Quah/SilverStone, *The Oxford Handbook of Information and Communication Technologies*, 2009; Surveillance and censorship: The impact of technologies on human rights, European Parliament, Directorate-General for External Policies, 2015.

⁶⁶⁴ The reference to the first 1215 Sealing of the *Magna Carter* by the UK Government which created a basis of law across the world when understanding the place of law in functioning society.

16. Conclusion

16.1. Summary

This Deliverable D7.7 has updated the legal and ethical framework presented in Deliverable D7.6 with relevant developments since July 2022. This overall SEL framework is applicable not only for the activities in the course of the CYCLOPES project but also for the identification of suitable automated tools to be filtered out in the innovation watch and research horizon scan for potential use in the course of cybercrime investigations. Both frameworks consist of a complex interplay between international and national layers of rules and regulations.

In chapters 3. – 12., the scrutiny of the international legal framework has been continued by updating the analysis of the relevant international treaties at global level of the United Nations as well as at regional level of the Council of Europe. Further, the in-depth examination of available rules and regulations at supranational level of the European Union has been updated.

In chapters 13. and 14. the ethical and societal framework for the use of automated tools in cybercrime investigations is outlined by identifying the ethical standard relevant for the CYCLOPES project and especially for the network of law enforcement agencies and practitioners to benefit from the innovation watch and research horizon scan, on the one hand, and by analysing and translating the seven soft law principles of the “Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence” for the use of artificial intelligence in the law enforcement environment in general and in the course of cybercrime investigations in particular.

16.2. Evaluation

The updated analysis here still presents a fragmented and challenging background for any technical solution which is to be applied EU-wide. The collection and preservation of electronic evidence as well as the use search crawlers by in the course of cybercrime investigations is predominantly determined by national law.

Only the legal frameworks for victims’ rights and data protection within the law enforcement ecosystem appear rather clear and coherent.

At the level of the European Union, the legislative process regarding electronic evidence has been completed and this new legal framework introduces much needed harmonisation and standardisation. In addition, the legislative process regarding the use of artificial intelligence is still pending, but already creates hope for further harmonisation and standardisation across all Member States. The emerging overall ‘bigger picture’ would seem to require a high degree of flexibility and room for adjustments for any automated tool considered for the use in cybercrime investigations throughout Europe so that the functionalities of its applications could be adjusted to the respective mandatory national legal requirements.

16.3. Future Work

The comprehensive societal, ethical and legal framework will be monitored closely and updated in the three remaining iterations of this report which will also include practical recommendations.

The 1st updated SEL report in this Deliverable D7.7 will help to prepare the identification of potential gaps and emerging requirements regarding important trainings for cybercrime investigators available within the law enforcement ecosystem the results of which will be presented in Deliverable D7.11.